

**A Mixed-Method Study into the Effect of a Well-known
British Luxury Brand's Training Practice on
Transforming its Frontline Employees into Brand
Ambassadors**

By

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Acknowledgements

Primarily, I would like to express my very great appreciation to Dr Leburn Rose not only for his support and guidance, but also for his motivation during this four-year DBA journey.

Meanwhile, I sincerely thank all the participants for their willingness to take part in this research at their spare time.

At last, I would like to take this chance to thank my family both in the U.K. and China, especially to my husband Simon, for their trust and encouragement.

Abstract

As the critical role of luxury frontline staff in luxury businesses cannot be underestimated, effective training activities are crucial for successful luxury brands as it affects their frontline employees' performance. However, there is little up-to-date evidence regarding this topic found in empirical studies, particularly the term 'brand ambassador' which until now has primarily been associated with external influencers. Therefore, this research examines the link between the use of training and the transformation of luxury frontline employees into brand ambassadors. A famous British luxury retailer has been chosen for this purpose, and a mixed-method research project was conducted in this company to evaluate its training policies and to identify the challenges, through in-depth interviews, observations, and questionnaires. The main findings indicate that the use of both in person training and an online learning platform have been adopted to enhance internal corporate communication across all levels of the selected luxury organisation. A partnership between the brand's retail trainers and its line managers has been introduced to create a learning atmosphere within the workplace. However, the reality of a lack of a training framework to systematically guide the chosen brand's retail trainers' daily work has been also identified. This would not only prevent the partnership between the brand's trainers and its line managers from being effective, but also damage the learning environment within the workplace. This study's contribution is a training model, which was developed based on the theories reviewed in this research and refined using this study's findings to make it fit within the current situation of the chosen luxury brand in practice. With the help of the proposed training framework, the chosen luxury brand could tackle the challenges to improve its training effectiveness. To the brand's frontline employees especially, they could be responsible for representing the brand at its best with changed behaviours and attitudes as a result of effective training practice. As currently the results of this research could only represent the situation of the chosen brand, a future study across more brands in the luxury sector is recommended.

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Chapter 1 - Introducing the Problem

1.1 Background and Introduction

The constant growth of the luxury market has been noticeable in recent years. According to a report by The Economist (2002, quoted in Husic and Cicic, 2009), it has dramatically grown ‘from \$20 billion in 1985 to \$68 billion in 2000’. This figure increased even more rapidly to ‘€1.2 trillion globally in 2017’ estimated by Bain & Company, a leading global management consulting firm (D’Arpizio *et. al.*, 2017). In Deloitte’s latest report on the development of the global luxury industry (2019), the earnings of the top 100 luxury companies internationally increased 14% from ‘\$217 billion’ in 2017 to ‘\$247 billion’ in 2018. These figures prove the tendency of the rapid growth of the luxury market. At the same time, it is noticed that most of the luxury firms shift their interest to the younger generations (D’Arpizio *et. al.*, 2017; Deloitte, 2019). There is no doubt that the market size of the luxury industry would expand significantly as the number of potential luxury consumers soars.

In spite of the increase in the consumption of luxury goods, few people have a clear understanding of what luxury really is. To many individuals, what matters most is ‘the symbolic meaning’ of the luxury brands (Hung *et al.*, 2011). Such as, Burberry’s trademark camel check has been negatively associated with ‘chavs’ (Mason and Wigley, 2013). As a result, the image of the luxury industry is poor due to the lack of understanding on the essence of the world of luxury. Only recently has the topic of Luxury Management received a small amount of attention from the public. Instead of only recognised by the brand logo, a luxury brand can be compared to a real human being with ‘its ancestors, history, cultural and geographical roots’, as a lot of luxury brands are named after their creators (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012). It is apparent that luxury brands are all unique due to their exclusive brand identities and values. By comparing with the traditional business principle of gaining the competitive advantages, the business models of luxury brands aim to ‘propose a world of its own in which consumers wish to immerse themselves’ (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012).

About enhancing the brand experience, the important role of storytelling in other business sectors has been widely recognised, as ‘many successful brands communicate with consumers through brand stories’ (Huang, 2010). It may also apply to the luxury brands, as ‘luxury is the expression of a taste, of a creative identity, of the intrinsic passion of a creator’ (Kapferer and Bastien, 2009). However, it is apparent that the messages from the luxury brands to their

consumers are more complex. Apart from the unique brand tradition, luxury brands aim to communicate with clients not only ‘the multisensory nature of the product’ (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012), but also brand-related dreams (Berthon *et al.*, 2009). Therefore, the impact of storytelling regarding luxury brands is critical not only in emotionally engaging with the consumers, but also in helping the brands build their exclusive and appealing brand identities.

In fact, a brand’s story is normally told by the brand’s frontline staff to the customers. Regarding the luxury world, the knowledge and skills of the frontline sales associates become far more significant as the messages through storytelling include ‘the mystery’ of the brand, ‘the spirit’ of the luxury boutique, ‘the nature of the product’ and ‘the narration that accompanies it’ (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012). It is apparent that there is an essential need to improve luxury brands frontline staff’s abilities to deliver the brand messages to the luxury clients appropriately. In general, on-the-job training interventions are normally adopted to ensure that employees have the knowledge and skills to perform their roles at work, as the significance of the corporate training interventions has already been strongly emphasised since the 90s (Facteau *et al.*, 1995; Thayer, 1997). There are other benefits of training that have also been discussed, which include maintaining company’s competitive advantages (Salas and Cannon-Bowers, 2001), improving organisational performance (Salas *et al.*, 2000), enhancing organisational learning (Koonce, 1997) and meeting the organisational goals and strategic objectives (Montesino, 2002). It is, therefore, apparent that luxury brands could adopt corporate training to translate the brand messages to the frontline brand ambassadors effectively.

For the purpose of this study, one of the well-known luxury brands around the world, has been chosen as a case to study in this research project. Based on the selected luxury company’s latest annual report (Burberry Group Plc, 2020), there are around 449 stores and 10,000 employees globally, and the company’s total revenue till the end of March in 2019 was £2.6 Billion. Established in 1856, this organisation has built its strong reputation by combining the brand’s unique British heritage and continuous innovations in brand development. At the same time, the correlation between the business vision and the training strategy is the other main focus of the company, as they offer the tailored training programmes to share the ‘key strategic shifts’ with its employees (Burberry Group Plc, 2019). Since 2006, it strategically aligned the brand business strategy with the adoption of digital platform (Milnes, 2015). They recharged the value of the brand’s heritage collection in 2009 through exposure on social media with a campaign which was called ‘the Art of the Trench’ (Milnes, 2015). The marketing campaign

was a big success; therefore, the chosen British luxury icon consistently updates its latest brand launch and the brand's messages on its social media channels. In 2018, the brand appointed a new Chief Creative Officer (Ogweng, 2018) as the former left the role after 17 years with the company (Fletcher, 2017). After the announcement, this chosen British luxury brand released a short documentary titled 'Inside the Lift' that featured short interviews with its staff, and its new Chief Creative Officer on social media platforms; and it generated over '264,000' views in total (Ogweng, 2018). As a result, it 'became the top digital luxury brand' (Milnes, 2015). Last but not least, this luxury organisation considers its employees as its 'primary asset' to 'nurture and invest in their development' (Burberry Group Plc, 2020). According to the brand's annual report for FY 2019/20, '87%' of the target population participated in the survey are 'proud' to work at this brand; and '82% motivated to go above what is expected' to make it successful (Burberry Group Plc, 2020).

1.2 Problem Statement

The researcher has been working at the chosen luxury brand as a part-time sales associate for over three years. During the days she worked there, tailored training sessions were scheduled on a monthly basis to prepare the brand's frontline employees with the latest knowledge of the company's business and the required work skills. Recently, the chosen luxury brand decided to utilise digital channels in its latest marketing campaign to engage more potential customers, which was a big strategic change. There were a few training sessions organised for this purpose at work. However, after returning from these courses, the researcher noticed some team member's frustrations at not being able to apply the newly acquired knowledge in their jobs. As a result of failing in delivering the correct brand message, the boutique in where the researcher was based received many complaints from the customers. It not only undermined some of the brand's frontline employees' confidence in representing the brand at work, but also damaged the brand's image in public significantly. This incident happened at work inspired the researcher to examine the success of the chosen luxury brand's current training practice, which were designed to deliver the knowledge of the brand's latest digital marketing campaigns. Through this, the researcher intended to understand what caused the ineffective training transfer and what could be changed to improve the training effectiveness at the chosen luxury brand.

1.3 Research Question

How effective are the training strategies practised by a luxury chain in the U.K. to deliver its innovative marketing strategies to its frontline staff? What changes can be implemented in regard to enhancing the effectiveness of the training design?

Sub Question 1

What are the training strategies regarding its alignment with the company's digital marketing campaigns and how effective are these strategies practised in the selected luxury brand?

Sub Question 2

What are the current challenges that the training department is facing for effectively translating the luxury brand's innovative marketing strategies to its frontline staff?

Sub Question 3

What changes can be implemented in regard to enhancing the effectiveness of the training design in the context of luxury?

1.4 Study Aims, Rationales and Objectives

After the research gap was identified, the researcher planned to undertake an exploratory study on the use of training in the implementation of the chosen luxury brand's latest marketing objectives.

The main research question of this study can be interpreted in three aspects. At the early stage of this research project, identification and evaluation were the two main focuses. That is, identifying the chosen luxury brand's current training practice, regarding the latest digital marketing campaign, as a start. Then, evaluating the effectiveness of these actions in achieving the learning objectives. As a result of the investigation into the detailed training initiatives, the challenges, which prevent these training sessions from successfully translating the brand's latest marketing objectives to its frontline employees, would be recognised. At last, some changes would be promoted for the purpose of solving the identified problems. Therefore, the objectives of this research project are presented as follows:

Objective 1

To evaluate the critical aspects of the selected luxury brand's training strategies aligned with its digital marketing campaigns.

Objective 2

To clarify the current challenges that the training department is facing regarding appropriately delivering the brand's digital marketing objectives to its frontline luxury staff.

Objective 3

To recommend the changes, which could be implemented in training design, to improve the training effectiveness in the luxury brands.

1.5 Structure of this Study

There are five chapters in this study. In the first chapter, a brief introduction was made to provide readers with the information of the current development of the luxury business sector and the chosen luxury brand of this study. At the same time, a problem statement is presented with the reasons why the researcher is interested in devoting her time and effort to this research project. Then, the main research question was explained in detail.

The second chapter consists of two parts, which are the literature review and restatement of the problem. Firstly, the literature review section was further divided into two sections; one focused on the area of organisational training while the other one gave a lot of attention to the topic of luxury management. It aims to critically review the current knowledge on the chosen area of this study. Through the discussions made on the evidence the researcher collected from the empirical research projects, the readers will grasp a better understanding on these two areas. The research gap between the previous studies and this research project was examined as the result of critically reviewing the relevant literature in the field. In the meantime, reading also enriched the researcher's knowledge about the topic. Therefore, some changes were made regarding the scope of the main research question. They are presented and justified in the section of the problem restatement in this chapter.

In the third chapter, there are also two parts included. In the first section, this study's theoretical framework was formed with the theories collected from the reviewed literature. Through the explanations of this framework, the researcher presented her understandings on the research

topic. Then, the justifications for the choices regarding research methodology were discussed in the second section of the third chapter.

Chapter Four is dedicated to data collection and data analysis. In this chapter, the data is presented while the chosen data collection and data analysis methods are identified. The findings of this research were also discussed in this chapter regarding the current situation of training in the selected luxury company and its training initiatives. At the same time, the findings of this study also provided the researcher with more insights in designing a training framework which is dedicated to not only the chosen luxury brand but also the luxury industry. At the end of this chapter, the evolution of this training model is presented.

The purpose of Chapter Five is to conclude this research. Apart from reviewing the whole journey of this study, the researcher also made some recommendations to the chosen British luxury brand to adapt the training framework, which is promoted as a contribution that the researcher made to the luxury business sector. Furthermore, the opportunity of conducting some further research on this subject is suggested while the limitations of this research are also presented.

Chapter 2 - Literature Review & Problem Restatement

2.1 Literature Review

2.1.1 Introduction

In this section, the researcher critically reviewed the literatures about both organisational training and the luxury business sector. As this research project was designed to explore the training practice in the luxury industry, the term 'training' and 'luxury' are the two keywords to be examined in the following paragraphs.

The first part of the literature review is about training. It aims to provide readers with the knowledge of the general training design models in theory and the debates about the key aspects of a training framework from the empirical studies. Before readers reach the part about training design, they will start from the arguments among the various definitions of the term 'training'. Then the focus switches from the general learning activities to organisational training programs in particular. It follows with the arguments over the role of the training function at work. As it is a hot topic that has been continuously discussed by many scholars in the field, the various understandings are discussed by categories, such as the role in gaining competitive advantages, the strategic alignment and the influence on employee development. It follows with different types of training activities that would normally be adopted by an organisation. Next, three different training models are compared and presented to readers. These three frameworks not only have the dominant position in the training field but also inspired the researcher on designing her training model in this research project. It follows with the critical reviews collected from previous studies on five components that are generally believed as the main stages in a training circle, which are training needs assessment, training design and delivery, organisational learning environment, transfer of training and training evaluation. By critically discussing each element one by one, readers could clearly recognise the correlations among all of them.

The second part of the literature review is about luxury. It aims to provide readers with the knowledge about the luxury industry and its training strategies. It starts from the arguments about the definition of the term 'luxury'. Although it is not a new concept, the understandings

on what does luxury mean vary from person to person. Then it follows with the differences that distinguish luxury brands from the others in the market. Two of the main business models applied in most of the luxury brands are reviewed and compared. It follows with the diamond business model designed by Louis Vuitton to provide readers with a real case to deepen their understandings on luxury business strategies from a business perspective. As it is also critical to review the uniqueness of the luxury market from a consumer's perspective, the different types of potential luxury clients are discussed by categories. It follows with the comparisons among three models on luxury consumption values; and then the psychology of the luxury consumers is discussed. The following part gives a lot attention on the impact of internal branding on transforming the luxury frontline employees into brand ambassadors in the luxury business. Firstly, the term 'brand ambassador' has been placed in the context of luxury businesses. Instead of having an external celebrity or influencer paid to represent a brand in public, it is believed the role of the luxury frontline employees play in sharing a luxury brand's unique image with the customers is more critical in this study. Therefore, the importance of the internal branding on improving luxury frontline employees' competencies to represent the luxury business at its best is discussed. As the internal corporate communication has been recognised as a critical tool to enhance the effect of internal branding by some scholars, the link between the use of internal communication and a transformation of a luxury frontline employee into a brand ambassador is demonstrated. Then, training practise in some luxury brands is examined. At last of the section of literature review, the research gap is identified and discussed.

2.1.2 Perspectives on the Topic of Training

2.1.2.1 The Definitions of Training

The formal definition of the term 'training' is 'a planned process to modify attitude, knowledge or skill behaviour through learning experience to achieve effective performance' (Manpower Services Commission, 1981, quoted in Wilson, 2005, p.4). Similarly, Goldstein and Ford (2002, p.1) explain it as 'the systematic acquisition of skills, rules, concepts, or attitudes that result in improved performance'. It appears that both of these two definitions describe training as a learning tool that can be applied to implement a change.

Although the learning feature within the process of training has been emphasised (Garavan, 1997, quoted in Wilson, 2005, p.8), the doubt about the link between training and learning has been raised at the same time (Salas *et al.*, 2012). On one hand, it is believed that 'learning is

training' (Antonacopoulou, 2001, quoted in Reed and Vakola, 2006). On the other hand, it is suggested that the aims of these two are different. According to Tannenbaum and colleagues (1993), learning activities can be simply conducted to gain knowledge aimlessly, but the purpose of training is to have attitudes, behaviour or performance changed as a result. By interpreting their views, a training activity is far more complicated than learning. By comparison, learning is only a cognitive process, which is not guaranteed to result in a behavioural or performance change. However, a well-planned training program is designed to achieve a certain learning goal. In other words, 'training involves learning' (Bramley, 2003, p.3) and could 'facilitate learning' at the same time (Bray, 2006, p.4). When it comes to define training in the context of business environment, it could be understood as 'job-related.... knowledge-based learning' activities (Noe *et al.*, 1997, quoted in Bunch, 2007). By taking both the feature of learning and change into consideration, a training program could be recognised as a learning activity that is designed to bring changes in trainees' skills, attitudes, and performance in the working environment.

2.1.2.2 Training and Organisation

a The Role of the Training Function

Some scholars believe that the concept of training has been narrowly defined, as in their opinions, the role of training in an organisation is more complicated than only enhancing learning at work. Firstly, the effect of on-the-job training has been linked to competitive organisational success in business. For example, Knoke and Kalleberg, (1994) recognise training as an approach for employees to adapt to the changes, such as 'organisational restructuring, market competition and technological innovation', in order to keep a company staying competitive in the market. Regarding the role of training in achieving organisational success, some evidence demonstrates it from a different perspective, for example, its influence on business performance (Aguinis and Kraiger, 2009) or 'organisational development' (Sammut, 2001). The results are both positive. However, the concern over whether or not this rule would be applied by all companies is raised. For example, Sonia Carey (2000, p.19) suggests that the relationship between the use of training and sustaining competitiveness would only work in multinational companies, because there was not any evidence found to prove its possibility in small-sized companies yet. In sum, it is widely believed that the use of training could offer companies great values in achieving organisational success. But at the same time, there is little evidence found in the previous studies to examine the applicability of this statement in the real cases.

Secondly, the strategic alignment of training has been discussed in many previous studies. For example, Salas and Cannon-Bowers (2001) consider training as an ‘integrated, strategic component of the organization’ instead of ‘a separate, stand-alone event’. Similarly, Goldstein (1980) also regards training as ‘a system within work organizations rather than simply treating instruction as a separate technology’. At the same time, some scholars explain how to align on-the-job training activities with a company’s business strategies in detail, for example, to communicate ‘organizational goals to new personnel’ (Arthur Jr *et al.*, 2003); to ‘reflect company policy and strategic direction’ (Carey, 2000, p.19). However, the results of some research projects reveal the disappointing state of training in some organisations. Despite the suggestions about its strategic alignment, ‘training is regarded as a cost rather than a core function and is therefore not a strategic consideration and is susceptible to cutbacks’ (Carey, 2000, p.20). Likewise, Sloman (2017, p.64) also experienced disappointment, as he could only find a limited number of cases which successfully recognised the relationship between the use of training and the implementation of corporate strategies. Obviously, the strategic integration of training has not gained enough attention in practice. Although this might be the case in most of the organisations, there is no denying that organisational training plays a vital role in communicating a company’s business strategy to different levels of its employees.

While some scholars emphasise training’s positive influence on organisational success, others give attention to its possible impact on a human capital of a company, as training is considered as ‘an organizational investment in its employees’ (Farrell and Rusbult, 1981). The reason that the on-the job training program is worth the investment is because it could ‘add value to the employees’ (Nikandrou *et al.*, 2009). To understand the influence of training from employee’s perspective, it could improve their ‘interpersonal and communications skills’ (Sharma and Patterson, 1999); decrease ‘the error rate’ (Aragón-Sánchez *et al.*, 2003) and develop their ‘creativity-relevant skills’ (Amabile, 1988). However, it could not just simply link the role of training to employee’s skill enhancement. A correlation of organisational training and the plan on managing a company’s human assets was studied. There is some evidence also positively suggests that training could result in enhancing employee satisfaction (Louis *et al.*, 1983), ‘employee retention’ (Huselid, 1995) and ‘job commitment’ (Aragón-Sánchez *et al.*, 2003). It is apparent that their views have broadened the role of training in the workplace by considering its significant impact on human capital within organisations.

While some researchers recognise the positive impacts that training activities could have on an organisation, others criticise it. This phenomenon was quite common in the 1980s. For example, Mangham and Silver (1986, quoted in Buckley and Caple, 2009, p.14) doubt whether or not there would be a positive impact of training on organisational performance, as they claim that ‘some companies which were doing no training at all were as likely to be successful as those who did a great amount’. It is understandable that some organisations could not fully recognise the benefits of training under the business environment in the 1980s. However, the situation seemingly remains the same in the 21st century, as the evidence reveals some negative reality. For example, some company’s training practice has been reviewed as ‘ridiculously silly...and insultingly disrespectful of the workers’ intelligence...’ (Panchak, 2004). Meanwhile, the results of Montesino’s research (2002) demonstrate that on-the-job training failed to deliver the organisation’s strategic direction due to the poor performance of some training. Pont (2003) explained the reason why training programs could not perform effectively in some organisations as they failed to conduct trainings ‘on a continuous basis’. Although those findings are quite depressing, the significant impact of training on achieving organisational effectiveness has been widely accepted by both scholars and practitioners. There is no denying that training is a worthwhile investment instead of an unnecessary cost. Furthermore, it is suggested to view the role of training in organisations from a broader perspective, as ‘the effects of training activities are different depending on the dimension they are related to’ (Aragón-Sánchez *et al.*, 2003).

b Different Types of on-the-job Training

Based on the book ‘Human Resource Management’ (Dias, 2011), there are eight different types of training, which are ‘technology training, quality training, skill training, soft skill training, professional & legal training, team training, managerial training and safety training’. The types of training vary with the training goals. The first four types of training are designed to enhance employees’ skills and knowledge related to job in order to improve employee’s competencies at work. For example, quality training provides employees with sufficient knowledge about quality standards, as customers nowadays are becoming increasingly knowledgeable about the products and services (Brockhoff, 2003). Moreover, technology training is necessary as both Dias (2011) and Noe (2010) identify the significant influence of new technology on shaping work roles and changing job requirements. Thus, these four types of training activities play a significant role in optimising a company’s performance, as Noe (2010, p.5) mentions ‘employees’ job-related competencies are critical for successful job performance’. In addition,

professional training is for the professionals to refresh their skills on an ongoing basis to keep competent in the field. As Noe (2010, p.5) believes that training programs would affect a company's intellectual capital, in this case, professional and legal training are suitable for achieving such purpose. Furthermore, team training is for enhancing employees' capabilities of working collaboratively at work, while managerial training is designed to improve leadership skills of the management team. At last, the purpose of safety training is for raising the awareness of safety at work. It appears that all the training programs are indispensable. Therefore, it would be better if organisations would cross different types of training with blended approaches to motivate their employees on self-growth and future development in various work roles.

2.1.2.3 Models for Training

In this section, three main training models are critically reviewed. They are the traditional systematic model, the revised systematic model and the transitional model, which reflect the most effective principles on training design that could result in delivering best training practice at the time.

The systematic training model has had a great impact on the development of training function in organisations, as Martyn Sloman (2017, p.21) considers it as the most representative training model that 'has shaped the approach to training since the 1960s'. It aims to provide organisations with the systematic principles in developing and delivering training activities. This model includes a sequence of steps to guide trainers at work. It is a cyclical process, which includes 'development of training policy, identification of training needs, development of training objectives and plans, implementation of planned training and validation, evaluation and review of training' (Sloman, 2017, p.21). Later, it is simplified to cover four major steps as shown in Figure 2-1, which are 'identify training needs, plan and design training, deliver training and evaluate training outcomes' (Sloman, 2017, p.22). The training process is undoubtedly a continuous loop, as the feedback from the last training session could provide trainers with some valuable clues to identify the needs for the next training. Meanwhile, the idea of organising a training session by following a systematic sequence of principles could ensure the consistency of the delivery of effective training in practice. However, it seems that this four-step training framework is too simple to show the interdependent relationships among the different stages. There should be multiple interactions among various steps instead of only a single loop.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Sloman, 2017.

Figure 2-1. The Systematic Training Model

(quoted in Sloman, 2017, p.22)

This idea is also supported by Kenney and Reid (1992, quoted in Sloman, 2017, p.21). Therefore, they restructured the systematic training model by adding more links between the stage of training evaluation and other steps. It appears that they place the emphasis on the significant impact of evaluation on different stages in the loop, as shown in Figure 2-2. By doing this, it ensures the effective training delivery as the session is designed to evaluate the feedback from all stages in the loop continuously. Although neither the traditional nor the restructured systematic model could be regarded as the most perfectly structured training framework in the field, both of them do not only provide practitioners with theoretical support, but also inspire them with the insights into the importance of validating the effectiveness of each step within a training circle.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Sloman, 2017.

Figure 2-2. The Restructured Systematic Training Model

(quoted in Sloman, 2017, p.21)

Apart from Kenny and Reid, Harry Taylor (1991, quoted in Sloman, 2017, p.24) also argues against the validity of the original version of the systematic training model, as he considers it to be too theoretical to be applied in practice. At the same time, he also criticises its effectiveness for failing to align training objectives to an organisation's strategic goals (Taylor, 1991, quoted in Sloman, 2017, p.24). As a contribution, Taylor also revised the traditional systematic training model by defining the training framework in the context of corporate strategy. In the transitional model that Taylor promotes, there are two interdependent circles. The inner loop is the systematic model, and the outer one relates to an organisation's business strategy, such as mission, vision and values, as shown in Figure 2-3 (Sloman, 2017, p.24). However, there are also arguments over the feasibility of this transitional model, as it is considered as 'far more creative and intuitive' but 'less specific' when it comes to apply it in practice; the model 'does not offer practical guidance for practitioners' (Sloman, 2017, p.25). There is no denying that this revised transitional training model aligns the training development with companies' business objectives to emphasise that a training circle could not function independently. It reminds company's trainers to take company's business strategies into consideration when it comes to the training needs assessment.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Sloman, 2017.

Figure 2-3. A Transitional Model

(quoted in Sloman, 2017, p.25)

2.1.2.4 Main Stages in a Training Circle

a Training Needs Assessment

The process of identifying a training need has been recognised as ‘one of the most important steps in training development’ (Salas and Cannon-Bowers, 2001), without it, ‘training sessions can be ill-conceived and worthless’ regarding ‘organizational effectiveness’ (Peterson, 1998, p.6). Despite its importance, the reality reveals a disappointing result that ‘it does not often take place and is often not done in organisations’ (Reed and Vakola, 2006). Even so, there is no denying that the training needs analysis plays a significant role in ensuring the quality of a training session. Therefore, it is recognised as one of the critical stages in a training circle in this study.

Then, how to define a training needs assessment? It is explained as a process to identify the necessity of delivering a specific training session to a group of target audiences (Goldstein and Ford, 2002). In other words, a training needs assessment is ‘the process of deciding who and what should be trained’ (Salas and Cannon-Bowers, 2001). Apart from this view, it is also discussed from different perspectives. For example, the explanation given by Arthur Jr and his colleagues (2003) focuses on various possible training needs, i.e. some problem that needs to be solved or a specific organisational goal that requests to be translated and communicated to its different levels of employees. Furthermore, the definition contributed by Robyn Peterson (1998, p.6) emphasises the importance of the act of assessing, as it ‘demands care, attention to detail, and a determination to search for the performance facts and their implications’. However, it concerns some scholars that it might be ‘costly’ and ‘time-consuming’ (Buckley and Caple,

2009, p.76). Despite this, it cannot be denied that the training needs analysis is a valuable approach that would have an influence on achieving training effectiveness.

Then, what actions should be taken during the process of a training needs assessment? The evidence collected in this study demonstrates a gradual process of change in people’s understandings. Firstly, a three-approach training needs analysis was developed by Kenny and Reid (1992, quoted in Buckley and Caple, 2009, p.76), which consists of ‘comprehensive analysis, key-task analysis and problem-centred analysis’, clearly shows the emphasis on the assessment on the job-related tasks. Then, the focus switched. Instead of only taking tasks into consideration, the idea of analysing an organisation as a whole is promoted by Goldstein in 1993 (Tannenbaum *et al.*, 1993). At last, a suggestion about identifying a training need from a broader perspective made public, which takes organisational analysis, task analysis and personal analysis into consideration (Arthur Jr *et. al.*, 2003). From the task-oriented approach to a focus on organisational development, and then aligning a company’s human assets with its values and vision becomes the main focus. This gradual change in training needs assessment indicates that the emphasis on business changed over time. This evolution also reflects on the public’s attitudes towards the role of training in business (see Table 2-1).

Kenny & Reid (1992)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Comprehensive Analysis ○ Key-task Analysis ○ Problem-centred Analysis
Goldstein (1993)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Organisational Analysis
Arthur Jr, Bennett Jr, Edens and Bell (2003)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Organisational Analysis ○ Task Analysis ○ Personal Analysis

Table 2-1. Different suggestions on how to assess training needs

Furthermore, some evidence also clarifies the correlations between the training needs assessment and other steps that are included in a training circle. For example, the results of a training needs analysis would affect the development of a training program, i.e. training design and the choice on training methods (Goldstein and Ford, 2002). Meanwhile, it would have an influence on both training delivery and training evaluation (Arthur Jr *et. al.*, 2003). Meanwhile, it would enhance the effectiveness of training transfer (Tannenbaum *et al.*, 1993). It appears

that training needs assessment is ‘a valuable component of any continuing effort to achieve performance improvement’ (Peterson, 1998, p.6). At the same time, it also emphasises the fact that training is an on-going process.

b Training Design & Delivery

Before the training design takes place, some evidence collected from empirical research suggests identifying training objectives to trainers. This is because training objectives have been considered as not only ‘guidelines for course design’ but also ‘a link between training needs and the training...so that the training can be validated’ (Buckley and Caple, 2009, p.127-128). The opinion on the value of training objectives is widely accepted, for example, Thorne and Mackey (2003) and Pont (2003). Therefore, ‘objectives must be clearly defined’ before start planning a training (Pont, 2003, p.21). Once the training objectives are identified, it comes to the stage of training design. Developing a training session is not effortless, but a decision-making process to ensure the most suitable ‘forms of learning’ would be adopted (Buckley and Caple, 2009, p.185). As what demonstrated in Figure 2-4, a trainer needs to take many factors into consideration. Those factors not only relate with each other in the process of training design, but also have an impact on the decision-making process.

*Figure 2-4. Interaction of Factors that Influence the Design of Training
(Buckley and Caple, 2009, p.186)*

Two training strategies that are reviewed by Buckley and Caple (2009, p.189), which are ‘trainer-centred strategy and learner-centred strategy’, are worth particular attention. As what their names indicate, the emphases of these two training strategies are different. The trainer has control of the training design process if the former is applied, for example, ‘the pace, tactics,

sequence... of the training’; while trainees would also take part in designing a session with trainers together and give voice to any decision made during the training design process when ‘learner-centred strategy’ is adopted (Buckley and Caple, 2009, p.189). Between them, some scholar shows the interest in the latter as it is believed that learners know better of their preferred learning methods (Sloman, 2017). Despite this, it is clear that both of them have their own advantages, therefore, trainers need to have the capability to pick the most suitable one under different circumstances. Furthermore, it is suggested to get line managers involved in the process of design, as it is the way to ensure not only the quality of training but also ‘committed attendance from subordinates’ (Sloman, 2017, p.135).

As the relationships among different factors are shown in Figure 2-4, the choice of training strategy would impact the decision on training methods and the arrangement of training content. Once a training session is planned and developed, it comes to the stage of training delivery. In this study, the STAR model (Bray, 2006, p.136) is introduced to discuss the process of delivering a training session.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Bray, 2006.

Figure 2-5. STAR Training Model

(Bray, 2006, p.136)

As shown in Figure 2-5, STAR refers to ‘stimulate, transfer, apply and review’ respectively (Bray, 2006, p.136). As these four words imply, the STAR training design model takes a training process from stimulating the trainee’s interest ‘from the initial contact’, to ‘transfer’

the training content from ‘your brain to theirs’, to give trainees opportunities to ‘apply’ what was taught through activities, to ‘review what’s changed as a result of the experience’ at the final stage of learning (Bray, 2006). This is a comprehensive model, as all four components that are included require the inputs from both trainers and trainees. On one hand, trainers need to be knowledgeable about creating an engaging environment and the most preferred learning styles of the target population; on the other hand, trainees have a better understanding of the importance of learning at work. On reflection, it appears that there is a correlation between the two training strategies introduced by Buckley and Caple (2009) and the STAR training model (Bray, 2006). Therefore, the latter would provide trainers with the guidelines to ensure an effective training session delivered.

In the meantime, some evidence collected from empirical research identifies the relationships between training design and other steps that are included in a training circle. For example, Smith and colleagues (1997) recognise the critical role of training design strategy plays in enhancing the acquisition and retention of the training skills and knowledge in their research. Likewise, Holton III and colleagues (2000) confirm that the choice on training design methods would affect not only the learning environment but also training transfer.

c Organisational Learning Environment

The term ‘learning organisation’ has caught a significant amount of attention from scholars. Due to its importance to the idea of building a supportive learning environment in an organisation, a gradual shift in the context of the term ‘learning organisation’ over time is discussed with the evidence collected from the empirical literature. Firstly, the idea of learning organisation was built based on the ‘Quality of Work Life Movement’, therefore, it emphasised a conception of ‘collective participation by... workers, in developing new patterns of work, career paths, and arrangements for combining family and work lives’ (Argyris, 1999, p.2). Then the focus shifted from individual-centred to the development of an organisation. This is because organisations are required to develop themselves continuously in order to keep their competitive advantages in the market. Therefore, the possible results of learning organisation could be more transparency in not only ‘production process’ but also ‘the performance of the organization as a whole’ across all levels of a company (Hayes *et al.*, 1988). Ultimately, it is considered as ‘a fundamental mind shift’ (Jones and Hendry, 1994). In other words, ‘people continually expand their capacity to create the results they truly desire, where new and

expansive patterns of thinking are nurtured, where collective aspiration is set free, and where people are continually learning how to learn together' (Senge, 2006).

Furthermore, the term 'learning organisation' has been defined by several scholars based on their different understandings. Some of them explain it in terms of the effectiveness of the organisational training. For example, Sloman (2017, p.33) considers it as 'an expression of the desired or ideal state for training in the organisation'. However, it is suggested that the concept of learning organisation should not only limit to the context of the training activities but 'a continuous process' or a better way of work (Barham *et al.*, 1988). In sum, the essence of 'learning organisation' is concluded as 'a climate of continuous learning and improvement' within an organisation (Pedler *et al.*, 1996). In other words, a learning organisation 'facilitates the learning of its members and continually transforms itself' (Pedler *et al.*, 1996).

Then, what is the relationship between creating a learning organisation and building an organisational learning environment? The evidence collected from the empirical studies indicates the link between them. For example, it is suggested that the former is as important as the latter (Argyris, 1999, p.4). That is, a learning culture is considered as 'the ideal of a learning organization' (Schein, 1992). In other words, the company culture of a learning organisation should be supportive, regarding the learning activities at work. This is because, the decision on creating a learning organisation is 'reflected in its corporate vision and business objectives which are communicated to, and shared by, its members at all levels' (Buckley and Caple, 2009, p.11). As a result, the senior managers of a learning organisation would commit to 'create and sustain such a culture' (Schein, 1992) through offering comprehensive learning opportunities and resources to its employees at all levels to motivate them to learn actively at work. Therefore, it appears that building a supportive learning environment within an organisation is one of the critical factors in the training circle.

Then how would a learning environment affect the effectiveness of training programs at work? Firstly, its impact on motivating trainees to actively take part in a training session is suggested (Buckley and Caple, 2009, p.201). It would also influence 'the acquisition phase during the training and the application phase in the transfer setting' (Goldstein and Ford, 2002, p.85). In other words, a supportive learning company culture would prepare trainees with the active learning mindset and take the responsibility to learn and apply the new knowledge to the jobs. Therefore, there is a correlation between the effective training practice and a supportive

company culture in the workplace. Although the purpose of building a learning organisation is not only for enhancing successful training programs in the workplace, but a learning environment at work would also contribute to achieving training effectiveness.

d Transfer of Training

According to the evidence, the importance of investing in employee training and development has been widely accepted by most of the organisations in the market (Montesino, 2002). However, the results of some research studies regarding the actual situation of training transfer are disappointing. For example, only '40 percent of the skills acquired during the training process are immediately transferred at work' (Burke and Baldwin, 1999); 'low return on training investment' (Montesino, 2002); 'high failure rates' of transfer of training (Anthony and Norton, 1991); '51%' and '47%' of training expenditure returned on employees' behavioural changes and organisational improvement (Saks, 2002). Undoubtedly, the problem of how to achieve training effectiveness exists.

But, how to define a successful training transfer? It is generally understood as a process in which trainees effectively apply newly learnt knowledge to their jobs after returning from a training session (Baldwin and Ford, 1988). However, some evidence suggests that training transfer is more complicated than only using new information at work after a training course. For example, Blume and colleagues (2010) promote the idea of considering 'generation' and 'maintenance' as two dimensions of training transfer. On one hand, 'generation requires trainees to exhibit trained behaviours in response to different settings' at work; on the other hand, 'maintenance issues focus on the changes that occur in the form or level of knowledge, skills, or behaviours exhibited in the transfer setting' (Blume *et al.*, 2010). It is clear that these two dimensions of the transfer of training represent two different levels of the transferring process. The former could be understood as an immediate transfer, which would occur as soon as trainees returned work from a session, while the latter refers to a long-term transfer, which would take some time as its success would depend on trainee's attitude change. Regarding this long-term attitude change, Goldstein and Ford (2002, p.86) link it to trainee's competence. Thus, if a trainee is confident in applying the learnt knowledge to the job, he/she would be capable of modifying the knowledge to meet different needs flexibly. Therefore, transfer of training could not be only considered as a process of applying what was learnt from training to the job, but a chance to improve the trainee's degrees of competence in performing the tasks at work.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Baldwin and Ford, 1988.

Figure 2-6. A Model of the Transfer Process

(Baldwin and Ford, 1988)

Then, what are the possible factors that may influence the effect of training transfer? A model of the transfer process that is introduced by Baldwin and Ford (1988) is worth the attention (see Figure 2-6). As Figure 2-6 indicates, both trainee characteristics and work environment, these two factors, would have a direct effect on training transfer. Clearly, the trainee plays a significant role in the process of transferring training, as trainees are ‘the basic inflow of the training system’ (Nikandrou *et al.*, 2009). Although the importance of trainees in training transfer has been widely accepted in the academic field, the interpretations of the trainee’s influence vary from person to person. For example, there are some debates about whether or not trainee’s intelligence would play a critical role in an effective training transfer. This issue has been examined in the field of education, and the result shows ‘students with higher general ability scores’ could be more possible to transfer what they learnt to their studies (Clark and Voogel, 1985, quoted in Burke and Hutchins, 2007). In the business context, on the other hand,

the findings of a 20-year research also identify the positive correlation between trainee's intelligence and effective training transfer result (Colquitt *et al.*, 2000). However, the findings of Lemke and colleagues' study (1974) reveal an opposite result as they found some 'low-ability' individuals have 'better transfer performance' (quoted in Burke and Hutchins, 2007). Therefore, it is too limited by only taking the intelligence into consideration when it comes to understand the trainee's influence on training transfer. Apart from trainee's intelligence, the impact of trainee's self-efficacy has also been discussed. On one hand, some scholars positively confirm its influence, for example, Gist, Schwoerer and Rosen (1989); Chiaburu and Marinova (2005); Gaudine and Saks (2004). On the other hand, others gave an opposite reply. For example, it is suggested that trainee's self-efficacy could not act directly on the effect of training transfer, instead it could be viewed as self-motivation that might have an influence on training transfer indirectly (Tannenbaum *et al.*, 1993; Axtell *et al.*, 1997). It seems that the role of high self-efficacy could be recognised as a motivation in successfully performing the job with newly acquired knowledge. At last, some academics also consider trainee's personality as one factor that would have a direct influence, for example, inquisitive personality (Seyler *et al.*, 1998); 'openness to experience' (Colquitt *et al.*, 2000). By contrast, someone even denies the relationship between trainee's personality and conditions of transfer (Miles, 1965, quoted in Baldwin and Ford, 1988). It seems that it would be too extreme to refuse to recognise the possibility that trainee's personality might impact the effect of training transfer. But its influence may be indirect (Ford and Weissbein, 1997). In sum, it would be better to taking all the potential trainee characteristics that might affect the transfer of training into consideration, as individuals are different.

Regarding the relationship between transfer climate and training transfer, the opinions also vary from person to person. On one hand, it is recognised as 'the single most important factor' would affect the effect of training transfer (Baumgartel and Jeanpierre, 1972, quoted in Seyler *et al.*, 1998). On the other hand, some researcher disagrees with overemphasising its significance. For example, it is viewed as a factor that may have a 'greater' effect on training transfer than other elements (Rouillier and Goldstein, 1993, quoted in Russ-Eft, 2002). It appears that its vital role in achieving an effective training transfer has been well acknowledged. But how would it affect the outcomes of training transfer? The evidence also provides some clues. Firstly, it is suggested that the 'highly humane-oriented organizational culture' could motivate employees in the process of training transfer (Kabasakal and Bodur, 2004). This statement is supported by many researchers, for example, Tannenbaum, Methieu, Cannon-

Bowers and Salas (1993); Holton III, Bates and Ruona (2000) and Nikandrou, Brinia and Bereri (2009). Secondly, the influence of ‘supervisory or peer’ is emphasised (Baldwin and Ford, 1988), as it is believed that its role is to ‘minimize obstacles or constraints’ to ensure a successful training transfer (Goldstein and Ford, 2002, p.86). Although this idea is not an assumption but was examined in some research studies, for example, Ford, Quiñones, Sego and Sorra (1992) and Tracey, Hinkin, Tannenbaum, and Mathieu (2001); some scholars still doubt its credibility, for example, Axtell, Maitlis and Yearta (1997). Alternatively, it is suggested that the impact of the managerial supports on the effective training transfer has been exaggerated (Seyler *et al.*, 1998). It seems that the concern over the role of the management team in the transfer of training is raised, while the influence of a motivating work environment is widely accepted. Regarding the doubts about the managerial support, there is no denying that it would contribute to a supportive transfer climate in an organisation. Its influence might not direct but would not only boost trainee’s self-confidence in transferring the new knowledge at work, but also motivate them to maintain the changed behaviours for the long term. Therefore, both work environment and managerial support would contribute to an encouraging transfer climate in the workplace.

In the meantime, in the transfer model that Baldwin and Ford (1988) introduce (Figure 2-6), a correlation between the training design and conditions of transfer is emphasised. Although it is not a direct impact, the relationship shown in this model clarifies that a training process is an on-going circle, as each step that is included in the circle relates to each other.

e Training Evaluation

The term ‘training evaluation’ has been defined in various ways by a number of professionals. Some of them explain it in terms of the effectiveness of a training activity. For example, Goldstein and Ford (2002, p.138) consider it as a systematic technique that would be applied to gather ‘descriptive and judgemental information’ of a training program to evaluate its effectiveness. Likewise, Buckley and Cape (2009, p. 208) also put emphasis on its role in examining ‘how effective the training has been’ in the post-training stage. From another’s point of view, the term ‘training evaluation’ is also defined regarding workplace well-being. For instance, it is suggested that training evaluation provides a company with information to ensure the right training programs have been adopted for the well-being of the organisation (Bramley, 2003, p.6). Apart from these opinions, the purpose of evaluating a training activity is also linked to the recognition of changes and improvements within an organisation (Thorne and Mackey, 2003, P.72). By comparing these different views on training evaluation, it is clear that they

share some similarities. Firstly, they all prove a relationship between training evaluation and training effectiveness. Secondly, it appears that an evaluation is not as simple as a process but also a critical approach that could benefit organisations. Therefore, there is no denying that the significant role training evaluation plays in training development. Regarding its importance, there are a number of studies discuss it in detail. For example, Sloman (2017, p.147) assimilates the role of training evaluation as ‘a necessary weapon in a training manager’s armoury’ to emphasise its significance. It is also suggested that a ‘meaningful evaluation allows you to monitor results and to make any appropriate changes...also provides you with information that you are “doing a good job” and allows you to celebrate your success’ (Thorne and Mackey, 2003, p.71). In other words, an effective training evaluation could not only benefit a company but also its employees who undertake the training activity (Buckley and Cape, 2009, p. 20p). However, the results of some studies reveal the reality of a disappointing situation. For instance, Thorne and Mackey (2003, p.71) report that there are still some firms have not put enough attention on evaluating the effectiveness of training activities but ‘direct vast energy into planning, developing and delivering’ trainings. It is evident that training evaluation could not be viewed as an unnecessary cost. Instead, ‘poor decisions are likely to be expensive’ (Bramley, 2003, p.6). Therefore, it is suggested to place the step of training evaluation at the end of a training cycle to not only ensure the effectiveness of a delivered training session, but also recommend some new training needs for the future sessions. It also indicates the fact that training is an on-going process.

As ‘the choice of evaluation criteria is a primary decision that must be made when evaluating the effectiveness of training’ (Day *et al.*, 2001), there is debate over the choice of a set of evaluation standards in empirical studies. First of all, the result of a survey conducted by the American Society of Training and Development in 2002 reveals that ‘78%’ of the targeted organisations only depend on the use of the reaction criterion in evaluating the effectiveness of their training activities (Van Buren and Erskine, 2002, quoted in Arthur Jr *et al.*, 2003). Apart from the reaction criterion, the training objective is also suggested to be applied as ‘the most appropriate criterion’ to provide the guidelines on how to conduct a training evaluation (Arthur Jr *et al.*, 2003). Furthermore, Kirkpatrick’s four-level model of training (1996), which is presented in Figure 2-7, has been regarded as the most popular theory that has been applied in valuing the effectiveness of a training activity in practice (Salas and Cannon-Bowers, 2001). This is because it includes not only reactions and behaviours but also learning and result. This idea is supported by Tannenbaum and Yukl (1992), at the same time, they criticise how

unreliable to judge the effectiveness of a training activity only based on trainees' attitudes and feelings. It is a concern as the feedback collected from trainees might be too judgemental to take into account. At the same time, it is believed that reaction data are difficult to collect and measure. Thus, the four-level training evaluation model that is promoted by Kirkpatrick (1996) is considered as a comprehensive approach by combining four various criteria to critically measure training outcomes. Meanwhile, it is believed that it is unrealistic to evaluate different training programs with the same criterion (Tannenbaum *et al.*, 1993). This view is also emphasised by other scholars, for example, Arthur Jr, Bennett Jr, Edens and Bell (2003). Thus, it appears that it is critical to identify the factors which would be appropriate to be applied as measurements to evaluate the effectiveness of a specific training program.

Figure 2-7. Kirkpatrick's Four-Level Model of Training

(Kirkpatrick, 1996)

2.1.2.5 Summary on the Training Related Literature

In the above section, some empirical literature on the topic of training has been reviewed to provide readers with background information on the subject of this research. It started with the general knowledge of training, for example, various explanations of what the term ‘training’ has been defined. The message revealed indicates the term ‘training’ cannot be easily explained as ‘learning’. Instead, a training course is a planned activity that aims to bring changes resulting from achieving expected learning objectives. Then, the topic of training was mainly reviewed from a business perspective afterwards, such as, its roles in organisations and different types of on-the-job training activities. In order to examine the effective training practice within the workplace, three important training models were introduced and compared. Among them, the systematic training model (Figure 2-1) has been considered as the fundamental framework that plays a critical role in developing training principles in organisations. In particular, it places an emphasis on the fact that training is an on-going process. The remaining two (The Restructured Systematic Training Model & A Transitional Model) were created based on it and transformed the systematic training model into a more practical training framework suits better in business. At the same time, these three models help this study to identify the main steps in a training circle, which are Training Needs Assessment, Training Design & Delivery, Organisational Learning Environment, Transfer of Training and Training Evaluation. The evidence collected from other literature on organisational training also confirms the importance of each of these steps and their great influence on others within this on-going process. At the end, the main training theories that were reviewed and discussed in the above section are presented in the following table,

Table 2-2. Included Training Theories and Models

The Systematic Training Model (Figure 2-1)
The Restructured Systematic Training Model (Figure 2-2)
A Transitional Model (Figure 2-3)
Different suggestions on how to assess training needs (Table 2-1)
Interaction of Factors that Influence the Design of Training (Figure 2-4)
STAR Training Model (Figure 2-5)
A Model of the Transfer Process (Figure 2-6)
Kirkpatrick’s Four-Level Model of Training (Figure 2-7)

2.1.3 Perspectives on the Topic of Luxury

2.1.3.1 The Concept of Luxury

The word 'luxury' originates from the term 'luxus' in Latin, which equates with 'extravagant' or excessively expensive in word meaning (Luzzini and Ronchi, 2010). To look it up in dictionaries, the word 'luxury' is explained as 'non-essential items or services that contribute to luxurious living; an indulgence or convenience beyond the indispensable minimum' in Webster's Dictionary (Webster 's, 2002, quoted in Wiedmann *et al.*, 2007). It is defined as 'something expensive that is pleasant to have but is not necessary' in Cambridge advanced learner's dictionary (McIntosh, 2013, p. 926). Both of these definitions describe it as a product or a service that is not a necessity. At the same time, they both place the emphasis on the enjoyable luxurious experience. Three expressions stand out from these two definitions. They are 'non-essential', 'indulgence' and 'expensive'. The evidence that is found from the empirical studies proves the existence of the same point of view in describing the term 'luxury' by some scholars in the academic field. Some of them emphasise how important the feature of costliness is to understand the meaning of luxury, for example, McKinsey (1990) and Nueno and Quelch (1998). At the same time, it is also noticed that the expression of low functionality is frequently used to define this word, for example, Grossman and Sharpiro (1988) and Sombart (1913). Furthermore, the term 'indulgence' has been applied to distinguish the concept of luxury from non-luxury in some literature, for instance, Nia and Zaichkowsky (2000). To combine these three important elements together, luxury can be understood as 'big, broad-reaching, and it sells wildly expensive stuff that nobody really needs' (Thomas, 2007, pp.18). Alternatively, it can also be explained as 'those whose ratio of functionality to price is low, while the ratio of intangible and situational utility to price is high' (Nueon and Quelch, 1998).

Meanwhile, it is noted that the concept of luxury is also explained from a consumer's perspective by some researchers. On one hand, it is discussed with the psychological benefits that luxury consumers would gain from luxury consumption. For example, Lipovetsky and Roux (2003) think the idea of luxury equates with 'the individual identity'. By detailing what does the individual identity mean to a luxury customer, Vigneron and Johnson (1999) believe a luxury item 'brings esteem for its owner'. This view could be comprehended by applying the theory of conspicuous consumption (Roper *et al.*, 2013). That is, people intend to get other's admiration and respect through purchasing expensive items. If the same theory is applied in the context of luxury, then the psychology of luxury clients could be interpreted as they enjoy

the sense of gaining prestige from others as a result of luxury consumption. On the other hand, there are also other opinions related to luxury consumer's emotions. For example, the emphasis of the explanation that is offered by Berry (1994) is on the pleasure that customers get from purchasing expensive luxury goods when it comes to define the term 'luxury'. This view is also supported by other scholars, for example, Wiedmann, Hennigs and Siebels (2009). However, Kaferer (1997) suggests taking 'human involvement', scarce supply and 'the recognition of value', these three critical elements, all into account, to define the concept of luxury comprehensively. It is also recommended that the meaning of luxury might differ from person to person, as personal relationship with luxury sector would affect individual's understanding (Berthon *et al.*, 2009; Roper *et al.*, 2013). Therefore, it is apparent that the meaning of luxury is not only about extravagance. Instead, 'luxury fulfils social and economic goals and is more than a status or conspicuous consumption games' (Kapferer, 2015, p.12).

2.1.3.2 The Luxury Brands

Due to the inconsistent understandings on the meaning of the word 'luxury', it is critical to identify the differences between luxury and non-luxury business sectors. At the beginning of this section, the opinions from the empirical studies about luxury brand's unique features are critically reviewed by comparing with those of non-luxuries. In terms of the luxury world, two luxury business models are introduced and compared. In particular, the diamond business model modified by Louis Vuitton, which is one of the most valuable luxury brands in the world, is also discussed. Overall, the purpose of this section is to differentiate luxury from non-luxuries. The mechanism of the luxury business is demonstrated to reveal its exclusivity.

a Luxury vs. Non-Luxury

Luxury has been viewed as 'something out of the ordinary' (Hansen and Wänke, 2011). It indicates the differences that exist between luxury and non-luxury business sectors. To detail what those factors would distinguish luxury from non-luxury, the unique features of the luxury industry are discussed from three perspectives; they are 'company size, financial characteristics and time factor' (Chevalier and Mazzalovo, 2008, p.2). After the comparisons, it is noted that 'the luxury brands are rather small but with strong awareness among consumers'; 'a significant number of luxury firms are losing money'; 'luxury brands are a very productive path that can lead to becoming a lifestyle brand' (Chevalier and Mazzalovo, 2008, p. 2-6). In sum, the priority of a small-sized luxury company is not to make profit in the short term, but to build its brand identity to attract customers. Apart from these three unique features, it is also recognised that the principles of traditional marketing do not fit within the luxury category. It

is even claimed that the luxury marketing strategy is ‘the opposite of what was taught in traditional marketing lessons’ (Chevalier and Mazzalovo, 2008, p.14), which is presented in Figure 2-8. In this diagram, the top three standards, which includes ‘high price’, ‘high cost’ and ‘craftsmanship’, correlate with each other. That is, a luxury company invests heavily in pursuing high-end quality and exclusive craftsmanship, which would result in a high cost. At the same time, the principle of ‘high price’, ‘craftsmanship’, ‘limited distribution’ and ‘low promotional activity’ also relate to each other. Because they would all contribute to the brand’s unique image. Last but not least, the rule of ‘advertising with no sophisticated copy strategy’ would have an impact on creating the brand-related dreams for customs. Ultimately, they would work together to build a luxury brand’s brand identity and raise its awareness in public, which would result in an increase in demand. In sum, Figure 2-8 clearly introduces the particular marketing principles that luxury brands adopt, which are ‘turning’ traditional marketing ‘upside down’ (Kapferer and Bastien, 2009). Moreover, it is apparent that luxury companies apply a different set of rules when comparing with those that are normally used in the traditional business sector.

Figure 2-8. The Paradox of Luxury-goods Marketing
(Chevalier and Mazzalovo, 2008, p.14)

There are still other significant guidelines mentioned in some studies, on which a strong luxury brand could build. They also distinguish luxury from non-luxury business sectors in the market. Firstly, brand tradition is considered as an exclusive factor in the context of luxury. Its importance is recognised as the ‘proof of the brand’s power and ability to survive’ (Gutsatz and Auguste, 2013, p.2). It appears that brand tradition plays a critical role in the success of a

luxury company. The reason behind this statement is because ‘there can be no luxury brand without roots’, because luxury brands ‘born with history, draw great self-confidence from it’ (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012, p. 93). To interpret this point of view, a luxury organisation’s brand history is inherited and contributes to its core brand values. Moreover, brand tradition contributes to the uniqueness of each luxury company’s identity. It is suggested that the history of a luxury brand is believed as the soil and its inherited values grow in it, which would be translated to its business and result in its exclusive brand image. In other words, brand tradition is recognised as ‘a great uniqueness and a cult of inherited values’, which differentiates the luxury from the non-luxury brands (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012, p. 93). Secondly, brand luxuriousness is also discussed as a distinctive feature that makes luxury companies different from traditional business sectors. It can be understood by contrasting with brand tradition, as it is described as ‘the future of tradition’ (Kapferer, 2015, p.17). It seems that a luxury firm’s brand history is extended and adds more value through brand luxuriousness. Therefore, brand tradition makes up the individual brand image which gives the luxury brand meaning. Brand luxuriousness, on the other hand, brings the brand inherited values through time. By focusing on both the past and the future, it ensures the luxury brand achieving the ‘long-term value’ (Chevalier and Mazzalovo, 2008). Furthermore, brand awareness is another factor that is frequently discussed in the empirical studies to understand the differences between luxury and non-luxury brands. It is apparent that raising brand awareness in public is a critical approach regarding all business sectors in the market, as ‘brand awareness is likely to increase brand market performance’ (Huang and Sarigöllü, 2014). However, to most of the non-luxury firms, brand awareness relates to boost sales and increase market share (Webster *et al.*, 2003). This is not the case regarding the world of luxury. To educate consumers about brand tradition and brand luxuriousness, luxury brands aim to build an emotional attachment with them. Instead of selling the products and competing with other brand, ‘luxury makes the bald statement “this is what I am”, not any comparison with a competitor’ (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012). Therefore, to increase the awareness of a luxury brand is to offer customers ‘psychological and sensory gratification’ (Chitturi *et al.*, 2008), which emphasises on ‘hedonic potential’ (Hagtvedt and Patrick, 2009), over ‘functionality’ (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012, p.19). Finally, all of these three variables (brand tradition, brand awareness and brand luxuriousness) would result in creating brand-related dreams for customers. In this study, Figure 2-9 is developed to present the relationships among these four distinctive elements that are discussed previously. As a conclusion, there is a considerable difference between luxury and non-luxury business. When it comes to luxury, the potential hedonic value of the brand is more vital than the actual

functionality of the product. The brand-related dream, which is nurtured by its exclusive brand heritage, creates bonds with those who are appealing to the unique brand identity that is presented in that dream.

Figure 2-9. The Key Features of Luxury

b *Luxury Business Model*

It is suggested that luxury is branded. In other words, a luxury brand ‘embodies unique elements of singularity which can never be copied’ (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012, p. 139). A comparison has been made between Hermès and H&M, and the result shows the brand equity of the former is worth about ‘5 times its global sales and 28 times its earnings’ while the brand value of the latter only equals to ‘0.9 times its sales and 6.5 times its earnings’ (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012, p. 141). It appears that brand value is the centre of the business of luxury brands. Therefore, it is necessary to explore luxury business models, to understand the luxury segment.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Kapferer and Bastien, 2012.

Figure 2-10. Luxury Brand Architecture: Poles and Product Roles

(Kapferer and Bastien, 2012, p.156)

In this particular luxury business model, which is presented in Figure 2-10, the four poles represent ‘the past; the pursuit of status and prestige; the modernity that gives it vibrancy, emotion and creativity; plus some accessibility’ (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012, p.156). It is clearly to see the vital role that brand value plays in luxury business strategies, as it is placed in the centre of this framework. Horizontally, brand values keep the balance between brand tradition and brand luxuriousness. On one hand, it emphasises the importance of maintaining a luxury company’s heritage root consistently. On the other hand, the brand also aims to create new launches which would keep it up with the latest modern trend in the luxury market. It is apparent that a successful luxury brand could not only stick by its brand history, but it is also required to carry its unique inherited values on the way of being more creative. That is, the essence of a luxury brand not only shines in the past but also provides inspirations for the new business ideas. To find a balance between brand tradition and brand luxuriousness is not to compromise the principles. Instead, ‘an old history gives you the obligation to be daring in the future’ (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012, p.143).

Vertically, brand values stand in between those new and those loyal to a luxury brand. On one hand, entry-level luxury goods are offered to create more accessibilities to engage with new explorers. On the other hand, luxury brands customise its products and services for their elite customers. This is because, luxury consumes ‘want different levels of engagement with their brands ranging from minimal to highly involved’ (Tynan *et al.*, 2010). Thus, luxury companies not only offer the brand-related dreams to attract new clienteles, but also provide the prestige experience to the high-end customers. In sum, it is noticed that ‘value is a central concept’ in luxury business (Payne and Holt, 2001).

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Kapferer and Bastien, 2012.

Figure 2-11. The Pyramid Business Model

(Kapferer and Bastien, 2012, p.306)

Figure 2-11 presents the pyramid business model, which is also quite popular in the world of luxury (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012, p.306). It demonstrates various strategies that would be applied to achieve a luxury brand’s growth. It is clear that the emphasis is placed on extending a fashion house’s product categories from entry level to premium collections in this model. Therefore, it is considered as a part of the luxury brand architecture, which is discussed earlier (see Figure 2-10), because it is similar as the vertical pole that is included in the luxury brand architecture. As shown in Figure 2-11, the wider the accessibility could be reached, the less creativity of the design of collections would be achieved. On the contrary, the product lines become more and more exclusive when climbs upward towards the top of the pyramid. The

insight of the pyramid model is to offer the luxury goods market approaches to reach more potential customers. As the entry-level product lines are not limited distributed and slightly cheaper, consumers are more willing to give a try. At the same time, the model suggests luxury brands treating their elite customers with tailored premium products and services to maintain the brand-related luxury dreams. However, there is a conflict between the pyramid business model and the financial characteristics of luxury sector that are discussed when comparing luxury with non-luxuries earlier in this section. It seems that the design of the bottom of the pyramid could be also understood as a strategy to help luxury companies to achieve ‘a rapid increase in turnover and profits through lines that have low cost of production through industrialization’ (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012, p.178). It is apparent that this is against the principle of ‘high price’, ‘limited distribution’ and ‘low promotional activity’ (Chevalier and Mazzalovo, 2008). It is believed that pursuing short-term profit through mass production would damage a luxury retailer’s brand image. The risk of losing brand values would unbalance either the vertical or the horizontal pole that is demonstrated in Figure 2-10. In this case, it is impossible to build a strong luxury brand though it has its unique brand tradition.

Figure 2-12. The Louis Vuitton Diamond Model

(Kapferer and Bastien, 2012, p.307)

Due to the concern over destroying brand values, many luxury brands customise the pyramid business model to fit within brand identity and market potential of their own. Taking Louis Vuitton, ranked as the No. one of the world's most valuable luxury brands (Davis, 2020), as an example. This luxury icon also adopts the pyramid business model but changed it into a diamond shape (Figure 2-12). As a result, this business framework is widely recognised as Louis Vuitton's diamond model in the luxury world (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012). From the diamond business model, it is clear to see that the management of Louis Vuitton complies with the suggestions of the pyramid business model (Figure 2-11). The luxury icon extends its product lines from the entry range to the top range. By comparing with the pyramid model (Figure 2-11), the one that is modified by Louise Vuitton keeps the right balance between the size of the accessibility and the prestige through its strong brand values. By doing so, it avoids the risk of damaging its exclusive identity. At the same time, the brand places its most iconic products in the middle of its business model. The so-called 'heart of range' (Figure 2-12) would never be removed from the centre of its product lines. It would also be well kept, as these collections symbolise the brand values and its powerful brand image. On the top of this diamond business model, the luxury icon customises its services and products for its elite customers to emphasise its prestige and supremacy. In sum, the Louis Vuitton's diamond model provides readers a good example of modified business model that is used in the luxury business.

2.1.3.3 The Luxury Consumption

Due to the ever-changing market conditions in the international luxury industry, it is critical to deepening the understandings of its customers. For this purpose, different opinions on potential types of luxury consumers from other studies are reviewed at the beginning of this section. Then, three models that dominate the field are presented and compared to explain luxury consumer's perceived values in the context of luxury consumption. It follows by a discussion on a framework about luxury brand purchase intention to consider both self-perceived values and external influence. Overall, this part aims to offer readers with evidence and findings from the empirical studies regarding luxury consumption to enhance their understandings on the phenomenon of luxury consumption from a consumer's perspective.

a The Luxury Clients

It is generally believed that only the individuals with relatively high personal earnings could be considered as ideal luxury consumers. For example, luxury consumption is viewed as a clear

statement that the wealthy make to show how superior they are than the rest (Han *et al.*, 2010, p.15). Likewise, both Capgemini Group and Merrill Lynch, these two global leading consulting firms, consider ‘High Net Worth Individuals’ (HNWIs) as ‘the best potential clients’ regarding global luxury market (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012, p.114). However, this opinion is also believed to be too extreme. For instance, it is noticed that luxury consumption is becoming more common among ‘the middle classes’ in some emerging markets (Walley *et al.*, 2013). It is even suggested that ‘everybody’ could be a luxury client (Chevalier and Mazzalovo, 2008, p.150).

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Vigneron and Johnson, 1999.

Figure 2-13. Prestige seeking consumer behaviour

(Vigneron and Johnson, 1999)

Regarding the types of luxury consumers, several debates are noticed in empirical studies. For example, in Vigneron and Johnson’s study of ‘prestige-seeking consumer behaviour’ (1999), luxury clients are divided into five categories, which are ‘the Veblen, the Snob, the Bandwagon, the Hedonist and the Perfectionist’. These five categories are presented in Figure 2-13. Among these suggested groups of luxury consumers, the Veblen is inspired by ‘Veblen effects’, which is proposed by Thorstein Veblen (1899, quoted in Bagwell and Bernheim, 1996) to discuss the phenomenon of conspicuous consumption. Therefore, this type of clients long for status by showing off their personal wealth through purchasing high-priced luxury items. As presented in Figure 2-13, the Veblen is placed in the bottom right quadrant which indicates a higher price range and a high public awareness. The category of the Snob can be understood through the word meaning of ‘snob’. Thus, the luxury clients fit this group are those who view the price of

a luxury product as an indicator of prestige. Although both Veblen and Snob customers crave public's respect and admiration through spending money on luxury goods, they are different in some ways. Those who is included in the customer group of the Snob could only be satisfied by the exclusive luxury products. In other words, they make it publicly known that they are not a part of the 'common herd' (Leibenstein, 1950). Therefore, the Snob is placed in the upper right quadrant that emphasises an expensive price tag and a low public awareness. About the category of Bandwagon customers, it can also be explained by the meaning of the term 'bandwagon'. This group of individuals are interested in those well-known luxury items. That is, 'the demand for a commodity is increased due to the fact that others are also consuming the same commodity' (Leibenstein, 1950). In Figure 2-13, it is clear to see that Bandwagon clients are placed in the bottom left quadrant to suggest that this particular consumer type mainly focuses on the public opinion on certain luxury items instead of its price. Then, it is apparent that the remaining two consumer categories, which are the Hedonist and the Perfectionist, are presented together in the top left quadrant in Figure 2-13. Accordingly, it seems that both Hedonist and Perfectionist consumers pay less attention on price and interpersonal influence. By comparison, it is suggested that consumers that are included in the Hedonist category 'are more interested in their own thoughts and feelings', while 'Perfectionist consumers rely on their own perception of the product's quality' (Vigneron and Johnson, 1999). In sum, the first three groups of luxury clients, which are the Veblen, the Snob and the Bandwagon, are interested in the symbolic value of the luxury brands, such as prestige and exclusivity, while the rest two types, which are the Hedonist and the Perfectionist, emphasise on the functional and experiential value, such as emotional involvement and quality.

Furthermore, Ziccardi (2001) segments the luxury clients into four groups mainly based on individual wealth, they are 'Millennium Money, Old Money, New Money and Middle Money. Despite that, it seems only the consumer's financial status matters in this point of view, it also reflects the specific spending pattern of each group when it comes to analysing consumer behaviours regarding luxury consumption. Apart from these views on the types of luxury consumers, Kapferer and Bastien (2012, p.117) identify another type of clients 'excursionists', who are 'less wealthy but are advanced in sociocultural terms', and they shop in luxury brands 'occasionally, motivated by self-indulgence or hedonism or to celebrate a person or a moment'.

It appears that the opinions on how to define luxury clients differ from person to person. It is even suggested that there might be individuals who are 'from a state of poverty' but enjoy

‘respect, extend VIP treatment’ offered by the luxury brands (Chadha and Husband, 2006). Therefore, the understanding of the potential luxury consumers would not only limit to the consumer groups, but also their perceived values and purchase intention in the context of luxury consumption.

b Theoretical Models on Luxury Consumption Values

The term ‘value’ is defined as ‘beliefs that guide the selection or evaluation of desirable behaviours’ (Schultz and Zelezny, 1999). Regarding luxury consumption, the opinions on consumer perceived values vary from scholar to scholar. In Figure 2-14, the key studies on this topic are listed (Walley *et al.*, 2013). It is clear that some of the researchers explain it based on functional benefits of luxury goods while others understand it from a personal aspect, such as self-esteem.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Walley et al, 2013.

Figure 2-14. Studies of brand luxury dimensions

(Walley et al., 2013)

The three dominant frameworks in this area are, Prestige-seeking Consumer Behaviour Model (refers to Figure 2-15), the Brand Luxury Index (BLI; refers to Table 2-3) and the Luxury Value Model (refers to Figure 2-16). Both of the first two are designed by Vigneron and Johnson in 1999 and 2004 respectively. Meanwhile, the Luxury Value Model is developed by Wiedmann, Hennigs and Siebels in 2007. There are a number of reasons why these models are chosen to discuss in this study. Firstly, the Brand Luxury Index (BLI) is designed on the basis of Prestige-seeking Consumer Behaviour Model. At the same time, the Brand Luxury Index (BLI) also has a significant impact on the development of the Luxury Value Model. Therefore, these three frameworks are closely related to each other. Then, these three models take both personal and interpersonal aspects into consideration when it comes to analysing luxury

consumers decision-making process. Thus, the evolution of these three frameworks provides a broader and balanced view on the relationships among different values. In the following section, they are introduced separately first and compared with each other afterwards to discuss their similarities and differences.

i Prestige-Seeking Consumer Behaviour Model

*Figure 2-15. A Conceptual Framework of Prestige-Seeking Consumer Behaviour
(Vigneron and Johnson, 1999)*

Prestige-Seeking Consumer Behaviour Model (refers to Figure 2-15) is developed to recognise different types of luxury consumers according to their perceived values in relation to their luxury consumption. As presented in Figure 2-15, five types of ‘prestige seekers’ and five ‘perceived prestige values’ are identified respectively by Vigneron and Johnson (1999). The idea of this model is inspired by ‘the Theory of Consumer Demand’, which introduced the concepts of ‘the Bandwagon effect, the Veblen effect and the snob effect’ (Leibenstein, 1950). As a result, three of these five types of suggested luxury consumers are defined as ‘the Veblenian, the Snob and the Bandwagon’ (Vigneron and Johnson, 1999). These five consumer types are explained and compared in detail in the previous part of this section (refers to Figure 2-13).

As the term ‘prestige’ is emphasised in the title of this framework, it is a priority to clarify the differences between the meaning of prestige and luxury. Firstly, the features of prestige brands are identified from multiple angles, such as ‘aesthetic appeal, best quality, social status, peer reference group and wealth’ (Vigneron and Johnson, 1999). At the same time, luxury is also

described with some similar expressions, for instance, ‘human involvement and the recognition of value by others’ (Cornell, 2002), ‘beauty’ (Kapferer, 1997), ‘expensive’ (Yeoman and McMahon-Beattie, 2006) and ‘premium image’ (Keller, 2009). Moreover, the relationship between luxury and prestige is revealed as a result of ‘the level of prestige’ of brands, which is divided into ‘upmarket brands, premium brands and luxury brands’ (Horiuchi, 1984). It is apparent, the concept of luxury and prestige is relevant. Even, luxury is also referred to ‘the extreme-end’ of the prestigiousness (Vigneron and Johnson, 1999). Therefore, the importance of Prestige-Seeking Consumer Behaviour model in interpreting luxury consumer’s behaviours is recognised in this study.

ii The Brand Luxury Index (BLI)

The Brand Luxury Index (BLI) was developed on the basis of Prestige-Seeking Consumer Behaviour Model (refers to Figure 2-15) by Vigneron and Johnson in 2004. There are two reasons to explain why this model is also included in this study. Firstly, the measurement scale of this framework is recognised as ‘the most complete, integrating, by virtue of its greater number of dimensions, different aspects of luxury’ (De Barnier *et al.*, 2012). Secondly, the idea of the Brand Luxury Index inspired the development of the Luxury Value model (Wiedmann *et al.*, 2007), which will be discussed later in this section. Therefore, there is no denying the significance of this model in understanding luxury client’s behaviours. Moreover, it would also present a background of the Luxury Value model.

As presented in Table 2-3, there are still five perceived luxury values included, which is the same when comparing with Prestige-Seeking Consumer Behaviour Model (see Figure 2-15). However, these values are classified into two groups, which are non-personal and personal perceived values. Although these two categories are not clearly presented in Prestige-Seeking Consumer Behaviour Model, the emotional and quality values that are included in it should be considered as personal perceptions. However, the BLI scale includes twenty well-chosen variables that are listed under these five sub-categories. By applying the Brand Luxury Index, it is believed that the perceived values and client’s behaviours in relation to luxury consumption could be studied and examined from multidimensions.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original table can be found in Christodoulides et al, 2009.

Table 2-3. The Brand Luxury Index

(Christodoulides et al., 2009)

iii The Luxury Value Model

Wiedmann, Hennigs and Siebels (2007) developed the Luxury Value Model, which is based on the Brand Luxury Index (see Table 2-3). Apart from personal and interpersonal dimensions that are emphasised in the previous two frameworks, both ‘financial and functional aspects’ are also added in this model, as presented in Figure 2-16 (Wiedmann *et al.*, 2007). This is because, ‘a customer’s luxury value perception and the motives for luxury brand consumption are not simply tied to a set of social aspects of displaying status, success, distinction and the human desire to impress other people, but also depend on the nature of the financial, functional and individual utilities of the certain luxury brand’ (Wiedmann *et al.*, 2007). By looking at the model presented in Figure 2-16, it introduces various correlations among different variables and dimensions. Although the key relationships between variables have been clearly highlighted in the model, there are more possible correlations that are also suggested. Therefore, it is considered as the most valuable framework in extending the current understandings of a customer’s value perception and purchase intention in the context of luxury consumption.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original table can be found in Wiedmann et al, 2007.

Figure 2-16. A Luxury Value Model

(Wiedmann et al., 2007)

iv A Comparison Among the Models

In the previous part, three frameworks about luxury perception values, which are Prestige-Seeking Consumer Behaviour Model (Figure 2-15), the Brand Luxury Index (Table 2-3) and the Luxury Value Model (Figure 2-16), are introduced individually. In the following paragraph, these three frameworks are compared to identify the similarities and differences among them.

Regarding the similarities they share, it is because they were developed based on each other. For example, the contribution, which was made by Vigneron and Johnson (1999), of taking perceived values from both interpersonal and personal aspects into consideration has been extended and emphasised in the later frameworks. Especially, the five perceived luxury values from Prestige-Seeking Consumer Behaviour Model (Figure 2-15), which are conspicuousness, uniqueness, prestige, hedonism and quality, have been kept in the rest two frameworks. However, they are also different from each other in some ways. By comparing the first two

models developed by Vigneron and Johnson in 1999 (Prestige-Seeking Consumer Behaviour Model, Figure 2-15) and 2004 (the Brand Luxury Index, Table 2-3) respectively, the feasibility of the latter has been tested in practice while the former is mainly based on the theories. Meanwhile, the latter includes twenty variables for accurately measuring the luxuriousness of a certain brand from the consumer's perspective. But the former was not designed with the detailed measurements. Despite Vigneron and Johnson testified the validity of the Brand Luxury Index with 'actual consumers', its feasibility under different cultural conditions is questioned (Christodoulides *et al.*, 2009). By comparing the Brand Luxury Index (Table 2-3) with the Luxury Value Model (Figure 2-16), the latter is created based on the former but is extended by specifying the non-personal value group. Instead of simply including conspicuousness, uniqueness and quality into this category, three sub-groups with six detailed variables that are organised to represent non-personal dimension. They are financial value (price), functional value (usability, quality and uniqueness) and social value (conspicuousness and prestige). By narrowly defining interpersonal aspect, the Luxury Value Model (Figure 2-16) provides a more detailed and clearer measuring scale when it comes to monitor a brand's luxuriousness. At the same time, it keeps personal factors to make it well-balanced. Therefore, the Luxury Value Model (Figure 2-16), which is developed by Wiedmann, Hennigs and Siebels in 2007, is the framework preferred in this study.

v The Discussions on Five Perceived Luxury Values

The five perceived luxury values emphasised in those three frameworks, which are conspicuousness, uniqueness, prestige, hedonism and quality. It is apparent that they also caught other scholars' attention. The evidence collected from some studies indicates the debates about whether or not they have an impact on luxury consumer's behaviours.

It appears that perceived conspicuousness is normally related to luxury consumer's social status. It is because 'the utility of prestige products' is viewed as to 'display wealth and power' (Veblen, 1899). This opinion is also supported by O'cass and Frost (2002), and they understand the value of perceived conspicuousness through 'conspicuous consumption'. In other words, the buying motive of 'the purely conspicuous consumer' is to impress others (Mason, 1984, quoted in Christodoulides *et al.*, 2009). As a conclusion, the consumers who expect to gain conspicuous value, such as 'social status and economic power' would be more likely to shop

with prestige brands (Park *et al.*, 2008). There is no denying that the relationship between perceived conspicuousness and luxury consumer buying behaviour is proved to be valid.

Then, the impact of perceived uniqueness on behaviours of prestigious clients is suggested. It is because the term 'uniqueness' is explained as an attempt of 'feeling differentiated from' others (Tian *et al.*, 2001). At the same time, it is believed that an individual who desires to communicate his/her unique image to others, would be more appealing to the brands that position to deliver the value of exclusiveness and rarity (Zinkhan and Prenshaw, 1994, quoted in O'cass and Frost, 2002). As exclusivity is considered as 'an important attraction for luxury brands' (Park *et al.*, 2008), therefore, it appears that perceived uniqueness would have an impact on consumer behaviours in the luxury market.

It is noticed that perceived social value is related to interpersonal influence on prestige-seeking consumer behaviours in some empirical studies. Initially, this perceived social value is called 'the Bandwagon Effect' by Leibenstein (1950) to explain the impact of other's opinions on an individual's behavioural change. Then, Festinger (1954) examined 'the opinion influence process in social groups' and identifies the relationship between the formation of an individual's attitude and the opinions of the majority. That is, people tend to behave the same way as most of the others of a social group. The Bandwagon effect also works in the context of luxury, as Dittmar (1994, quoted in Vigneron and Johnson, 1999) demonstrates its influence in differentiating 'prestige from non-prestige reference groups'. Meanwhile, it is suggested that 'people's desire to possess prestige brands may serve as a symbolic marker of group membership' (Vigneron and Johnson, 1999). This statement is also agreed by Husic and Cicic (2009). Therefore, the correlation between perceived social value and consumer behaviour in luxury consumption is also positively confirmed.

It appears that perceived hedonism is referred to the prestigious consumer's emotional attachments with luxury brands in some academic articles. Perceived hedonist value is considered as 'intangible benefits' (Vigneron and Johnson, 1999) or 'emotional values' and 'sensory pleasure' (Roux and Floch, 1996) offered by luxury brands. Likewise, Hagtvedt and Patrick (2009) agrees with this opinion, and they also believe that hedonic value would distinguish luxury from non-luxury brands. In the meantime, it is suggested that 'hedonist consumers' put 'their own thoughts and feelings' as a top priority when it comes to prestige seeking (Vigneron and Johnson, 1999). That is, those consumers who consider their emotions

as an indicator of prestige would be more likely to shop with luxury brands. Therefore, the relationship between perceived hedonism value and prestige-seeking consumer behaviours is proven.

At last, perceived quality value is often viewed as one of the key characteristics of luxury products in empirical articles on luxury consumption. For example, Vigneron and Johnson (2004, quoted in Wiedmann *et al.*, 2007) consider the superior quality value as an important feature to distinguish luxury from non-luxury brands. This is also one of the reasons that some consumers decide to purchase luxury products (Gentry *et al.*, 2001). From this point of view, the association between perceived quality value and consumer behaviour regarding the consumption of luxury brands is also proven.

c *Luxury Purchase Intention*

But, whether or not there is a relationship between customer's perceived luxury values and the decision on a purchase of luxury goods? Based on the evidence collected from literature, factors that would have an impact on consumer's purchase intention towards luxury brands have received a considerable amount of attention from scholars and practitioners. However, the opinions vary from person to person, for example, an individual's 'modernity', 'level of education' and 'the disposable income level' (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012, p.115-117); the cultural dimension of a luxury brand (Roper *et al.*, 2013). Among all the findings, the 'Luxury brand Purchase Intention Model', which is presented in Figure 2-17, stands out (Hung *et al.*, 2011). It is said, the idea of this model is inspired by the Brand Luxury Index, which was developed by Vigneron and Johnson in 2004 (refers to Table 2-3). In this framework, it includes three variables, which are 'Luxury Brand Perception, Social Influence and Trait of Vanity' (Hung *et al.*, 2011). It is apparent that both personal and interpersonal aspects are taken into consideration when it comes to examine the relationships between each variable and the intention of purchasing luxury items.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original table can be found in Hung et al, 2011.

Figure 2-17. The Luxury Brand Purchase Intention Model

(Hung et al., 2011)

Firstly, 'functional, experiential and symbolic values' are considered as the elements that compose luxury brand perception factor in this model (Hung *et al.*, 2011). Surprisingly, the results of their study reveal 'a weak negative relationship' between symbolic perceived value and luxury purchase intention, while confirm the positive impact of both functional and experiential values on the intention of purchasing luxury goods (Hung *et al.*, 2011). It is assumed that participants' different cultural background would affect the result of the research, therefore, it is believed that the perceived symbolic value would potentially have an impact on luxury consumer's purchase intention if the cultural difference would be accepted (Hung *et al.*, 2011). Apart from culture issue, it is suggested that personal influence would have an impact on behaviours of certain types of luxury consumers, for example, the functional value would affect the Perfectionists while the symbolic value might have an impact on either the Veblenian or the Snob, according to Vigneron and Johnson's Prestige-Seeking Consumer Behaviour Model (refers to Figure 2-15). Therefore, it is believed that perceived luxury values would affect consumer's purchase intention. But its influence might differ from customer to customer.

Secondly, the social influence is viewed as an ‘external’ factor that would affect individual’s intention of spending money on luxuries (Hung *et al.*, 2011). It can be understood as an interpersonal variable. There is no denying the awareness of a luxury brand by the public could have an impact on individual’s purchase intention. On one hand, this link is suggested by the Brand Luxury Index (refers to Table 2-3) and the Luxury Value model (refers to Figure 2-16). These two models are developed by several reputable scholars, for example, Vigneron and Johnson (2004) and Wiedmann, Hennigs and Siebels (2007). On the other hand, the results of Hung and colleague’s study (2011) also positively confirm the relationship between the social influence and purchase intention regarding luxury consumption. Therefore, it is believed that interpersonal factor would have an influence on luxury consumer’s purchase decisions.

Thirdly, the trait of vanity is promoted as the other variable that would have an impact on consumers’ purchase intention in the context of luxury consumption, apart from luxury brand perception and social influence (Hung *et al.*, 2011). The term ‘vanity’ is explained as ‘having an excessive concern, and/or a positive (and perhaps inflated) view of, one’s physical appearance/personal achievements (Netemeyer *et al.*, 1995). The word ‘vanity’ is also understood as ‘symbolic and sensory fulfilment’ (Wang and Waller, 2006). It seems, what the trait of vanity factor represents in this model is similar with ‘Extended self’ perceived value from the Brand Luxury Index (refers to Table 2-3) and ‘Self-Identity’ value from the Luxury Value model (refers to Figure 2-16), which are introduced by Vigneron and Johnson (2004) and Wiedmann, Hennigs and Siebels (2007) respectively. It appears that the role of the factor of vanity in luxury consumption has already caught many scholars’ attention. Moreover, the findings of Hung and colleague’s research (2011) reveal only ‘achievement vanity was seen to moderate between perception and purchase intention, and neither form of vanity can moderate between social influence and purchase intention’ (Hung *et al.*, 2011). Therefore, it seems the influence of vanity on consumer’s purchase intention of purchasing luxury products is supported in the academic field. However, further research on testifying this correlation in practise is suggested. Last but not least, it is clear to see the connections among the Luxury Brand Purchase Intention Model (refers to Figure 2-17), the Brand Luxury Index (refers to Table 2-3) and the Luxury Value model (refers to Figure 2-16). This also indicates the link between consumer perceived luxury values (both interpersonal and personal values) and individual’s intention of purchasing luxuries.

2.1.3.4 Internal Branding & Luxury Brand Ambassador

a *Luxury Brand Ambassador & Internal Communication*

As a result of the uniqueness of luxury business, ‘luxury brands have a lot to tell, to show, to reveal, to say and to make people experience’ (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012, p.268). Although brand messages could also be presented by ‘the product, store concept and visual merchandising’ (Gutsatz and Auguste, 2013, p.158), the critical role of the luxury frontline staff in the interactions with external customers could not be neglected. They are the ones who welcome luxury consumers and try to connect with them. Although the retail workers in the non-luxury business would also be expected to play an important role in managing customer relationships, ‘sales staff is a key population in the luxury industry and must be addressed with a better care’ (Gutsatz and Auguste, 2013, p.160). It is because they are not working in luxury stores for simply making sales, but ‘to share the mystery, the spirit of the place, of the objects, and the time embodied in each object’ with the brand clients (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012, p.236). Therefore, it is suggested that a qualified luxury frontline employee should have the knowledge of ‘the key elements that have passed on from generation to generation to nurture the brand’s DNA’ and ‘the craftsmanship experience’ (Gutsatz and Auguste, 2013, p.55); ‘the brand’s culture... its identity, and its philosophy’ (Pignataro, 2019, p.71) and ‘the story of the product’ (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012, p.77). Regarding skills that are critical to performing the luxury frontline employee’s role, on the other hand, recommendations include the ability to recognise consumer behaviours (Pinkhasov and Nair, 2014); ‘delivering the highest levels of service’ (Gutsatz and Auguste, 2013); the skills to ‘engage in different topics of conversation’ (Pignataro, 2019). From these points, the researcher considers the role luxury frontline employees play as luxury brand ambassadors, who are capable of not only fulfilling customer’s brand-related dreams, but also ensuring their ‘psychological and sensory gratification’ (Chitturi *et al.*, 2008).

The term ‘brand ambassador’ has been defined as ‘who are genuine supporters and devotees of a brand, and...are employed and trained by the company’ (Wang and Hariandja, 2016). Although the expression ‘brand ambassador’ usually refers to an external celebrity endorser or influencer on social media (Smith *et al.*, 2018), the researcher views its significance from a company’s internal perspective. In her opinion, not only those celebrities who are influential can be paid to promote a brand to the public as its brand ambassadors; a company’s employees who work in the frontline of the business should also be capable of taking this role by using their own voices in their daily work practice. In the Human Resource Management field, the

concept of employee voice has become a hot topic. It can be simply defined as ‘an opportunity to have a say’ within the workplace (Mowbray *et al.*, 2015). But at the same time, it has been linked to employee participation (McCabe and Lewin, 1992), employee involvement (Lavelle *et al.*, 2010) or employee satisfaction (Dundon *et al.*, 2004). Therefore, the researcher found the interrelationship between the concept of employee voice and internal corporate communication, as they can be both defined as types of communication within the workplace. In the meantime, both these two mechanisms that aim to give employees voice at work would benefit the organisation indirectly (Ramsay 1977; Marchington *et al.*, 1993), for example, ‘to improve business performance’ (Dundon *et al.*, 2004); to ‘infuse corporate values’ (Chong, 2007). Therefore, the researcher considers the possibility that luxury business transforms its frontline employees into luxury brand ambassadors through the use of internal corporate communication.

b Internal Branding & Internal Communication

In order to prepare an excellent luxury brand ambassador, a luxury company needs to be strongly associated with its employees, as one of the unique assets of luxury business is brand tradition (see Figure 2-10). Many luxury brands are named after their founders, for example, Chanel, Burberry and Louis Vuitton. ‘Like a living being, the brand has ancestors, a history, cultural and geographical roots’ (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012, p. 143). Therefore, the priority of building a strong luxury brand is to make employees feel part of its heritage, culture and values. However, this is recognised as one of the challenges that most of multinational luxury brands are facing nowadays, as ‘conflicts of culture’ are unavoidable between a brand and its multinational employees (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012, p. 242). Despite this, the significant role that internal branding plays in solving cultural problems in luxury firms cannot be denied. For example, the evidence demonstrates that Hermès (2019) manages to ‘cultivate a sense of belonging’ for its employees through internal branding. Belonging has been recognised as ‘a basic human need’ (Maslow, 1981; Thoits, 1982). Therefore, the sense of belonging is needed by ‘people in all cultures’ (Hagerty and Patusky, 1995). In the case of Hermès, the brand aims to infuse its people with the brand’s values through creating a workplace of belonging. Apart from benefiting from instilling the brand’s values into its employees, Hermès would achieve higher organisational commitment and engagement. Because these are linked to higher workplace belonging (Carr *et al.*, 2019). Taking the researcher’s own work experience as an example, the luxury brand at where she worked consistently passes the knowledge regarding its exclusive British identity on to its employees through internal communications, such as

training sessions and corporate communication platform. By doing this, no matter the various nationalities of the people that work there, they all immerse themselves in the same universe as the brand at work. It is noticed that this brand's employees respect the brand's own identity and fit within the values of the brand culture, as everyone has 'the need for relatedness' (Markus and Kitayama, 1991). Therefore, having colleagues to bond within the workplace can be viewed as a good example of an effective internal branding initiative. As a result, the brand at where the researcher worked successfully promotes its values to its employees.

A company's values are viewed as 'philosophy that had long steered people's behaviour'; however, 'values will only come to have meaning once they are experienced by individuals and they discover for themselves' (Ind, 2007). Therefore, the use of internal corporate communication is suggested in enhancing the effect of internal branding by many scholars, for example, Thomson *et al.* (1999); Grof (2001); De Chernatony and Segal-Horn (2003) and Chong (2007). Its significant role includes, for example, 'to promote commitment to the organization, a sense of belonging to it' (Welch and Jackson, 2007, see Figure 2-18); 'to engage their minds, creativity, energy and commitment' (Quirke, 2017). In the meantime, the role of internal communication in the business environment can be also viewed from both a macro and a micro perspective, which are listed as 'awareness' and 'understanding' in Welch and Jackson's internal corporate communication model (2007, see Figure 2-18). Firstly, it could provide a brand's employees with the chance to 'see the bigger picture' (Pignataro, 2019, p.93), which is defined as 'developing their awareness of environmental change' (refers to awareness in Figure 2-18). In the context of luxury, it can be understood as the opportunity to understand the whole luxury segment, for example, the unique characteristics of the luxury business (see Figure 2-9); various luxury business models (see Figure 2-11, Figure 2-12) and the factors that would affect luxury consumption (see Figure 2-16, Figure 2-17). Then, if the influence of internal communication is discussed from a micro perspective, it could ensure 'high-quality brand content' be delivered as 'employees develop understanding of the evolving aims of the organisation' (Welch and Jackson, 2007, see Figure 2-18). In other words, the employees feel the brand as their brand, and 'contribute to its development' (Ind, 2007). Therefore, it is suggested 'the real value of internal communication is to help deliver business ends by enabling employees to turn strategy into action' (Quirke, 2017). In the context of the world of luxury, the luxury brand's employees 'create the dream and to recharge the brand's value' (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012, p.255) can be expected as an outcome of an effective internal communication. This is because, firstly, the quality of brand message would be affected by the

amount of knowledge the brand's employee obtained at work. In other words, more information regarding a brand's business directions its employees acquired through the company's internal communication consistently within the workplace, more successfully the brand image could be portrayed by its employees because of delivering high-quality brand messages to the public. On the other hand, the dream aspect could also be considered as a result of an effective internal corporate communication regarding specific skills in engaging with luxury customers at work. In reality, the benefits of internal corporate communication in internal brand-building are recognised by some luxury brands in the market, for example, Burberry Group Plc (2020), Hermès (2019) and Giorgio Armani S.p.A (2018). These brands proactively apply their own internal communication tools, such as, 'Burberry World' (Burberry Group Plc, 2020), 'HermèSphère' (Hermès, 2019) and 'the Armani Intranet' (Giorgio Armani S.p.A, 2018) to interact with their employees.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original table can be found in Welch and Jackson, 2007.

Figure 2-18. Internal Corporate Communication

(Welch and Jackson, 2007)

‘When internal branding efforts are implemented, employees are more likely to understand the brand, take ownership in the brand, and provide evidence of the brand in their organizational responsibilities’ (Devasagayam *et al.*, 2010). To those who work in the front line of the luxury business especially, they are expected to represent their brand outstandingly in their interactions with the customers, by acting as ‘a reliable port for the customer, inspire trust, strengthen the relationship between the company and the customer’ (Pignataro, 2019, p.93).

c Training Strategies in Luxury Chain

As what Pignataro (2019, p.71) believes, luxury fashion houses should invest in their ‘customer-facing employees’ to ‘give them the opportunity to operate at their fullest’. For this purpose, the evidence from the empirical studies that could identify the real training situation in the luxury world is collected. It shows that many well-known luxury brands view training programs designed to their sales associates as the main focus of their business (Dion and Arnould, 2011). However, the emphases of these customised sessions are different. For example, both the programs that are adopted by Giorgio Armani S.p.A (2018) and Prada S.p.A (2019) focus on sales skills, product knowledge and service standard; while some are designed to educate frontline staff about the brand’s history and identity instead of products knowledge or selling techniques. Take Christian Dior as an example, the brand believes ‘what the role of the salespersons is in transmitting the brand ideology’ (Dion and Arnould, 2011). Likewise, Burberry also understands the value of its frontline employees, therefore, the brand deploys training programs to ‘reinforce behaviours, culture and values’ (Burberry Group Plc, 2020). Apart from these types of training that are dedicated to luxury sales personnel, Hermès (2019) also employs ‘management training sessions’ and ‘Mosaïque—the onboarding programme for new employees’, as they are believed to have an indirect impact on the brand’s frontline employee’s work performance. That is, the well-trained managers could apply what they learnt from training to guide their team members’ work. At the same time, the onboarding training program could provide the new sales associates with the brand’s identity and made them immerse themselves in the uniqueness of the brand’s history and culture from day one. Likewise, LVMH, ‘the world leader in luxury’, also widely deploy on-boarding training in the group’s ‘75’ luxury brands (LVMH, no date). By doing this, it aims to ‘introduce the world of luxury to novices to the industry’ (Gutsatz and Auguste, 2013, p.154). However, the data found from Giorgio Armani’s annual report (2018) reveal the disappointing reality of the training practice, as not only the number of sales personnel involved in training activities in the workplace reduced from ‘2,904’ in 2017 to ‘2,672’ in 2018, but also there is an 82% decrease

in the brand’s sales personnel’s training hours from ‘143,556’ hours in 2017 to ‘25,330’ hours in 2018. It seems that it is necessary to re-evaluate the training initiatives that are dedicated to frontline personnel deployed in the luxury sector.

The Paradox of Luxury-goods Marketing (Figure 2-8)
The Key Features of Luxury (Figure 2-9)
Luxury Brand Architecture: Poles and Product Roles (Figure 2-10)
The Pyramid Business Model (Figure 2-11)
The Louis Vuitton Diamond Model (Figure 2-12)
Prestige Seeking Consumer Behaviour (Figure 2-13)
Studies of Brand Luxury Dimensions (Figure 2-14)
A Conceptual Framework of Prestige-seeking Consumer Behaviour (Figure 2-15)
The Brand Luxury Index (Table 2-3)
A Luxury Value Model (Figure 2-16)
The Luxury Brand Purchase Intention Model (Figure 2-17)
Internal Corporate Communication (Figure 2-18)

Table 2-4. Included Theories and Models regarding Luxury Business

2.1.4 The Summary of Literature Review Section

There are two areas of focus in this study’s literature review section, which are training and luxury. Regarding training, the role of the training function in modern organisations was discussed. Its strategic alignment makes it more than just learning at work. Through comparisons among three training models, training has been proposed as an on-going process. The discussions on possible correlations among the five chosen components that compose the process of training also emphasise this on-going feature. Regarding luxury, the unique characteristics of the luxury segment were critically reviewed. Due to the differences that distinguish luxury from non-luxury businesses in the market, the role of the luxury brand’s sales personnel differs from regular retail sales, as they are responsible of representing their luxury brands as brands ambassadors to the public.

Based on the findings of empirical studies that were reviewed, it is confirmed that the impact of effective training on bringing positive organisational outcomes has been widely accepted. But at the same time, the reality reveals that a lot of companies still consider the spend on training development as a cost rather than an investment. Meanwhile, the evidence shows that

there is no comprehensive training model, which has been designed and promoted to guide modern organisation's training practice; while the results of many studies are outdated. When evaluating the topic of luxury, it is evident that this is a relatively new area. It appears it has recently become popular in the academic field, as either there are not many research articles on this subject or most of the literature is mainly from specific authors. In the luxury context, the significant role of the internal communications has been emphasised by a number of empirical research studies. As organisational training can be viewed as a communication tool in general, a link between the deployment of training programs and the delivery of brand messages to frontline employees is indicated. It seems this relationship would also work in the context of the luxury business. While literature suggests increasing attention is being paid by luxury brands to training in the workplace, there is little practical evidence to support this. Specifically, there is no conclusive evidence to show whether or not some luxury retailers effectively transformed their frontline employees into brand ambassadors through the use of training. Furthermore, there is no training model, which has been adopted by any luxury company, is mentioned in the empirical studies.

At the same time, most studies reviewed in this research project applied quantitative research methods to collect data, such as questionnaires or surveys to measure the effectiveness of training activities in some organisations. A few research projects chose qualitative methods for data collection, such as interviews, focus groups and observations, in order to have more insights into how the training program took place, on what content did the training mainly focus in the selected firms.

As a result, the research gap between the undertaken studies and this research has been demonstrated. The researcher aimed to explore the practical training initiatives that are adopted at a luxury brand mainly through qualitative research methods. For this purpose, a training framework is expected to be developed based on the evidence collected in the process of this research project. Therefore, it is designed to fit within the current situation of training practice at the chosen luxury brand. It will be contributed to the selected luxury brand in this study.

2.2 Restatement of Problem, Study Aims and Objectives

As stated in the problem statement section, the secondary data collected from the empirical studies justified the strategic alignment of organisational training, as training has been considered as an 'integrated, strategic component of the organization' instead of 'a separate,

stand-alone event' (Salas and Cannon-Bowers, 2001). However, training effectiveness in the world of luxury has not gained enough attention both in the academic and business area, as there are only few recent studies on this topic that can provide readers with up-to-date data. Therefore, the researcher is still interested in examining the current training practice in the selected luxury brand. However, there are some changes regarding the aim of this study the researcher made after reviewing the literature. The refined main research question is presented as follows:

How effective are the training strategies practised by a luxury chain in the U.K. to transform its frontline staff into luxury ambassadors? What changes can be implemented with regard to enhancing the effectiveness of the training design?

Here comes the original research question of this study:

How effective are the training strategies practised by a luxury chain in the U.K. to deliver its innovative marketing strategies to its frontline staff? What changes can be implemented in regard to enhancing the effectiveness of the training design?

By comparing these two research questions, it is clear to see that the scope of the study aim has been broadened. The focus of the original study aim was to examine a correlation between the use of tailored training sessions and the implementation of the marketing objectives. The decision was made based on the researcher's work experience when she just joined the select company as a part-time luxury sales associate. At that moment, launching a marketing campaign via social media platforms was something new in the luxury world, as the marketing strategies for the luxury brands are considered as 'the opposite of what was taught in traditional marketing lessons' (Chevalier and Mazzalovo, 2008, refers to Figure 2-8). As a pioneer in this area, the chosen luxury brand was determined to get its employees well prepared with the knowledge of the upcoming marketing campaign. Therefore, some training sessions were developed for this purpose. They left the researcher a deep impression and aroused her interest in the area of organisational training. Especially, when she observed that some team members failed to deliver the newly learnt knowledge of the marketing campaign to the customers, it reminded her of the importance of the training design and training transfer. Thus, she formed the first research question. However, she realised the luxury business is larger than a marketing campaign, after reviewing the literature on the topic of luxury management. In the meantime,

she also learnt the fact that the job responsibility of the frontline luxury staff is not only to communicate with the luxury clients about the brand's marketing campaigns after gained more work experience. Luxury brands need outstanding brand ambassadors who could represent their business with distinction. Therefore, it is essential for luxury brands to transform their frontline staff into brand ambassadors by preparing them with the right mindset to work in the world of luxury with knowledge and skills through the adoption of training.

Therefore, the refined research objectives and the sub questions are listed as follows,

Sub Question 1

What are the current training strategies regarding transforming the selected luxury brand's frontline staff into qualified luxury ambassadors and how effective are they in successfully preparing its frontline employees with the luxury mindset to represent their luxury brand?

Objective 1

To evaluate the key aspects of the selected luxury brand's training strategies in transforming its frontline staff into outstanding luxury brand ambassadors.

Sub Question 2

What are the current challenges that the selected luxury brand's training department is facing for effectively preparing the brand's frontline staff with the right mindset for working in luxury?

Objective 2

To assess the current challenges that the selected luxury brand's training department is facing regarding effectively preparing the brand's frontline staff with the right mindset for working in luxury.

Sub Question 3

What changes can be implemented in regard to enhancing the effectiveness of the training design in the context of luxury?

Objective 3

To recommend the changes, which could be implemented in training design, to improve the training effectiveness in the luxury brands.

Chapter 3 - Theoretical Framework & Research Methodology

3.1 Theoretical Framework

Figure 3-1. The Theoretical Framework of this Study

The researcher developed a theoretical framework for training after reviewing the empirical studies (Figure 3-1). This training model is built based on the general knowledge of organisational training the researcher collected from reading. Through the process in which the researcher becomes confident with the information she gathered during reading, this training framework is gradually developed. The connections among the factors that are included in the model can be viewed as the evidence to suggest the researcher's understandings of a training circle after reviewing the empirical literature.

There are three stages included in this training model, which are pre-training, training and post-training stage. Before delivering a training session, there are four steps of preparations, which are training needs assessment, creating a learning environment, training methods, and evaluation plan. By going into detail, the purpose of assessing whether or not there is a certain training need in the workplace is to make sure the right learning requirements would be recognised and met. In this theoretical framework, the training needs assessment is suggested to be organised from various aspects, for example, an upcoming event planned by the company, a situation arising from a particular store or the requests from employees. The idea of taking all these into consideration, aims to not only align training with a company's business goals, but also look into the possibility that an individual store or employee might have problems with certain things at work. The second step of preparation is to create a supportive learning environment within the workplace. It is suggested adopting a top-down approach in this training model. Therefore, the message from the senior management about learning opportunities provided at work would be broadly elucidated and passed down to the junior staff members with open conversations. This would reduce employee's concerns and resistance to trainings. At last, the next two steps included in the pre-training stage are related to the training design. According to a specific training need, the suitable training methods would be selected. In the meantime, an evaluation plan is suggested to be made in advance to ensure that the learning objectives could be achieved afterwards. After the preparations are done, the session would be delivered as scheduled.

After a training course, it comes to the post-training stage, which includes two steps. They are the transfer of training and training evaluation. Regarding the former, two types of transfer are suggested in this framework, which are the immediate transfer and the long-term transfer. The main difference between these two is the time factor. Therefore, the former refers to the immediate behavioural changes of trainees as a result of attending a training course. By contrast, the latter is related to their attitudinal changes that could be observed after a relatively long period of time since they returned from training. These changes no matter in trainee's behaviours or attitudes could provide a clue about whether or not the session was effective. Then it is the time to evaluate the effectiveness of the previous training course with all the evidence collected, for example, trainees' reactions, the adopted learning approaches and the related business results.

In the meantime, the findings from the evaluation stage could be useful for either identifying another training need or improving the training design. Therefore, all the factors included in this theoretical framework are not independent but correlate with each other in a training circle.

3.2 Research Methodology

In the methodology section, the researcher explains in great detail about how this research was designed and justifies her choices. It starts with the clarification of the choice of the research philosophical framework. In this study, the interpretivism research philosophy has been selected to guide the researcher through investigation of the chosen business phenomenon in the selected field. It is an important decision to make, because this choice did not only have an impact on the essence of the study but also provided the researcher with the guidance in designing this research project. The decisions on both inductive approach and grounded theory methodology were affected by the choice of interpretivism research philosophy. As a result, the researcher started this study with the collection of participant's personal interpretations of the research objectives and to end with developing a theory that was derived from the data. In order to gather participant's feelings and thoughts, qualitative data was the first choice, while with the guidance of grounded theory, quantitative data was also collected in this study to support the qualitative data. Therefore, this research project was designed as a mix-method research. In particular, it is a qualitatively driven study, in which interviews, observations and questionnaires were all adopted to collect data.

In the meantime, one of the most famous British luxury brands has been selected as the single case to study in this research project. This decision was also made with the guidance of grounded theory methodology. At the same time, the researcher was working at the selected luxury brand at the early planning stage of this study. Her work experience brought her a high possibility to access to the data.

In the following paragraphs, the researcher not only explains the reasons why she made her decisions on how she designed this research project, but she also justifies the rationale of sampling and how she ethically conducted this study in the methodology section.

3.2.1 Interpretivism Research Philosophy

The importance of the research philosophy has been emphasised by many scholars, as an appropriate philosophical framework would provide a suitable guidance to researchers through

the entire research process (Quinlan *et al.*, 2015, pp. 55). In this study, the interpretivist philosophy, which is one of the epistemological positions, has been chosen as the most appropriate philosophical framework to guide this research project. However, the researcher deliberated on whether or not to employ constructionism instead, at the early planning stage. It is because these two research philosophical frameworks share many similarities in the way how they would guide a research study. Even sometimes they are suggested as interchangeable by some scholars, for example, Creswell and Poth (2016). In particular, both of them emphasise the importance of the human factor as they both suggest the path to learn a certain situation through other's perceptions of it (Berger and Luckmann, 1991). Likewise, the researcher believed the human factor would also play a critical role through the entire process of this research. It is because, training experience is personal. Therefore, with the guidance of either these two types of research philosophy, this study would be conducted among the group of people whose training experiences would be helpful regarding the purpose of this study. However, there are differences between these two philosophical frameworks. On one hand, if this study would adopt interpretivism research philosophy, it 'takes human interpretation as the starting point for developing knowledge about the social world' (Prasad, 2017). As stated, this study would be designed to collect luxury frontline staff's training experiences and their thoughts on the training initiatives practised by the luxury brands at where they work. In particular, participants' reflections on the effect of training at work would provide the researcher with rich details about the research objectives of this study, as 'people's perceptions of the same phenomenon can be rather varied' with the guidance of interpretivism research philosophy (Chen *et al.*, 2011). By comparison, if this research project would be guided by constructionism philosophical framework, the language the participants use would be the main focus (Burr, 1998). Therefore, the researcher would place the emphasis on the various ways that different participants present their ideas of the research topic. In the meantime, the role that researcher plays varies, by comparing interpretivism and constructionism research philosophy. On one hand, the former puts emphasis on 'noncommittal and neutral discovery of...the viewpoint of research participants' (Chen *et al.*, 2011); while, the latter aims to 'reconstruct ourselves' based on the reality of participants' (Burr, 1998). Although the goal of both these two types of research philosophy is to collect people's 'lived experience' (Berger and Luckmann, 1991), the researcher believes this study would achieve a better result with the guidance of interpretivism research philosophy. This is because the researcher intended to examine the reality of the training practices in the luxury business sector regarding the influence on transforming luxury frontline employees to brand ambassadors, through

participant's interpretations of the research objectives of this study. The role of the researcher in this research project was to reflect on the evidence she collected from the participant's perspective, instead of constructing her own understandings on the topic from her point of view, which aligns with the interpretivist philosophical paradigm (Adom *et al.*, 2016). Therefore, interpretivism research philosophy was considered as the most appropriate choice.

3.2.2 Inductive Research Approach

In this study, the inductive reasoning was chosen as the research approach. The decision on an inductive approach was mainly influenced by the research topic. This research project was planned to understand whether the frontline employees could be successfully transformed into excellent brand ambassadors through the use of training within a luxury retailer. After reviewing relevant empirical research projects in the field of both organisational training and luxury management, the researcher learnt a lot about not only the significant role of training in the workplace in general but also the uniqueness of luxury business models. However, these pieces of knowledge only helped the researcher in understanding either the area of organisational training or luxury business better. But the link between the importance of training in the context of the luxury industry has not brought enough attention in the academic field. As a result, there are only a few empirical research studies which include real cases that were aimed to investigate the deployment of training in luxury companies to provide this research with relevant background information. In particular, there is not any relevant finding from which the researcher could conclude the relationship between the use of training and a change from frontline employees to excellent brand ambassadors at luxury brands.

Due to a lack of sufficient information, the researcher made a decision on the research strategy to start with an investigation into the training practice at a selected luxury brand, for example, its training strategies for the brand's frontline staff, its retail trainer's work experience and the brand's frontline employee's opinions on the company's training practice. As it is discussed that the interpretivism research philosophy has been chosen to guide this research project, through interpreting the collected data the effect of the chosen brand's current training practice can be revealed with some of its employees' perceptions of it. Their lived experience helped this study to build up a picture of what is the role of training in this luxury brand's business, from both the corporate and its employee's perspectives. Then, the brand's frontline employees' perception of the changes in their work performance which happened after attending training sessions organised in the workplace acted as the evidence to suggest a link between the use of training and a possible result of transforming frontline staff into brand ambassadors at the

chosen luxury brand. Eventually, it is suggested that the findings of this study could be applied by more brands in the luxury business sector.

Obviously, the researcher's idea of revealing a general situation of training in the luxury industry through gathering the specific training experience and practice from a specific luxury brand fits the principles of the inductive research approach well. Therefore, the inductive approach was selected for the purpose of this study, as this research approach is considered to start from 'the specific' and end with 'the general' idea (Blackstone, 2018, ch. 2).

3.2.3 Mixed Methods Research Design

The researcher's initial thought on how to carry out this project was to design a qualitative study. It was due to the researcher's lack of relevant knowledge of the chosen area at the early stage. As a result, the original plan was to conduct an exploratory study to make a discovery of the research objectives. Specifically, participants' personal training experience and reflections on what they experienced were considered as the main information to collect. This rough idea clearly indicates the critical role of the human factor in this study. At the same time, the choice of applying the interpretivism research philosophy also suggested the importance of human participation. Either an exploratory study or the interpretivist philosophy demonstrates a chance that a qualitative research project would fit the purpose of this research. Because it is suggested that 'in qualitative research, the inquiry is more exploratory' (Creswell and Poth, 2016). In the meantime, the use of the interpretivism research philosophy has been linked to the qualitative research methods (Chen *et al.*, 2011). Therefore, this research was firstly designed as a qualitative study. However, the researcher had concern for the credibility of the results by conducting a purely qualitative project. Eventually, the idea of mixing both qualitative and quantitative methods in this study has been brought up to ensure 'the integrity of findings' (Bryman, 2006).

Due to the great importance of human factors, this study was 'a QUAL → quan design', which means 'more weight is attached to the data coming from the core qualitative component' (Schoonenboom and Johnson, 2017). The qualitative methods were applied to have a better understanding of the training practices at the selected luxury brand from its employee's perspective. Meanwhile, the quantitative research approach helped this study to reach a broader range of participants to hear their opinions on the research topic. Specifically, interviews and observations provided this study with in-depth information while questionnaires validated the collected qualitative data. By combining both qualitative and quantitative data, it did not only

prevent the results of this study from being too subjective, but also help the researcher to understand the topic from a bigger picture.

3.2.4 Grounded Theory Research

In this study, the grounded theory was chosen to guide both the data collection and the data analysis stages. Firstly, the choice of inductive reasoning suggested the researcher's intention to explore the research objectives through the specific participants' experiences to conclude with a general idea of the studied phenomenon in this research. This suits the grounded theory research as the purpose of using the grounded theory is to 'gather data and then systematically develop the theory derived directly from the data' (Dey, 1999, quoted in Walker and Myrick, 2006). Secondly, it is suggested applying 'multiple' data collection approaches (Goulding, 1998) in grounded theory researches. In particular, 'grounded theorists can...combine qualitative and quantitative techniques' (Strauss and Corbin, 1994). In the process of this study, the grounded theory helped the researcher to make the decision on the use of interviews, observations, and questionnaires to collect the data. It also guided the data coding stage.

For the purpose of gaining insights into the effect of training on preparing luxury frontline employees for representing their brands excellently, one of the most famous British luxury retailers was chosen as a single case to study in this research. This decision was firstly made due to a high possibility to access the data. The chosen luxury brand is where the researcher used to work as a part-timer. Because of her work experience with the brand, the trust is constructed. Therefore, she was successfully given the access to the data.

Regarding the choice of only including one case in this study, it was made to ensure the rich and detailed data would be collected. Especially, not only the training design varies from session to session, but the reflections on training experience also vary from person to person. The chosen single case provided this study with in-depth knowledge of the research topic. In the meantime, this decision also fits the guidance of the grounded theory, as the aim of conducting a grounded theory research is not to 'generalize findings to a broader population' (Corbin and Strauss, 1990) but to investigate 'in depth with meticulous attention to detail' (Quinlan *et al.*, 2015, p.131). At the same time, the time constraints also affected the choice between single case and multiple cases. It was not realistic to reach a broader range of cases in this study. As a result, the use of a single case in this research ensured the research objectives were properly studied and examined.

3.2.5 Research Methods – Mixed Methods

As the researcher justified earlier, this study was designed as a mixed methods research. At the same time, it was a qualitatively driven study. Therefore, although both qualitative and quantitative data collection methods were adopted, a major portion of the data gathered in this study is qualitative. Three data collection methods were chosen for the purpose of this study; two of them are qualitative approaches (in-depth interviews and observations) while the remaining one is quantitative method (questionnaires). The proportion of the former to the latter is presented in Figure 3-2.

Figure 3-2. Mixed Methods Research Design

3.2.5.1 Interviews

The interview research method was the main tool the researcher decided to apply in this in-depth investigation about the effect of the on-the-job training practice in the chosen luxury brand on preparing its frontline employees to be the excellent brand ambassadors. The researcher scheduled a one-to-one interview with each of the chosen interviewees. These face-to-face interviews were loosely designed instead of systematically structured. The purpose of this was to put the emphasis on fully exploring the feelings, experiences and thoughts on training activities from the interviewees' perspectives. There were three reasons for applying interviews in this research's data collection stage.

Firstly, the decision of conducting in-depth interviews was influenced by the choice of the research philosophy. In this study, the researcher selected the philosophical framework of interpretivism to guide the whole research process, as she intended to develop her understandings of the selected topic through the realities that perceived by the participants, who joined this research. As what Kvale and Brinkmann (2009, p.1) believe 'If you want to know how people understand their world and their life, why not talk to them?', the researcher considered holding conversations with some of the selected luxury brand's employees about their training experiences at work. Furthermore, an interview is recognised as 'an inter-change

of views' between the interviewer and the interviewee (Kvale and Brinkmann, 2009, p.2). Therefore, the researcher thought that qualitative interviews suit the purpose of this study well.

Secondly, the decision to deploy interviews in this study was due to the high possibility of gaining access to conduct this research in the selected luxury brand. At the early planning stage, the researcher was working at the chosen luxury brand as a part-time sales associate. Therefore, she had a great opportunity to gain the permission to conduct interviews with the employees who work at the selected company. Furthermore, building comfortable and confident interviewing atmosphere with the interviewees was much easier to achieve, as all the potential participants used to be her work colleagues. Therefore, the researcher believed that in-depth interviews were the best option for the purpose of this study.

Last but not least, the choice of the grounded theory also guided the researcher to make her decision on data gathering methods. Although the grounded theory methodology offered the researcher 'flexible guidelines rather than rigid prescriptions', it inspired her to get the research started by planning interviews to 'let the informant speak and don't get in the way' (Strauss and Corbin, 1994). Therefore, the researcher believed that in-depth interviews were the most appropriate choice to give voice to the interviewees to express their thoughts and feelings regarding the research objectives.

3.2.5.2 Participant Observations

Apart from interviews, observation data-gathering technique was another tool the researcher decided to apply in this in-depth investigation about on-the-job training practice in the chosen company. In particular, the participant observation was used in the stage of data collection of this study to collect the qualitative data about people (trainees and trainers) and training processes. In other words, the researcher did not only capture the interactions between trainers and trainees, but also experienced the effect of the different training design on achieving training effectiveness as a participant. These observations were well organised and recorded by taking fieldnotes in terms of the validity of the research.

There were two reasons behind the researcher's decision on applying participant observation research method in this study. Firstly, the researcher thought it was necessary to explore the delivery of training in a more detailed way. Apart from conducting face-to-face interviews with some participants, observations provided the researcher an opportunity to experience some training sessions that were organised by the selected luxury brand by herself as a trainee. Through the chance to attend some training programs, the researcher was able to collect a

broader range of data, for example, facial expressions, body languages and both the interactions between trainers and trainees and among trainees. Secondly, the decision to use observation as one of the data collection methods was due to the high possibility of gaining access to the data required for this research. In this research, one of the most famous British luxury fashion icons has been selected as the single case to study. During the early planning stage, the researcher worked at the chosen luxury brand as a part-time sales associate. Due to this reason, the researcher had a great opportunity to gain the permission to carry out the observation within the selected luxury brand. Therefore, observation data collection method was recognised as an appropriate approach for the purpose of this research project.

3.2.5.3 Questionnaires

Apart from interviews and participant observations, the questionnaire method was another data collection tool the researcher applied in this research project. The main reason this particular quantitative data collection method was also deployed in this qualitatively driven study was to minimise the limitations of the research results. Due to this reason, the use of the questionnaires aimed to generate a good amount of quantitative data to testify the collected qualitative data through interviews and observations in this research. By doing this, the results of this study were expected to be more precise by comparing with those as a result of a purely qualitative research, because questionnaires are considered as ‘precisely structured data-gathering instruments’ (Quinlan *et al.*, 2015, p. 272).

In practice, the main data were collected through the conversations to the chosen interviewees in this study. At the same time, a certain amount of the data was gathered when the researcher took part in some sessions as a participant at the selected brand. Therefore, the majority of the findings were generated through the use of qualitative research methods. Then, the primary purpose of including questionnaires here is to reach more luxury frontline employees of the chosen luxury brand and understand their views on their latest training experience they had at work. In order to motivate more respondents to engage in this research, each questionnaire was designed with twelve single choice questions. As a result, the simplicity of the questionnaire’s design was recognised by the participants, and they found it easy to complete by simply ticking boxes. At last, the questionnaire data were taken into consideration in the process of analysing the collected qualitative data to prevent the results from being too subjective. Although the use of quantitative data in this study was not weighed heavily, it played a critical role. By borrowing the words of Strauss and Corbin (1994), the results of questionnaires are ‘turning toward supplementary qualitative analyses’ in this study. From this point, the mixture of both

qualitative and quantitative research methods ensured the objectivity of the findings of this study. For this purpose, the analysis of the quantitative data was included and demonstrated in the data analysis chapter after the analysis of the qualitative data in this study. The findings as a result of examining the questionnaire data were discussed by comparing with the discoveries of the qualitative data in the discussion sector to reveal the reality of training that is practiced at the selected luxury brand.

3.2.6 Sampling

In order to have an in-depth understanding of the research topic, the researcher decided to mix both qualitative and quantitative data-gathering methods in this study. They are interviews, participant observations and questionnaires. Based on the various needs required by the individual data collection approach adopted in this research project, different sampling techniques were used. They are snowball sampling, judgemental sampling and internet sampling.

As discussed in the previous part, this research was conducted in the chosen luxury company to study its on-the-job training activities that are particularly designed for the brand's frontline employees. The chosen British luxury brand was the single case that was selected for the purpose of this research. Therefore, the target population was identified as the employees who work in the chosen luxury company's London stores. This brand has 11 stores located in London, including concessions in Selfridges, Harrods and Westfield shopping centre. There are around 25 people employed in each store, including management, sales, stockroom staff and security. Therefore, these 300 employees who work in the selected luxury brand's London stores were defined as the target population in this research. The researcher worked in one of its Heathrow Airport Boutiques at the early planning stage of this research. By considering of the cost and time constraints, all the employees work in the chosen luxury brand's stores that are located in Heathrow airport terminals were selected as the sample frame of this study.

After making the decision on the target population and the sample frame, the researcher started to think about which sampling method to select. Because of the nature of this study, the researcher mainly focused on collecting qualitative data to answer the research question. Therefore, this study is a qualitatively driven study. As a proven association between non-probability sampling technique and qualitative research design (Mays and Pope, 1995), the

researcher decided to apply this specific sampling method as the primary sampling technique to select the appropriate sample for this study.

Among all the non-probability sampling techniques, snowball sampling and judgemental sampling methods were selected for choosing the sample and sample units for the in-depth interviews. The reason for deciding to use two non-probability sampling methods in one research was because the researcher divided all the potential interviewees under two categories, which are trainee group and trainer group. The interviews conducted with the participants who normally attend training sessions at work as trainees aimed to collect their experiences, feelings and thoughts about the latest training activities that they involved. In the meanwhile, the interviews conducted with the participants who normally deliver training sessions at work as trainers aimed to collect their experiences and thoughts about training design and training strategies that adopted in the selected organisation. Therefore, they shared the different set of characteristics. As a result, the researcher believed the proper way was to apply two sampling methods for guaranteeing the accuracy of the data.

The reason for choosing the judgemental sampling method was because the researcher selects the sample units by herself according to the purpose of the interviews. As discussed in the previous part, all the frontline employees work in the chosen luxury brand's stores that locate in Heathrow airport terminals were selected as the sample frame of this study. The researcher decided to select the store in which she worked as a sample unit. There were two reasons for making this decision. Firstly, it was more likely for the researcher to gain access by selecting the store where she worked. Secondly, she put the budget and time constraints into consideration. There are 17 employees working in that store, included managers, sales and stockroom staff. According to her judgement, the researcher selected six out of seventeen of them. The chosen sample units included the store manager, assistant store manager, duty manager, key holder and two sales associates. The criterion for the sample units was based on the contributions they could make to this research. Due to their various job responsibilities in the store, they provided an overall image about on-the-job training experience from different perspectives.

The reason for choosing the snowball sampling method was because there was only one trainer who delivered the training activities to all four stores in Heathrow airport terminals. In order to find the most appropriate participant who is also an experienced trainer in the chosen organisation, snowball sampling technique provided the researcher a better way to decide the

sample units. Therefore, she discussed with the trainer she knows well about her topic and asked for her help to gain the permission for conducting the interviews. After she gained the permission, she invited the potential participants that were recommended by the trainer she knows from work. In total, four retail trainers who also work in the selected organisation agreed to participate in this study. As there are fewer than ten retail trainers employed in the chosen luxury brand's London area, the researcher believed that the sample size is representative of the target population.

Regarding the questionnaires, the researcher considered it as a tool to reach a broader range of target population to understand their ideas that are related to the research objectives of this study. By considering the time constraints, the researcher decided to adopt online questionnaires. The link for the online questionnaire was shared with the chosen luxury brand's London based frontline employees through the researcher's internal work email account.

3.2.7 Ethical & Access

Speaking about research ethics, it is considered as a researcher's 'inner duties' that urge him/her to critically examine his/her thoughts and actions through the process of a research (Symon and Cassell, 2012, p.91). At the same time, it also refers to the 'ethical principles and standards' in the context of business and management research (Quinlan *et al.*, 2015, p. 41). As this is a mixed-method research about on-the-job training activities in a chosen luxury firm, it involved a lot of human participants. The researcher understood the importance to adhere to ethical principles in conducting this research project. In the following paragraphs, she explains how she conducted the project ethically.

Firstly, the researcher conducted this project with the use of the principle of transparency. It is because transparency is critical in conducting research ethically (Quinlan *et al.*, 2015, p. 43). By adhering to this rule, the researcher was open with everyone who engaged in this research project about the nature of her research and the choice of the research methods. With her supervisor, she reported the progress relates to the research design while arising problems she dealt with for solutions monthly. For the participants who were considering their involvement, she provided them with sufficient information about her research, such as the nature of her research design, research strategy, data-gathering and analysis methods. She encouraged the participants to speak out their thoughts, and she answered their inquiries with great patience. As a result of the use of openness in the design and development of this research, it did not

only prevent the participants from the potential pitfalls but also helped the researcher to build the trust with them.

Secondly, the researcher conducted this study with the use of the principle of integrity. It is because integrity has been recognised as one of another important research ethics (Easterby-Smith *et al.*, 2015, p. 122; Quinlan *et al.*, 2015, p. 43). By adhering to carry out her research with integrity, the researcher of this study clearly demonstrated the idea of her research, the research design, the techniques for data collection and data analysis and the way of presenting the findings to the authority of the university and gained the ethical approval for conducting this research. Then she requested the permission of conducting the research in the chosen organisation. As she worked there as a part-time sales associate, she explained the nature of her study and the possible benefits to the company to her management team. She also provided them with the ethical approval letter from the university. With their knowledge of the researcher and proof that no harm would come to the organisation, they trusted the researcher's intention of conducting the research ethically and granted her access to the field of the research project to collect data. As a result of the use of honesty through the research process, it urged the researcher to conduct the research the way she promised.

Thirdly, the principle of avoidance of harm has been strictly followed. In the early stage of this study, the researcher kept everything that relates to the research open to all the participants to avoid any potential risk that would harm them. During the data-gathering stage, the participants were informed about the purpose of research and the possible effects of taking part. In order to avoid bringing any harm to them, they were given the opportunity to withdraw the research at any time they wanted. For those who were intended to engage in the face-to-face interviews, the information about the level of their involvement and expected duration of the interviews has been provided before the scheduled interviews took place. For those who got involved in the observed activities, they were provided with the information about what the researcher aimed to observe and recorded as the data during the observations. The participants allowed to speak out what concerned them the most and the researcher did her best to avoid the risk of harm. As a result of putting herself in their shoes to acknowledge the participants' interests through the research process, the researcher ensured that nothing would make the participants uncomfortable or stressful or threatened during the study.

Finally, the principles of the confidentiality of the provided data and the anonymity of the individual participants have been adhered to by the researcher in this project. The researcher kept her agreement with the participants those who involved in this study about storing the data collected from this research confidentially and remaining the identities of the participants of this project anonymously. The information about confidentiality and anonymity has been emphasised in both the participant information sheet and the consent form. Those two documents have been provided to all the participants who decided to engage in this research before the data-gathering stage started. Only after those two forms have been agreed with all the participants, the researcher began to carry out the study within the selected organisation.

Chapter 4 - Data Acquisition, Analysis & Findings

In this chapter, the data is the main focus. It is developed with the details of how the data was collected and analysed in this research. The purpose of this study is to explore the training activities at the selected luxury brand to develop an understanding of how the on-the-job training works, i.e., what the processes the chosen luxury company uses from the training design stage till the final delivery of a session. Furthermore, this research was also designed to find out the impact of the learning activities at work on the frontline employees in the context of the luxury business environment. As a result, the data that gathered are mainly qualitative by adopting both the in-depth one-to-one interviews and the observations. But in the meantime, the questionnaires, which are more popular in the quantitative studies, were also employed in this study to testify the reliability of the qualitative data collected. As a theoretical framework was built as the result of the evidence collected from the empirical studies on both the topics of organisational training and the business model in the luxury industry, the feasibility of this framework in practice was examined and improved by the data gathered in this study. In order to achieve this purpose, the data were analysed through coding process, and categorised and interpreted by applying the grounded theory method.

In order to provide readers with a clear understanding of how the data was gathered in this research, the chapter starts with the choice on the data collection methods, then, the data gathering process is presented to bring readers the visual experience. It follows by the decisions made on the appropriate data analysis methods, and, at last readers are invited to take part in the data analysis process.

4.1 Data Acquisition

4.1.1 In-depth One-to-One Interviews

In this study, seventy-five percent of the data collected are qualitative, as this study aimed to understand the one-the-job training activity at the selected luxury company through learning from the first-hand experience and attitudes towards it. In order to fully capture what the

employees think and the things that have happened to them, in-depth interview data gathering method has been considered as the most suitable approach for the purpose of this study.

There were two types of the interviewees included in this study. They were all chosen from the employees of the selected luxury brand. These two types of participants included some frontline staff members who always attend training sessions at work and some retail trainers who are the experts in the training field. By dividing the interviewees into these two categories, the data collected from the interviews can display the whole picture with both of these two sides of the story. There were six trainee participants and four trainer participants that have been chosen and included in the interviews of this study.

4.1.1.1 Choosing the Interviewees

a Trainees

These six participants are all from the boutique, at where the researcher used to work. The reason for picking the potential interviewees there, was due to her familiarity with the team. By doing this, it helped to gain access. In the meantime, it ensured the suitable candidates were chosen for the purpose of this research.

Among them, the picked participants work in various positions in the same store of the chosen luxury brand, i.e. from the management to the team members. Specifically, three of them work at the management level. The rest of the participants are all sales associates.

The choice of these interviewees was not made randomly but planned carefully. About the selected managers, the reason why they were considered suitable was because of the broader range of the training courses that they are entitled to attend at work. By conducting a one-to-one conversation with each of them, the researcher explored their personal experience in participating in various learning programs at work in depth. In the meantime, all of them have been taking part in delivering some sessions in collaborations with the retail trainers at work. By giving the opportunity to share the knowledge that they have gained through such work experience, it has been considered as useful to be applied to examine the feasibility of the theoretical training framework that was developed with the information that was obtained from some empirical studies.

About the other selected team members, three of them were also not chosen at random. Although their job titles are the same, their experience with the selected luxury brand varies from person to person. One of them has been working as a sales associate at this company for 12 years; therefore, this member's experience that has gained through this many-year working

at the same organisation has been considered as valuable for this study. Another one of them is responsible for the visual merchandising function within the store, though she also works as a sales associate. Because of the additional job role at work, this participant was expected to provide information about the training sessions that were designed mainly for visual merchandisers. As most of the sales associates only would be entitled to attend retail-related courses at work, this different experience has been applied to make a comparison with others. At last, the third participant, who was a sales associate, was selected to take part in this research was because she used to work on a part-time basis. As the work hours are different between full-time and part-time employees, the conversation with this participant was helpful to understand what the special arrangement the chosen company made for the part-timers to accommodate them to the timetable for some training sessions.

b Trainers

The same rule has been applied when it comes to the choice of the trainer interviewees, as every one of them has been selected for a specific reason. There were four professional trainers, who work at the selected luxury brand, have been chosen to take part in this research. As the brand has its stores in multiple locations, i.e. highstreets, airport terminals and the outlets, the trainers are working under varying conditions. Therefore, the participants of this study were chosen from relatively unique working environments in order to reflect different training practices.

In the meantime, they shared quite a different career path, though they are all working as trainers at the selected luxury brand currently. Among these four participants, two of them came from a training educational background while the other two switched their career path from taking a sales associate role to a trainer's role at the selected company. This difference in personal experience has had an impact on the way they work as a trainer. Therefore, the data of the one-to-one interviews with each of them was helpful to understand their different approaches to training.

Last but not least, they all have been working in the luxury industry for a long time. As this research was not only about the on-the-job learning practices, but also about the luxury world; thus, how the correlation between the training activity and the luxury environment works was the question that this study tried to answer. Therefore, their experience of working as a trainer in the luxury brand has provided this research valuable information on the reason why the on-the-job training activity is more important in the luxury world. Especially, three of these four

trainer participants have been with this selected luxury brand for over five years at least; their participation gave great insights into the brand's attitude change towards the importance of the training function among the years they work there.

4.1.1.2 Conducting In-depth Interviews

a Before the Interviews

After the request of accessing to participants of this research was granted, the key information on this study, which included the main research aim, the background of this study and the theoretical framework, has been provided to all the interviewees via email to prepare themselves for the coming interviews. In the meantime, an agreement on the time and location of the one-to-one interview has been reached with each of the interviewees separately. According to them, all the interviewees felt comfortable; and agreed it was convenient to conduct the interviews during the working day. The researcher accommodated to each of the participants' work schedule. About the location, the staff canteen and coffee places located around their offices have been preferred. By also taking the quality of the audio-recording of the interviews into the consideration, the locations that were ultimately chosen include Heathrow Terminal four staff canteen, Elan Café at Selfridges, Starbucks Coffee in Vigo Street, and Pret A Manger on Vauxhall Bridge Road.

Then, another email that included the participant information sheet and the participant consent form was sent to each of the candidate a week before the interviews took place, as an assurance to reduce their anxieties. In this email, it also contained a sample of questions that might be asked during the interviews to boost their confidence in expressing themselves during the interviews.

b During the Interviews

The researcher conducted ten separate person-to-person interviews with all the chosen participants once a time. At the beginning of each interview, the first couple of minutes of casual conversation helped to put the interviewee at ease. As all the candidates work in the same organisation as did the researcher herself, especially most of them were from the same team, the familiarity was also helpful for shaping the start of every interview.

When the interviewee became more relaxed, the participant information sheet was presented and explained again to clear the uncertainties about providing information. Fortunately, all the interviewees agreed to give their consent to take part in this research and signed the participant consent forms before the interviews started.

During the process of each in-depth interview, some open questions were applied to start the conversation. The questions for the trainer participants and the trainee participants were not the same as the areas that the researcher was interested in exploring from each side were different. That is, the work experience of the trainer interviewees was helpful to find out the current training strategy that is employed at the selected luxury brand, i.e. how a session is designed, delivered and evaluated. But the training experience of the trainee interviewees provided an extensive answer to understand the impact of the learning activity on their daily work performance, i.e. whether the training programs have effectively prepared them with the right mindset to work in the luxury industry. A sample of open questions that were applied in the interviews are listed as follows,

For trainees

Q1: How frequently do you attend the training at work?

Q2: How was your most recent training experience?

Q3: How did you apply the new knowledge from the most recent training to your job?

For trainers

Q1: How do you identify the training needs at work?

Q2: How do you develop the training course based on the needs?

Q3: How do you evaluate the effectiveness of a training session?

For most of the time during the interviews, the interviewee was given the opportunity to talk freely about his/her personal experience and reflections on the on-the-job trainings that offered by the selected luxury brand. In the meantime, some probing questions were also applied to extend the conversations. A sample of probing questions that were used in the interviews are listed as follows,

Q1: Tell me more about the activities. What did you have during that event?

Q2: How would you evaluate the effectiveness of the training session you just talked about?

Q3: What if the first pilot session is not good enough?

Q4: That is interesting. What do you mean by tweaking as a means to tailor the session for meeting the certain needs?

4.1.1.3 Reflections on the Process

Although the interviews were well-planned, there are still some limitations in the process of data collection, as this was the researcher's first time to conduct ten person-to-person in-depth interviews all by herself. To start with the interview questioning techniques, it is clear that the use of the open questions could help to reduce the bias. However, sometimes the probing questions that were used were the close-ended questions, for example, 'Can I understand that they access the needs from the corporate's perspective?' or 'Do you only discuss with the management or also include other employees?'. Obviously, the researcher reflected on the point that was made by the interviewee and tried to paraphrase it with her own words. However, she was too involved in the conversation to pay attention to the choice of her questions.

Furthermore, in the very first couple of interviews the researcher failed to apply her attentive listening skills. This was because that she is very interested in this topic and would love to learn as much as possible from the participants; therefore, her curiosity aroused by a certain point that was made by some interviewee rushed her to express her own thoughts by interrupting the conversation.

Both of these that were mentioned above, were due to the lack of interview experience by the researcher. However, this changed through the process as the interviewer reviewed the transcript of the previous sessions ahead of upcoming interviews. However, the quality of the data collected in the interviews was not consistent.

4.1.2 Observations

Among this seventy-five percent of the qualitative data, a small amount of them were collected by applying participant observation qualitative data gathering method in this study. The decision on using observations was made based on the research objectives, which are related to what people at the selected brand usually do training at work. Since the researcher worked as a part-time sales associate at the chosen luxury company, she had an excellent opportunity to understand the on-the-job training activities by taking part in the process. By doing this, she did not only observe how the session was taken place, but also experienced it and felt it from a trainee's perspective. The observation in this study is not the main method to collect the qualitative data but an approach to improve the quality of the data gathered from the in-depth interviews. The idea was not to collect too much data but to add the richness of it.

4.1.2.1 Data Collection through Observations

In total, the researcher observed two sessions that she attended fully as a participant at work for the purpose of this study. Both of these two sessions she observed during her participation, she received the approval from the relevant trainers on conducting the observations. In the meantime, she also revealed her role as an observer to the other participants in these two sessions. One of these two training programs was a one-day session and the other one was a three-hour course. Fortunately, these two represent very different situations, regarding the training methods, delivery and the interactions with the trainees.

The one-day training session was held in the meeting room at the Westfield shopping centre that is located in London's Shepherd's Bush area. This training session was organised to educate the brand's front-line staff with the knowledge of the brand's new designer's debut collection. It was an important session as the brand was in the transition after the former Chief Designer left the job after his 17-year journey with the company. Therefore, it was a compulsory session for all the brand's front-line staff. The other three-hour course took place at the meeting room in a terminal at London Heathrow airport. It was organised by the local retail trainer to prepare the brand's front-line staff members, who locate in the stores at the terminals of the Heathrow airport, for the coming festival season by refreshing their memories of the key knowledge, i.e. product knowledge and service standard. This was also a compulsory training session for all the chosen candidates.

During these two sessions, the researcher made notes on everything she observed as a participant, for example, the physical settings of the training room, the process of the session, the training methods that trainers applied, trainers' performance, trainees' reactions and activities. In the meantime, she also recorded her own feelings involved in the process of the course. Furthermore, certain aspects of these two sessions piqued the researcher's interest. Taking the one-day session as an example, the trainer's teaching style and trainees' involvement in the outdoor activities aroused the researcher's curiosity. About the other three-hour course, she was eager to learn the reactions from the trainer to face an unexpected situation. Therefore, she also focused on these aspects that caught her attention during these two sessions, apart from involving herself in both of them as a participant. All of these notes she made were helpful to assist her to write the memos after she returned home. In her memos, she not only narrated what happened in these two events, but also critically examined those special moments that she focused her attention on during these two sessions with her own feelings and experiences. The memos were made for the purpose of the analysis.

4.1.2.2 Reflections on the Process

Although the choice of applying the observation data collection method was made based on the aim of this study, the limitation still exists. Firstly, an observation needs to be planned and designed thoroughly. However, the researcher did not have too many choices on which training session might be interesting to observe as she only worked at the selected luxury brand as a part-timer. It was difficult for the management team to accommodate every training schedule alongside her work shifts. As a result, only a few courses she was able to attend at work. Most of the time, she was only informed with the timetable of the coming training session until the last minute. She had to rush into planning the observation schedule while requesting the permission from the organiser of the session. Therefore, it is important to be aware that the vigour of the observation might be arguable. Secondly, the rule of consistency has not been fully followed during the observations. This is the very first time for the researcher to play the participant-as-observer role to collect qualitative data in practice. Sometimes, she left her role as an observer behind when she fully concentrated on the context of a training session. It is clear that she definitely needs more practice to help her to switch from a participant to an observer smoothly and vice versa.

4.1.3 Questionnaires

In this study, the questionnaires were also used to collect data. This method is usually most preferred in a quantitative research as it is designed to engage a large number of target population. But the decision of including this data collection approach is not contrary to the purpose of this study. The reason for having the questionnaires was to verify the validity of the qualitative data collected through both the in-depth interviews and the observations. The researcher believed the mixture of both qualitative and quantitative method for the data collection provided the possibility of avoiding bias in qualitative research. But the main focus of this study was to explore people's feelings and experiences regarding the on-the-job training activity, this quantitative data collection method was only applied to supplement other methods. Therefore, only 15% of the data were gathered through questionnaires in this research.

4.1.3.1 Data Collection through Questionnaires

The questions that were included in the questionnaire were designed to collect the selected brand's frontline employees' opinions on both the success of the most recent training program itself and its effectiveness on affecting individual's work performance. Both these two aspects are critical, regarding the aim of this study. The factors that would affect the success of a

training session include the training design, the delivery of the session, trainer’ performance and the interactions with the trainees. Furthermore, this study also aimed to examine the effectiveness of training transfer after a session, as having a satisfied training course is not considered as the end of a training circle. However, the effect of training on the jobs is not a phenomenon that can be easily observed. Instead, it can be reflected in the trainee’s work performance and attitude change. Therefore, twelve questions that are included in the questionnaire were designed to gather the factual information regarding these two criteria from the trainee’s perspectives. These twelve rating-scale questions were all designed to be simple, clear and precise.

The three hundred employees that work at the brand’s London stores were chosen as target population. The on-line questionnaire was created by using Google Forms. The link of the online questionnaire has been distributed through the internal company email system, with the explanation of the purpose of this study in details. In total, the researcher received one hundred responses. All the questions that were used in the questionnaire are listed in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Questions	Variables	Detail in which data measured
Q1. I am satisfied with what I have learned from the most recent training that I attended.	Strongly Agree; Agree; Neutral; Disagree; Strongly Disagree	trainee’s opinions on training needs assessment
Q2. I think the most recent training program that I attended was effective in achieving the learning objectives.	Strongly Agree; Agree; Neutral; Disagree; Strongly Disagree	trainee’s opinions on training delivery
Q3. The most recent training session was easy for me to follow and understand.	Strongly Agree; Agree; Neutral; Disagree; Strongly Disagree	trainee’s opinions on training design
Q4. The multimedia materials were clearly visible and audible during the most recent training.	Strongly Agree; Agree; Neutral; Disagree; Strongly Disagree	trainee’s opinions on training delivery

Q5. The presentation slides used in the most recent training session were well-designed and appealing.	Strongly Agree; Agree; Neutral; Disagree; Strongly Disagree	trainee's opinions on training design
Q6. On a scale of 1-5, how engaging was the most recent training session?	1/ 2/ 3/ 4/ 5 (5 means the most engaging.)	trainee's opinions on training delivery
Q7. The trainer was knowledgeable about the subject matter.	Strongly Agree; Agree; Neutral; Disagree; Strongly Disagree	trainee's opinions on training delivery
Q8. Were you satisfied with the interactivity provided by the most recent training?	Strongly Agree; Agree; Neutral; Disagree; Strongly Disagree	trainee's opinions on training design
Q9. I usually have a clear idea about the learning objectives before attending a training program conducted by my organisation.	Strongly Agree; Agree; Neutral; Disagree; Strongly Disagree	trainee's opinions on learning environment at work
Q10. I understand how to apply the knowledge from the training session to my job.	Strongly Agree; Agree; Neutral; Disagree; Strongly Disagree	trainee's opinions on training transfer
Q11. I have the opportunity to apply the knowledge from training to my job.	Strongly Agree; Agree; Neutral; Disagree; Strongly Disagree	trainee's opinions on training transfer
Q12. I will be interested in taking training sessions designed for my future career development.	Strongly Agree; Agree; Neutral; Disagree; Strongly Disagree	trainee's opinions on learning environment at work

Table 4-1. Questions Used in Questionnaire

4.1.3.2 Reflections on the Process

Although the on-line questionnaire was well-designed, there is still something the researcher would improve if she is going to apply the questionnaires again in her future study in this field. As all of the questions were prepared in the early stage of this research, the researcher's understanding on the chosen research objectives were limited by then. This was a new area that she felt interested in. Her knowledge on this area accumulated through the intensive reading and data collection, her thoughts on those questions from the questionnaire changed. Some certain questions were not included as she could not figure them out in the early exploring stage. For example, there are only two questions about the training transfer. They could not reveal the real situation regarding how much knowledge would retain and be used after a session. Therefore, the possible improvement made to the questions could help to provide higher quality data to the research.

4.2 Data Analysis

4.2.1 Methods and Data Presentation

4.2.1.1 Grounded Theory Method

The decision on applying the grounded theory method in the process of analysing the qualitative data that was collected in this research, has been made mainly because this study is designed to employ the grounded theory to guide the entire research from gathering the data, analysing the data, interpreting the data till developing the theory that is grounded in the data. As 'in grounded theory, data analysis has a well-defined process' (Patton, 2002, quoted in Walker and Myrick, 2006), Strauss and Corbin's three-phased coding method, which includes 'open, axial, and selective' is applied in this study (Strauss and Corbin, 1990). The reason for following the process suggested by Strauss and Corbin instead of the one that is recommended by Glaser (1978) is because the latter requires a longer timeframe as 'only patience, persistence, and going over and over the data using constant comparison will lead to emergent categories and their properties' (Walker and Myrick, 2006). Within the time constraints, a more systematic way of data analysis would provide more guidance in the analytical process of this research.

4.2.1.2 Introduction to Data Presentation

As all the data in this study is analysed by the researcher manually, the process of data analysis is clearly presented in the following paragraphs to provide readers a full picture of this stage

of the research. Regarding the qualitative data (interview data & observation data), Strauss and Corbin's three-phased coding method (1990) is applied. Specifically, the initial codes as a result of In Vivo coding are quoted in italics upper case, for example, "MANAGER, MORE CHOICES". Meanwhile, the links among codes and the relationships among core categories are presented in figures. Regarding the quantitative data (questionnaire data), the results are also demonstrated in figures.

4.2.2 Interview Data

Among all the qualitative data collected in this study, most of them were gathered from the in-depth interviews. Through conducting these ten person-to-person interviews, the chosen participants that work at the selected luxury company shared their experience of the on-the-job training activity very detailed and thorough. In order to clarify what they really expressed; the grounded theory method has been chosen to guide the analytical procedure. As a result, In Vivo coding, Axial coding and Selective coding have been applied to code, condense and categorise the interview data. At last, the theory, which is grounded in the data, is developed.

In this study, the researcher insisted on conducting the data analysis manually, instead of using computer software, as she believes that computer-driven data analysis method could be good at measuring the quantity of data but not the quality. By analysing the data with the human cognition, the messages that are embedded in the contexts would be more easily revealed. Therefore, the analytical research memos were updated with a complete record of activities, thoughts and findings on a daily basis.

Before the analysis was taken place, the audio interview recordings have been transcribed to text. All of the transcripts were saved under two folders, which are the trainer folder and the trainee folder. The profile name of each interview transcript includes the interviewee's gender, job title, the location and the date of the interview. At the beginning of the data analysis stage, some of the first cycle coding methods have been chosen, for instance, attribute coding method, holistic coding method and In-Vivo coding method. After reorganising the codes generated in the first coding processes through the code mapping technique, the condensed codes were categorised to build theory during the second cycle processes, which includes axial coding and selective coding method.

4.2.2.1 In Vivo Coding

In the initial step of the coding process, open coding is suggested as the method of the first phase by not only Glaser (1978) but also Strauss and Corbin (1990). About Open coding, it

refers to ‘every way possible’ (Glaser, 1978, pp.56). Since it is the researcher’s decision to make on the way to code the data, In Vivo coding was chosen to act as the first step into the coding process. The reason for selecting In Vivo coding is because the researcher intended to let the interviewees tell their stories. As the meaning of in vivo means ‘in that which is alive’ (Strauss, 1987, quoted in Saldaña, 2016, pp.105), this coding method would be the most appropriate to give voice to the participants to let them express their opinions on the studied phenomenon.

In the process of first coding cycle, the data of each interview was transcribed and coded on the same day as the interview was conducted. By doing this, anything that was missed but ‘salient to the area under study’ could be examined during the next interview (Corbin and Strauss, 1990). Every interview transcript was coded line by line with interviewee’s ‘word or short phrase’ (Saldaña, 2016, pp.105), according to the guidance from In Vivo coding. In the meantime, the researcher made a note of her thoughts and everything that brought her attention that was necessary to keep track of in the analytic memos, during the coding process of each interview transcript. In total, there are five hundred and fifty-five codes generated in the process of In Vivo coding. By comparing the codes among all the interview transcripts, some patterns have been noticed.

Group 1: Discussions on Training Needs

Firstly, all the participants discussed training needs in the interviews, though it is clear that the dimensions of their views on the needs of training vary. In the interviews with the chosen trainees, particular training needs were revealed from their reflections on some sessions they attended at work. During the conversations with the selected trainer participants, they identified the training needs through sharing their work experience of training needs analysis. Although all the trainee interviewees who work in the management team had the responsibility in training at work, their focuses regarding training needs were on the local initiatives while the members from the trainer group reviewed this topic from both a macro and a micro level. These pieces of evidence clearly demonstrate the importance of training needs analysis in a training cycle. By taking all the codes that are related to the needs of training from all interview transcripts into consideration, there are nine codes that are kept after the process of condensing the data. They are listed as follows,

“ASSESS THE TRAINING NEEDS”

“CORPORATE LEVEL: DIRECTION FROM CORPORATE”

“STORE LEVEL: TEAMS, INDIVIDUAL NEEDS”

“NEVER RUNNING OUT OF THINGS”

“NEEDS ASSESSMENT IS IMPORTANT”

“MANAGER, MORE CHOICES”

“YOUR OPINION, NOT IMPORTANT”

“ASK OUR OPINIONS”

“DON’T VALUE US”

Group 2: Reflections on Training Design

Secondly, there is a great amount of information on training design. Most of the details about the process of preparing for a session were shared by the interviewees who work as a trainer at work, while a small amount of them were provided by those who work as a manager in the chosen firm. By contrast, the experience shared by some of the trainee participants is more about how to assist trainers in getting ready for certain course, while the trainer participants provided the researcher with the whole picture. At the same time, some data also represent the opinions from a trainee’s perspective based on what they have experienced in the workplace. To make the data more manageable, all the codes that are related to the process of training design from all interview transcripts were selected and condensed. As a result, there are fifteen codes that are kept and listed as follows,

“MATERIALS, TIME, ACTIVITIES”

“WHO ORGANISES”

“WHERE YOU PRESENT”

“WHAT TO ACHIEVE, HOW DELIVER”

“AGREE ON A SCHEDULE TRAINING”

“THE CONTENT OF TRAINING”

“KNOWING WHO LEARNS AND HOW”

“BEST METHODS, DEPEND ON THE MESSAGE”

“DESIGN ONE SUIT ALL”

“DON’T LIKE ACTIVITIES”

“TOO FREQUENT, GET ANNOYED”

“PREFER SOMETHING PRACTICAL”

“NOT AT SCHOOL ANYMORE”

“HAVE TO GIVE UP BREAK TIME”

“MERGE PERSONALITY AND COURSE”

Group 3: Experiences of Training Delivery

Thirdly, it is noticeable that training delivery has been repeatedly discussed and was given many details by all the interviewees from various perspectives. In the interviews with the trainees, they recalled how those sessions they have attended were organised and how those arrangements made them feel, for instance, the interactions between trainers and trainees, the training schedule, or the quality of the delivery. On the other hand, the trainer interviewees presented this study with rich details about scenario-based training examples to explain how to deliver a session in practice. After reorganised all the codes that are related to training delivery from all interview transcripts, there are thirteen codes that are kept and listed as follows,

“BRING THIS TO LIFE”

“TONES, BODY LANGUAGE, ACTIVITIES”

“THINK ABOUT YOUR AUDIENCE”

“EVALUATION: TRAINING PROGRAM ITSELF”

“BEING FLEXIBLE TO FACILITATE SESSION”

“AN OPEN-TABLE DISCUSSION”

“INTERESTING BUT CHALLENGING”

“IMPROVE”

“NOT SATISFIED”

“CHOSEN MANAGER, NOT PROFESSIONAL”

“FEW PEOPLE THERE”

“NO ENOUGH EXPLANATIONS”

“ENJOYED”

Group 4: Current Learning Atmosphere at Work

Fourthly, the idea of creating a learning environment in the workplace has been repeatedly linked to the effectiveness of on-the-job training activities. During the interviews, the situation regarding learning atmosphere within the selected luxury brand has been reviewed from various dimensions. The trainers reviewed it from a business perspective, while the trainees discussed it based on their experience and expectations. The detailed evidence plays a critical role in having a better understanding of the current learning atmosphere in the chosen company. By taking all the codes that are related to the learning environment from all interview transcripts into consideration, there are eighteen codes that are kept after the process of condensing the data. They are presented as follows,

“CREATING A LEARNING ENVIRONMENT”

“UNDERSTAND THE IMPACT”

“TRANSITION”

“LONG-TERM VISION”

“CHANGE, LITTLE BY LITTLE”

“DON'T WANT TO ATTEND”

“TOLD TO GO, HAVE TO GO”

“NEED ENCOURAGEMENT FROM MANAGEMENT”

“COMFORTABLE TO EXPRESS THOUGHTS”

“MOTIVATION, CHANGE ATTITUDES”

“WILLING TO GET INVOLVED, MINDSET”

“IMPORTANT, EVERYONE TO BE TRAINED”

“TREAT COURSES AS INVESTMENT”

“YOUR GROWTH MATTERS BRAND’S GROWTH”

“HAPPY TO APPLY TO THE JOB”

“NICE TO LEARN, SHARE, DISCUSS”

“YOU DID WELL”

“MADE TIME FOR IT”

Group 5: The Influence of Training Evaluation on Training Transfer

Then, a significant link between training evaluation and training transfer was captured in the qualitative data collected in this study. From the trainer’s perspective, a specific set of operations that is normally applied to evaluate a training session has been prepared and provided. In the meantime, the necessity of conducting training evaluation afterwards has been emphasised by the trainee participants with examples to demonstrate both good and bad situations they have experienced at work. From the evidence that was given on both training transfer and training evaluation by these participants during the interviews, it is clear to see the relationship between these two variables. By filtering all the codes that are related to the success of a training program, which includes both training evaluation and training transfer, there are fourteen codes that are kept after the process of condensing the data. They are presented as follows,

“EVALUATION: HOW SUCCESSFUL THE PROGRAM IS”

“EFFECTIVE”

“IMMEDIATE TRANSFER, TELLING STORIES AND SALES”

“LONG-TERM, ATTITUDE CHANGED”

“EVALUATE WITH FIGURES, KNOWLEDGE CHECKS, OBSERVATIONS”

“A LOT OF TIME, TEAM REMEMBER”

“GAIN CONFIDENCE”

“VIVIDLY, REMEMBER DETAILS”

“NOT THE CASE FOR US”

“IRRELEVANT”

“CANNOT BE APPLIED”

“ONLY 30%, LEARNT, USEFUL”

“A LITTLE KNOWLEDGE, BENEFIT CAREER”

“YOU DO FORGET THINGS”

Group 6: Views on Making Plans for Training Evaluation

Furthermore, an argument over whether there should be an evaluation plan in the training design stage caught the researcher’s attention during data analysis. All the trainer participants expressed their opinions based on each of their individual work experience. By contrast, some of them prefer making decisions on how to evaluate a session during the training delivery stage, while others emphasise the importance of having an evaluation plan in the early design stage. At the same time, a suggestion was made by one of the trainers about having a check-in point at every step in a training cycle to ensure the key training objectives are being met. After reorganising all the codes about both evaluation plan and evaluation point from the interview transcripts, there are seven codes that are kept and listed as follows,

“EVERY POINT, AN EVALUATION”

“A CHECKING”

“KEEP YOU ON TRACK”

“ESTABLISH FROM BEGINNING, EVALUATE AT THE END”

“MERGE WITH TRAINING STAGE”

“AFTER SESSION”

“UNTIL YOU PRACTICE, NOT ABLE TO EVALUATE”

Group 7: Current Guidelines on Trainer’s Performance

In the meantime, the routine procedures that the trainer participants apply in their daily work were presented and discussed during the interviews. Apparently, there is not a set of rules to guide the trainers through the process of training at the selected luxury brand. Every trainer interviewee has a unique way of managing day-to-day work. These pieces of information would be useful in the theory developing stage to provide the guidance in building the training

framework in this study. After filtering and reorganising the codes that are related to training guidelines, there are six codes that are kept and presented as follows,

“TRAINING ANALYSIS, A ROUND CIRCLE”

“CULTURE OF TRAINING, MENTALITY, COME BEFORE”

“THE NORMAL PROCEDURE”

“NEEDS ASSESSMENT, CONSIDER WHAT TO DO, THEN LAUNCH”

“DESIGN, LAUNCH, EVALUATE THE PROGRAM ITSELF”

“EVALUATE THE SUCCESS OF PROGRAM”

Group 8: Importance of Training in Luxury Business

Then, about the relationship between the impact of training and the luxury industry, most of the interviewees shared their opinions based on their work experience as employees in the luxury brand. All the relevant codes have been selected and condensed. Eventually, five codes are kept and presented as follows,

“GIVE YOU LUXURIOUS MINDSET”

“NEED MORE IN LUXURY”

“IMPORTANT TOOL, LUXURY INDUSTRY”

“LUXURY, ABOUT FASHION”

“LUXURY, ABOUT SERVICE”

Group 9: Comments on this Study's Theoretical Framework

At last, all the interviewees expressed their opinions on this study's theoretical framework that was generated in the early literature review stage of this research. The idea of this training model came from the knowledge gathered from empirical studies in the field of training. Therefore, the evidence collected from the in-depth interviews would be applied to testify whether this theoretical framework would be effectively applied in luxury companies. These pieces of information are also critical for developing new theory regarding the process of training as a result of the data analysis in this study. After filtered and reorganised, there are six codes that are kept and listed as follows,

“I LIKE YOUR FRAMEWORK”

“LOOKS GOOD”

“WOULD WORK IN REALITY”

“YOU ARE ON THE RIGHT TRACK”

“WELL ORGANISED”

“I LIKE, EVALUATION PLAN AND TRANSFER OF TRAINING”

In the end, there are nine groups of codes generated as a result of applying In Vivo coding method in the first coding cycle. Most of them are related to the steps in a training cycle, while the rest of the categories are about individual feelings towards their training experience.

4.2.2.2 Axial Coding

Through the initial step of the coding process, the codes revealed what is significant to the interviewees regarding the research objectives with their own words and expressions. After the initial codes were reorganised and filtered, some categories were formed with sets of initial codes that were kept after data condensation. In the second coding cycle, Axial coding method was applied, as it is the second of Strauss and Corbin’s three-phased coding method (Strauss and Corbin, 1990). Through employing Axial coding method, the relationship among a set of initial codes within a category can be identified, as this approach ‘aims to link categories with subcategories and asks how they are related’ (Charmaz, 2014, pp.148).

Category 1: “ASSESS THE TRAINING NEEDS”

The first category consists of nine initial codes (see Group 1: Discussions on Training Needs). Among them, there are some codes about the measures that are taken to assess the training needs, for instance, “CORPORATE LEVEL: DIRECTION FROM CORPORATE” and “STORE LEVEL: TEAMS, INDIVIDUAL NEEDS”. There are certain codes to express individual attitudes reflecting on the actions that were taken to analyse the training needs at work, such as, “MANAGER, MORE CHOICES”, “YOUR OPINION, NOT IMPORTANT”, “ASK OUR OPINIONS” and “DON’T VALUE US”. In the meantime, there are also some codes that are inspired by trainer interviewees to demonstrate their thoughts on training needs analysis, for example, “NEVER RUNNING OUT OF THINGS” and “NEEDS ASSESSMENT IS IMPORTANT”. It is clear to see the similarity all the codes in this group share. That is, they are all related to training needs assessment. Therefore, the code “ASSESS THE TRAINING

NEEDS” is chosen and transformed as a category in this coding stage to summarise the main idea of all the other codes in this group. However, “ASSESS THE TRAINING NEEDS” as a category represents a broader concept. Under it, multiple layers were formed to detail all the procedures and individual’s opinions regarding this step in a training circle (see Figure 4-1). The relationships among the main category code and subcategory codes are demonstrated and explained in Appendix E.

Figure 4-1. Interview Data - Axial Coding: Training Needs Assessment Overview

Category 2: “MATERIALS, TIME, ACTIVITIES”

The second category consists of fifteen initial codes (see Group 2: Reflections on Training Design). Some of these codes are the factors that would affect training design, for instance, “WHO ORGANISES”, “WHERE YOU PRESENT”, “WHAT TO ACHIEVE, HOW DELIVER”, “AGREE ON A SCHEDULE TRAINING” and “THE CONTENT OF TRAINING”. Some of them emphasise the influence of audience’s personality on the choice of training methods, such as, “KNOWING WHO LEARNS AND HOW” and “MERGE PERSONALITY AND COURSE”. There are also some codes, which reveal the conflict between the chosen training methods and individual’s preferences, for example, “DON’T

LIKE ACTIVITIES”, “PREFER SOMETHING PRACTICAL” and “NOT AT SCHOOL ANYMORE”. Furthermore, some codes are inspired by trainer interviewee’s unique experience on training design, for example, “BEST METHODS, DEPEND ON THE MESSAGE” and “DESIGN ONE SUIT ALL”. There are also codes that captured some trainee interviewee’s negative attitude towards the training schedule organised at work, for example, “TOO FREQUENT, GET ANNOYED” and “HAVE TO GIVE UP BREAK TIME”. Obviously, the actions that all these codes represent in this category are within the boundary in which the process of training design occurs; and the code “MATERIALS, TIME, ACTIVITIES” can be used to summarise all the initial codes in this group. Therefore, it is chosen to represent this category in the process of the second coding cycle. The relationships among the main category code and other subcategory codes are demonstrated in Figure 4-2. The details among various layers under this category are explained and illustrated with figures in Appendix F.

Figure 4-2. Interview Data - Axial Coding: Training Design Factors Overview

Category 3: “BRING THIS TO LIFE”

In the third category, there are thirteen codes that are generated during the first coding cycle. All these codes are listed in Group 3: Experiences of Training Delivery. Among them, some codes indicate the techniques to conduct an effective session from a trainer’s perspective, for example, “TONES, BODY LANGUAGE, ACTIVITIES”, “THINK ABOUT YOUR AUDIENCE” and “BEING FLEXIBLE TO FACILITATE SESSION”. In the meantime, there are some codes to suggest the idea of evaluating the success of a training design through the training delivery, for instance, “EVALUATION: TRAINING PROGRAM ITSELF”, “AN

OPEN-TABLE DISCUSSION” and “IMPROVE”. Correspondingly, there are also certain codes in this group provide this research with both positive and negative feedback from the trainee interviewees on particular sessions that they attended at work, such as, “NOT SATISFIED”, “CHOSEN MANAGER, NOT PROFESSIONAL”, “FEW PEOPLE THERE”, “NO ENOUGH EXPLANATIONS”, “ENJOYED” and “INTERESTING BUT CHALLENGING”. Clearly, all the codes that are included in this group are all related to the training delivery stage; and what the code “BRING THIS TO LIFE” expresses can summarise all the important ideas that the other codes represent in this group. Therefore, this category is named with the code “BRING THIS TO LIFE” in the process of the second coding cycle. The links among the main category code and other subcategory codes are presented in Figure 4-3, while they are explained with details and illustrated with figures in Appendix G.

Figure 4-3. Interview Data - Axial Coding: Training Delivery Overview

Category 4: “CREATING A LEARNING ENVIRONMENT”

In the fourth category, it includes eighteen codes that were captured in the first coding cycle (see Group 4: Current Learning Atmosphere at Work). Some codes present a series of changes that happen within the selected luxury brand, regarding creating a learning culture at work. This “TRANSITION” can reflect on trainee’s attitude change, from “DON’T WANT TO ATTEND” and “TOLD TO GO, HAVE TO GO” to “NICE TO LEARN, SHARE, DISCUSS”, “MADE TIME FOR IT” and “HAPPY TO APPLY TO THE JOB. The reason why this change

happens can be understood from both corporate level and individual perspective. Within the selected organisation, “IMPORTANT, EVERYONE TO BE TRAINED” has become the brand’s “LONG-TERM VISION”, thus, the supportive atmosphere at work makes this transition happen, as “MOTIVATION, CHANGE ATTITUDES”. In the meantime, individuals start to “UNDERSTAND THE IMPACT” of learning at work, such as, “TREAT COURSES AS INVESTMENT” and “YOUR GROWTH MATTERS BRAND’S GROWTH”; they “NEED ENCOURAGEMENT FROM MANAGEMENT” and they have been motivated with “YOU DID WELL”. All these codes demonstrate the importance of a supportive work environment and revealed the transition moment that the selected company is experiencing in building a learning-friendly atmosphere at work. Therefore, the code “CREATING A LEARNING ENVIRONMENT” is picked as a category to represent others in this group. The various links among all the codes in the category are presented in Figure 4-4 and are explained with details and figures in Appendix H.

Figure 4-4. Interview Data - Axial Coding: Learning Environment Overview

Category 5: “EVALUATION: HOW SUCCESSFUL THE PROGRAM IS”

In the fifth category, it includes fourteen codes (see Group 5: The Influence of Training Evaluation on Training Transfer) that were highlighted in the first coding cycle. Among all these codes, some identify the methods of training evaluation, for example, “EVALUATE WITH FIGURES, KNOWLEDGE CHECKS, OBSERVATIONS”; while others reflect some previous results, such as, “YOU DO FORGET THINGS”, “VIVIDLY, REMEMBER

DETAILS” and “A LOT OF TIME, TEAM REMEMBER”. On the other hand, training effectiveness is explained from a different dimension. For example, both the code “IMMEDIATE TRANSFER, TELLING STORIES AND SALES” and “LONG-TERM, ATTITUDE CHANGED” link the success of a program with different levels of transfer results. Meanwhile, there are also codes to reveal some poor training practice in the selected organisation, for instance, “NOT THE CASE FOR US”, “IRRELEVANT”, “CANNOT BE APPLIED” and “ONLY 30%, LEARNT, USEFUL”. It is clear to see the conflict between the high expectation and the frustrated reality by comparing the code “GAIN CONFIDENCE”, “EFFECTIVE” and the code “A LITTLE KNOWLEDGE, BENEFIT CAREER”. Obviously, the similarity all the codes of this category shares is the evaluation of training effectiveness. This evaluation is not about examining the quality of a training design but following up on how the learnt knowledge is applied to the jobs after a session. Therefore, the code “EVALUATION: HOW SUCCESSFUL THE PROGRAM IS” is most appropriate to be transformed as a category during the second cycle of coding. The connections among all the codes in this category are presented in Figure 4-5. The detailed explanation regarding the relationships among the subcategories is attached in Appendix I.

Figure 4-5. Interview Data - Axial Coding: Evaluating Program Success Overview

Category 6: “ESTABLISH FROM BEGINNING, EVALUATE AT THE END”

There are seven initial codes in this category (see Group 6: Views on Making Plans for Training Evaluation). Among them, different opinions about where to place the evaluation plan are mainly discussed, for instance, “ESTABLISH FROM BEGINNING, EVALUATE AT THE END”, “MERGE WITH TRAINING STAGE”, “AFTER SESSION” and “UNTIL YOU PRACTICE, NOT ABLE TO EVALUATE”. As the evaluation plan that is discussed here is only about a decision-making step, the code “ESTABLISH FROM BEGINNING, EVALUATE AT THE END” captures the essence of this mental process. Thus, it is transformed as a category at this coding stage. In the meantime, some codes are also chosen and included here, for instance, “EVERY POINT, AN EVALUATION”, “A CHECKING” and “KEEP YOU ON TRACK”. Because in this group other codes also suggest the possible step within a training cycle that an evaluation plan could be placed. No matter it is called an evaluation plan or an evaluation point, they are both suggested by the interviewees as a result of their own work experience. By including all aspects, the relationships among codes in this category are illustrated in Figure 4-6. The detailed explanation regarding the links among some subcategories is attached in Appendix J.

Figure 4-6. Interview Data - Axial Coding: Evaluation Plan Overview

Category 7 – “TRAINING ANALYSIS, A ROUND CIRCLE”

In this category, it includes six codes that were generated in the first coding cycle (see Group 7: Current Guidelines on Trainer’s Performance). Most of the initial codes in this group present “THE NORMAL PROCEDURE” that the trainer interviewees usually apply in their daily work, for example, “CULTURE OF TRAINING, MENTALITY, COME BEFORE”, “NEEDS

ASSESSMENT, CONSIDER WHAT TO DO, THEN LAUNCH”, “DESIGN, LAUNCH, EVALUATE THE PROGRAM ITSELF” and “EVALUATE THE SUCCESS OF PROGRAM”. Although there is not a suggested training procedure at the selected brand to guide its trainer’s work performance, these codes are all inspired by individual trainer participant’s valuable work experience. Among them, the code “TRAINING ANALYSIS, A ROUND CIRCLE” is applied as the category code, because it is agreed by all the trainer interviewees that training is an on-going process. The following diagram (see Figure 4-7) presents the relationships among the codes in this category.

Figure 4-7. Interview Data - Axial Coding: An Ongoing Training Process

Category 8 - “IMPORTANT TOOL, LUXURY INDUSTRY”

There are five initial codes in this category, which are presented in Group 8: Importance of Training in Luxury Business. Among them, personal opinions about the importance of training in luxury companies are identified, for instance, “GIVE YOU LUXURIOUS MINDSET”, “NEED MORE IN LUXURY” and “IMPORTANT TOOL, LUXURY INDUSTRY”. From another dimension, some codes clarify it from a business aspect, such as, “LUXURY, ABOUT FASHION” and “LUXURY, ABOUT SERVICE”. Overall, the code “IMPORTANT TOOL, LUXURY INDUSTRY” summarises the main idea. Therefore, it is transformed as a category during the second cycle of coding. The following diagram (Figure 4-8) presents the connections among the codes in this group.

Figure 4-8 . Interview Data - Axial Coding: Importance of Training in Luxury Sector

Category 9 - “YOU ARE ON THE RIGHT TRACK”

The six codes in this group represent the interviewee’s opinions on this study’s theoretical framework. They are listed in Group 9: Comments on this Study’s Theoretical Framework. Among them, the code “YOU ARE ON THE RIGHT TRACK” is chosen to represent the others and become the category in the second coding cycle. The links among all the codes in this category are presented in Figure 4-9.

Figure 4-9. Interview Data - Axial Coding: Attitudes Towards Theoretical Framework

4.2.2.3 Selective Coding

After identifying the categories within the initial codes by applying Axial coding method, Selective coding approach is chosen to demonstrate the correlations among the categories in order to formulate a theory in this study. The reason for using Selective coding method after processing the initial codes with Axial coding approach in the second coding cycle, is because Strauss and Corbin' s three-phased coding method (1990) has been selected to guide the data analysis in this research.

After applying Axial coding method to reorganise the codes generated in the first coding cycle, there are nine categories identified. They are listed as follows,

“ASSESS THE TRAINING NEEDS”

“MATERIALS, TIME, ACTIVITIES”

“BRING THIS TO LIFE”

“CREATING A LEARNING ENVIRONMENT”

“EVALUATION: HOW SUCCESSFUL THE PROGRAM IS”

“ESTABLISH FROM BEGINNING, EVALUATE AT THE END”

“TRAINING ANALYSIS, A ROUND CIRCLE”

“IMPORTANT TOOL, LUXURY INDUSTRY”

“YOU ARE ON THE RIGHT TRACK”

Among these categories, “TRAINING ANALYSIS, A ROUND CIRCLE” is considered as the core category. This is because it demonstrates the core concept of the training structure that was inspired by the trainer interviewee' s work experience. This chosen central code identifies that training is an ongoing process, in the meantime, the codes that form the category “TRAINING ANALYSIS, A ROUND CIRCLE” also indicate the suggested sequence of the steps in the training process, which provides the useful evidence to integrate other categories into a theory regarding the process of training.

Figure 4-10. As Figure 4-7

Based on the sequence of training steps that is shown in Figure 4-10, “CREATING A LEARNING ENVIRONMENT” comes first in the structure of training, as “CULTURE OF TRAINING, MENTALITY, COME BEFORE”; then follows by “ASSESS THE TRAINING NEEDS”, “MATERIALS, TIME, ACTIVITIES” and “BRING THIS TO LIFE”, as the code “NEEDS ASSESSMENT, CONSIDER WHAT TO DO, THEN LAUNCH” clearly indicates the sequences among these three steps in the process of training. This also is confirmed by the code “DESIGN, LAUNCH, EVALUATE THE PROGRAM ITSELF”. It is important to clarify that ‘evaluate the program itself’ is different from ‘evaluate the success of program’, as the former represents the evaluation for assessing the training design while the latter indicates the evaluation for examining the effectiveness of a session. At last, the category “EVALUATION: HOW SUCCESSFUL THE PROGRAM IS” comes at the end, as the evidence shows “EVALUATE THE SUCCESS OF PROGRAM” comes after “DESIGN, LAUNCH, EVALUATE THE PROGRAM ITSELF” in the diagram presented above. Therefore, the connections among the categories are presented in the following diagram (Figure 4-11).

Figure 4-11. Interview Data - Selective Coding: Training Cycle 1

However, the researcher considers that the feasibility of this framework is low in reality, as it is impossible to temporarily build a learning-friendly company culture every single time when a new potential training need is recognised as a result of training evaluation. Then, she fully understood what the code "CULTURE OF TRAINING, MENTALITY, COME BEFORE" indicates. That is, a learning environment at work takes time to create, therefore, it should come first. In the meantime, the evaluation plan, which is suggested by the code "ESTABLISH FROM BEGINNING, EVALUATE AT THE END" is also included in the improved framework. The researcher decided to place it between "MATERIALS, TIME, ACTIVITIES" and "BRING THIS TO LIFE". This is because, an evaluation plan is a mental process for figuring out how to measure according to what to achieve before conducting a session. The diagram (Figure 4-12) which includes the changes that were made is listed as follows,

Figure 4-12. Interview Data - Selective Coding: Training Cycle 2

In order to make readers understand better, the researcher applied the core words to rename all the steps in the training process, for example, using training needs assessment to replace “ASSESS THE TRAINING NEEDS”; training design for “MATERIALS, TIME, ACTIVITIES”; evaluation plan for “ESTABLISH FROM BEGINNING, EVALUATE AT THE END”; training delivery for “BRING THIS TO LIFE”; training evaluation: training effectiveness for “EVALUATION: HOW SUCCESSFUL THE PROGRAM IS”; ongoing process for “TRAINING ANALYSIS, A ROUND CIRCLE”, and learning environment for “CREATING A LEARNING ENVIRONMENT”. The final version of the framework that is developed as a result of applying Selective coding method in the second coding cycle is presented in the following diagram (Figure 4-13).

Apart from the categories that are included in the theory regarding the process of training, there are still two categories left. They are, “IMPORTANT TOOL, LUXURY INDUSTRY” and “YOU ARE ON THE RIGHT TRACK”. Although they are irrelevant to the training structure, these two will be discussed in the following chapter with other findings together.

Figure 4-13. Interview Data - Selective Coding: Finalised Training Cycle

4.2.3 Observation Data

Apart from the qualitative data gathered through in-depth interviews, participant observation data collection method has also been employed in this study. The researcher aimed to have a better understanding of the on-the-job training activities that are designed for luxury frontline staff within real settings, through observing two training sessions as a participant at the selected luxury company. The grounded theory method has also been chosen to analyse the data collected through observations, in order to develop a model to help to make more sense of the phenomenon that is under study. As with the analytical procedure that was adopted to analyse interview data, In Vivo coding, Axial coding and Selective coding have been applied to code, condense and categorise the observational data. At last, the theory that is grounded in the data is developed.

After each session, the researcher narratively described everything she observed through the whole process with the help of the field notes that were taken in the course of the research. Apart from writing down the narrative accounts of both two courses, the descriptions of

particular events in the course of the observations were also recorded with details. Regarding the analysis of the data gathered through observations, the researcher still conducted the process manually, as what she claimed earlier in this chapter, she believes this is the best way to reveal the messages embedded in the contexts with human participation.

4.2.3.1 In Vivo Coding

As grounded theory method is still chosen to guide the analysis of the observational data, Strauss and Corbin's three-phased coding method (1990), which includes Open coding, Axial coding and Selective coding, is also being followed. About the choice of the open coding method, the researcher still prefers applying In Vivo coding to code the data in the initial coding process. As the participant observations were conducted by the researcher and she is also the one recorded everything observed with her own words, In Vivo coding method is selected to emphasise the stories from her perspective directly, instead of reinterpreting the descriptions. In total, there are one hundred and eighty-two codes developed as a result of the appliance of In Vivo coding in the first coding cycle. Among them, some similarities and differences have both been recognised.

Group 1: Differences in Arranging Training Schedules between Sessions

Firstly, the information about training time schedule is found from the descriptions of both training sessions that the researcher observed as a participant. However, the attitudes and the activities that were taken varied between sessions. After condensed the data, there are five codes are kept for the second coding cycle. They are listed as follows,

“AGREEMENT ON SCHEDULE”

“AN EMAIL WITH DETAILS”

“CONFIRM DATE WITH ME”

“DIDN'T KNOW THIS SESSION”

“ONLY GOT TOLD ON THAT MORNING”

Group 2: Differences in Pre-Training Engagement between Sessions

Secondly, the full details of the effort trainer made to establish a bond with trainees before these two sessions were described. The researcher recorded it from both the physical and psychological aspects, for example, the physical setting and greetings. There are seven codes are kept after the process of condensing the data. They are presented as follows,

“WELCOMED US”

“ROOM, WELL PREPARED”

“TRAINER, INTRODUCE HERSELF”

“MOTIVATED US TO INTRODUCE OURSELVES”

“ROOM, PREPARED SIMPLY”

“WAITING FOR OTHER PARTICIPANTS”

“DIDN'T ASK, INTRODUCING OURSELVES”

Group 3: Differences in Training Techniques between Sessions

Thirdly, the researcher drew a comparison of the training methods that were adopted between these two sessions. The similar choices on the methods that were made between these two training programs are noticed. However, the different outcomes as a result of employing similar training approaches under two different situations brought up the researcher's attention. After reorganising the data, there are six codes kept and listed as follows,

“METHODS”

“COMBINATION, TEACHING AND HANDS-ON”

“OUTDOOR ACTIVITIES”

“PLANNING TO DO ACTIVITIES”

“TRIED TO DO QUIZ”

“HAD TO CHANGE TO TEACHING”

Group 4: Differences in Trainer's Performance between Sessions

Furthermore, the researcher gave a lot of attention to the trainer's performance when she was attending these two training sessions as a participant. Therefore, there are a few codes that indicate whether these trainers were doing a good job, for example, the tone, building confidence, participants' involvement and their abilities to adapt to various situations. There are eleven codes are kept after the process of condensing the data. They are illustrated as follows,

“COMFORT TRAINEES”

“EFFECTIVELY ENCOURAGED US”

“TONE, WELL SET, FIRST TRAINER”

“TRAINER’S PERFORMANCE”

“CONSISTENTLY KEPT, SECOND TRAINER”

“ENGAGE WITH AUDIENCE”

“FAILED, LAST TRAINER”

“READ EVERYTHING WORD BY WORD”

“FAILED TO ENGAGE”

“TRAINER, TRIED, FAILED”

“TRAINER, NOT FLEXIBLE”

Group 5: Differences in Trainee’s Reactions between Sessions

Then, trainee’s reactions towards the approaches that were adopted by the trainers were recorded. As a result, a lot of codes regarding their feelings and behaviours were generated in the process of first coding cycle. These codes can provide evidence to examine the success of the training design. There are eight codes are kept after the process of condensing the data. They are listed as follows,

“CONCENTRATING”

“WILLING TO CONTRIBUTE”

“ENJOYED”

“READ OUR REACTIONS”

“NOT HAPPY”

“FEEL AWKWARDNESS”

“EXHAUSTED”

“DIDN’T WANT INVOLVED”

Group 6: Differences in Trainee’s Willingness to Work together between Sessions

Furthermore, not only the interactions between trainers and trainees were observed and recorded, but also the cooperation among trainees were also discussed in the description notes in detail. The researcher collected all the codes that are related to the interactions among the trainees. By comparing them, it is noticeable that the different level of involvement of the trainees in these two sessions can also reflect on the success of these two session’s training designs. After condensed the data, there are five codes are kept for the second coding cycle. They are presented as follows,

“COMPETITION”

“GET INVOLVED”

“PRESENT ALTOGETHER”

“INTERACTIONS AMONG MEMBERS”

“INDIVIDUALLY”

Group 7: Differences in Post-Training Evaluation between Sessions

In the meantime, the codes that are related to the after-session evaluation caught the researcher’s attention, as they represent two opposite situations that happened in these two training programs that the researcher observed. There are three codes are kept after the process of condensing the data. They are listed as follows,

“ASK OUR OPINIONS”

“TRAINERS APPROACHED FOR FEEDBACK”

“NO FOLLOW UP”

Group 8: Differences in Appreciating Trainee’s Involvement between Sessions

At last, the researcher also noticed the opposite actions that were taken, regarding the appreciation for trainee’s effort and attendance. This is important as it reflects on the ability of treating trainees with respect. After condensed the data, there are three codes are kept for the second coding cycle. They are listed as follows,

“APPRECIATION FOR ATTENDANCE”

“THE EFFORT OF TRAINEE”

“DIDN’T APPRECIATE MY TIME, EFFORT”

4.2.3.2 Axial Coding

Through the first coding cycle, the codes revealed some repeated patterns exist in the descriptive observations of the two training sessions that the researcher observed as a participant with her own words and expressions. After the initial codes were reorganised and filtered, eight categories were formed with sets of initial codes that were kept after data condensation. In the second coding cycle, Axial coding method was used to explore the categories and the connections within each of them, as it is the second of Strauss and Corbin’s three-phased coding method (Strauss and Corbin, 1990).

Category 1: "AGREEMENT ON SCHEDULE"

The first category consists of five initial codes (see Group 1: Differences in Arranging Training Schedules between Sessions). Among these codes, there are some codes about reaching an agreement on the date that works for both trainer and trainees, for example, "CONFIRM DATE WITH ME" and "AGREEMENT ON SCHEDULE". In the meantime, some codes reveal the opposite situations, in which the different actions were taken regarding informing trainees about the training schedule, such as, "AN EMAIL WITH DETAILS", "DIDN'T KNOW THIS SESSION" and "ONLY GOT TOLD ON THAT MORNING". Since every code in this group is related to the arrangement made on training time schedule, the code "AGREEMENT ON SCHEDULE" can summarise the main idea of all the others. Therefore, it is transformed as a category during the second coding cycle.

Noticeably, the differences between these two observed sessions regarding the arrangements over the training time schedule were recorded. By comparison, the organisers of the one-day session actively negotiated for an available date for both the participants and trainers themselves. However, trainees who attended the observed three-hour program only passively got a short notice before it happened. Therefore, the researcher considered including the codes that represent both these two opposite situations within the boundary of this category. The relationships among these five codes are identified in Figure 4-14.

Figure 4-14. Observation Data - Axial Coding: Training Schedule

Category 2: "WELCOMED US"

There are seven codes in the second category (see Group 2: Differences in Pre-Training Engagement between Sessions). Among them, some codes describe the physical settings of these two observed training sessions, for instance, "ROOM, WELL PREPARED" and "ROOM, PREPARED SIMPLY". Meanwhile, some codes identify different actions that these two groups of trainers took to establish an early rapport with trainees before the sessions were taken place, for example, "WELCOMED US", "TRAINER, INTRODUCE HERSELF" and "WAITING FOR OTHER PARTICIPANTS". Some codes present trainer's effort on breaking the ice despite the psychological barriers that prevent the participants from communicating with others at the very beginning, such as, "MOTIVATED US TO INTRODUCE OURSELVES" and "DIDN'T ASK, INTRODUCING OURSELVES". Clearly, all the codes in this category reveal the reality of how the trainers comforted the trainees before the sessions started. Therefore, the code "WELCOMED US" is recognised as a category in the process of the second cycle of coding.

Under this category, the researcher decided to include the codes that represent the similar situations but can be compared to demonstrate the different initiatives taken by trainers in the pre-training stage. The relationships among the codes in this group is presented in Figure 4-15.

Figure 4-15. Observation Data - Axial Coding: Start of Training Session

Category 3: "METHODS"

The third category consists of six initial codes, which are presented in Group 3: Differences in Training Techniques between Sessions. Among these codes, some of them indicate different types of training methods that were applied during two sessions, for example, "COMBINATION, TEACHING AND HANDS-ON" and "OUTDOOR ACTIVITIES". By comparison, some codes reveal the conflict between the choice of training methods during training design stage and the flexibility in applying them to deliver a session, such as, "PLANNING TO DO ACTIVITIES", "TRIED TO DO QUIZ" and "HAD TO CHANGE TO TEACHING". Since all the codes in this group are related to the decisions made on training methods, the code "METHODS" can summarise the main idea of all the others. Therefore, it is transformed as a category during the second coding cycle.

All the codes that are included in this category represent different situations with the similar choices on the methods. The relationships among the codes in this group is presented in Figure 4-16.

Figure 4-16. Observation Data - Axial Coding: Training Methods

Category 4: "TRAINER'S PERFORMANCE"

There are eleven codes in this group, which are included in Group 4: Differences in Trainer's Performance between Sessions. Some of them reveal how the three trainers performed their roles in the one-day session, for example, "TONE, WELL SET, FIRST TRAINER", "COMFORT TRAINEES", "EFFECTIVELY ENCOURAGED US", "CONSISTENTLY KEPT, SECOND TRAINER", "ENGAGE WITH AUDIENCE", "FAILED, LAST TRAINER", "READ EVERYTHING WORD BY WORD" and "FAILED TO ENGAGE". By comparison, there are also codes describe the performance of the trainers who delivered the three-hour training program that the researcher also observed as a participant, such as, "TRAINER, TRIED, FAILED" and "TRAINER, NOT FLEXIBLE". It is noticeable that all the codes included in this category are employed to discuss trainer's performance. Therefore, the code "TRAINER'S PERFORMANCE" can summarise the main idea of all the others. Then, it is transformed as a category in the second coding cycle.

In Figure 4-17, these eleven codes are divided into four subgroups to describe the specific performance of each trainer from both two observed training sessions separately.

Figure 4-17. Observation Data - Axial Coding: Trainer's Individual Performance

By linking all these four subcategories to the main category, the comparisons are made not only between these two sessions, but also within the first one-day training program. All the relationships among all the codes in this category are presented in Figure 4-18 that is presented as follows,

Figure 4-18. Observation Data - Axial Coding: Aggregate Trainer Performance

Category 5: “READ OUR REACTIONS”

In this group, there are eight codes, which are included in Group 5: Differences in Trainee’s Reactions between Sessions. Among them, some codes reveal trainee’s feelings that is a direct result of trainer’s performance during the two training programs that the researcher attended and observed, for example, “ENJOYED”, “NOT HAPPY”, “FEEL AWKWARDNESS” and “EXHAUSTED”. In the meantime, some codes reflect trainee’s behaviours in the process of training, for instance, “CONCENTRATING”, “WILLING TO CONTRIBUTE” and “DIDN’T WANT INVOLVED”. It is clear, all the codes in this category indicate trainee’s reactions during these two training courses. Therefore, the code “READ OUR REACTIONS” can

summarise the main idea of all the codes, and it is transformed as a category in the process of the second coding cycle.

Within this category, all the codes are included to compare trainee’s reactions between these two training programs. The relationships among them are presented in Figure 4-19 that is listed as follows,

Figure 4-19. Observation Data - Axial Coding: Trainee's Reactions

Category 6: “INTERACTIONS AMONG MEMBERS”

There are five codes included in this group (see Group 6: Differences in Trainee’s Willingness to Work together between Sessions). Most of them identify the researcher’s experience of engaging with other group members during the group activities in the one-day training session that she observed as a participant, for example, “COMPETITION”, “GET INVOLVED” and “PRESENT ALTOGETHER”. By contrast, the code “INDIVIDUALLY”, represents what she observed from the other three-hour training program is also included. Since all these codes indicate trainee’s interactions during both two observed training courses, the code “INTERACTIONS AMONG MEMBERS” is transformed as a category in second coding cycle, and the connections within this category are presented in Figure 4-20.

Figure 4-20. Observation Data - Axial Coding: Interactions among Trainees

Category 7: "TRAINERS APPROACHED FOR FEEDBACK"

This group includes three codes, which are included in Group 7: Differences in Post-Training Evaluation between Sessions. Two of them demonstrate the opposite situations that arose as part of the two training sessions that the researcher attended and observed. They are both related to the evaluation of these two programs themselves, for example, "ASK OUR OPINIONS" and "NO FOLLOW UP". Therefore, the code "TRAINERS APPROACHED FOR FEEDBACK" is chosen as the category to summarise all the other codes in the group. The relationships within this category are presented in Figure 4-21.

Figure 4-21. Observation Data - Axial Coding: Post Session Follow-up

Category 8: "THE EFFORT OF TRAINEE"

There are three codes in this category (see Group 8: Differences in Appreciating Trainee's Involvement between Sessions). Two of them reveal the different trainer's attitudes towards the time and effort that trainees made to attend training sessions, for example, "APPRECIATION FOR ATTENDANCE" and "DIDN'T APPRECIATE MY TIME, EFFORT". It is obvious that the code "THE EFFORT OF TRAINEE" can be applied to represent the other two in this group as a category in the process of the second coding cycle. The relationships among the codes in this category are demonstrated in Figure 4-22.

Figure 4-22. Observation Data - Axial Coding: Attitudes Towards Trainee Attendance

In the end, there are eight categories generated as a result of applying Axial coding method in the second coding cycle. The correlations within each category are explained and demonstrated.

4.2.3.3 Selective Coding

After recognising categories and the relationships among the subcategories within each group by applying Axial coding method, Selective coding approach is chosen to demonstrate the links among the categories in order to reveal the theory that is embedded in the observational data. The reason for using Selective coding method is because Strauss and Corbin's three-phased coding method (1990) has been selected to guide the analytical process of the qualitative data analysis in this research.

The eight categories, which are generated as a result of applying Axial coding method in the second coding cycle, are listed as follows,

“AGREEMENT ON SCHEDULE”

“WELCOMED US”

“METHODS”

“TRAINER’S PERFORMANCE”

“READ OUR REACTIONS”

“INTERACTIONS AMONG MEMBERS”

“TRAINERS APPROACHED FOR FEEDBACK”

“THE EFFORT OF TRAINEE”

Among all these eight categories that are presented above, “TRAINERS APPROACHED FOR FEEDBACK” is recognised as the core category. The reason for making this decision is because all the information that is related to the remaining categories could provide trainers with some valuable ideas of how a training session went, in order to improve the arrangement for the session that would satisfy both trainers and trainees. Therefore, the links among the categories are presented in the following diagram (Figure 4-23).

Figure 4-23. Observation Data - Selective Coding: Evaluating Training Design

4.2.4 Questionnaire Data

In this study, questionnaires have also been applied to collect some quantitative data. However, it only represents around twenty-five percent of the data in this study. They were collected through the questionnaires with rating-scale questions. Therefore, the data cannot be measured numerically, instead they are ranked data. At last, there were one hundred responses received and analysed. The results are listed in Figure 4-24.

Figure 4-24. Responses to Questionnaires

These twelve questions (see Figure 4-24) were designed to reflect on the different stages in a training circle that were emphasised in this study's theoretical framework (see Figure 3-1). The first question was prepared to investigate how well the learning objectives met with the trainee's practical needs to reflect on the current situation regarding assessing the training needs in practice at the chosen brand. Regarding the design of a training session, questions three, five and eight were set to discover it from different angles, for example, the structure of a course, the presentation slides and the activities adopted in a session. Furthermore, four questions were structured to examine the success of the training delivery at the selected brand. They are questions two, four, six and seven. They also provided this study with rich information

on how successfully the sessions were delivered from various perspectives, such as clearly defined learning principles, physical settings of the session, the interactions between trainers and trainees and trainers' performance. In the meantime, both the tenth and eleventh questions aimed to understand the situation of training transfer after-sessions at the chosen brand. Question ten was designed to examine it from the participant's perspective, i.e., their willingness to transfer what they have learnt to their jobs. While question eleven was set to explore the opportunities that the brand offered regarding training transfer. At last, both questions nine and twelve were prepared to discover the current situation of the chosen brand's learning environment. Apart from the information regarding whether a supportive learning work culture has been created there, the participants' opinions on the benefits of learning at work were also gathered through the questionnaires.

As a result of the analysis, these one-hundred participants positively responded to most of the questions that were included in the questionnaire. For example, seventy-nine percent of them considered the most recent training sessions that they attended were quite helpful to improve their work performance. This statistic result clearly indicates to this study that the successful training needs assessments have been conducted by the chosen luxury brand. Regarding the brand's training design, no matter the structure of a session, the presentation slides or the activities, the majority of the participants recognised their latest training experience was enjoyable. On average, around seventy-three percent of the respondents positively reacted to the questions regarding training delivery (learning objectives 78%, physical settings 77%, interactions 64% and trainer's performance 72%) also suggests their confidence in their recent training experience with the selected brand. In relation to the after-session training transfer, seventy-six percent of the participants intended to apply the newly learnt knowledge to their daily work after they returned from their most recent training sessions, while sixty six out of these hundred people recognised the opportunities the selected brand provided to them to facilitate the transfer. Meanwhile, ninety-five percent of the participants considered the opportunities to learn at work as their benefits. All these positive responses contribute to their satisfied training experience with the selected brand, while one of the results, which is related to the brand's learning environment in the workplace, is negative. All the analytical processes eventually lead to these findings that are included in Appendix K.

4.3 Discussions on Findings

After both the qualitative and quantitative data collected in this study have been analysed, the primary analytical process was explained and presented in the previous sections. In this part, all the findings will be discussed altogether to discover the answers to the research questions of this study. The structure of this section will follow the sequence of the stages that are included in a training circle. Therefore, it starts from creating a learning environment, follows by assessing the training needs, designing a session, planning on measuring the success of this course, delivering the program, and evaluating its effectiveness. Within each step, the information that was discovered while analysing the data collected by using these three chosen data gathering methods will be compared to reveal their differences and similarities.

4.3.1 Creating a Learning Environment

When it comes to the discussions on the learning environment at the chosen luxury brand, the participants in this study expressed themselves from different dimensions. Those individuals who work as trainers and managers viewed it mainly from a corporate perspective, while those who work as frontline sales associates examined it from an individual's view. It is exciting to see people's various responses to the same phenomenon. Some of them are similar, while some are opposed. In particular, some points that were repeatedly emphasised by most of the participants brought up the researcher's attention.

The first pattern came to the researcher's notice is the idea of creating a learning work environment has been promoted by the selected brand recently. One of the interviewees mentioned '*training is a massive callout for the business*' since the new CEO joined the company in 2017. It is worth mentioning that this participant has been working with the chosen brand for thirteen years as a manager and recently started her role as a retail trainer there. Apparently, this new key business goal has been recognised as a significant change by her. In the meantime, she also considered it to be the '*good news*' for the brand's trainers, as their job could '*go further and deeper*'. The expressions she used to voice an opinion on this matter match up with some scholar's viewpoints on defining a learning organisation which have been reviewed in this study (refers to 2.1.2.4c). Such as, it is believed that the mission of building a learning atmosphere in the workplace needs to be embedded in a company's 'corporate vision and business objectives' (Buckley and Caple, 2009, p.11). This is exactly what the chosen brand did. Meanwhile, the significance of encouraging its employees at all levels to

continuously improve themselves is considered as ‘a fundamental mind shift’ (Jones and Hendry, 1994). This explains what this interviewee meant ‘*go further and deeper*’. Similarly, some of the brand’s other trainers, who also participated in this study’s interviews, expressed their views on why this change could bring a dramatic influence on the brand’s business. They stated, ‘*training is one of the most important tools for luxury industry*’. This is because it does not only ‘*provides you all kinds of the information about the whole luxury environment*’, but also ‘*give you the luxurious mindset to adapt yourself to the job in the luxury industry*’. Apparently, they could not agree more on this new long-term business direction that the senior management team of the chosen brand recently made. At the same time, more information was given to detail what initiatives have been suggested to make this change happen, for example, a newly formed partnership between the brand’s retail trainers and its line managers. This new way of working is well accepted by all the trainers who took part in this study’s interviews. Some of them appreciated that ‘*when I joined the company, the training was your job particularly. But now, it is the joint efforts. We will support each other.*’ Another trainer participant also approved this cooperation between trainers and managers. She described the reality of her daily work as ‘*one person is looking after seven stores*’; therefore, ‘*management needs to do their training too*’. It is not an excuse for shirking her responsibilities at work, instead, she strongly believes the important role that managers play in encouraging learning locally, as she critically argued, ‘*they are there every day, it is their team*’. From these two trainer participants’ opinions, it is clear to see that creating an organisational culture that supports learning at work cannot be done only by trainers. The importance of having a supportive learning environment in the workplace needs to be recognised not only by the senior management level but also by the store level. The partnership between trainers and managers in enhancing the learning atmosphere in the workplace is also emphasised in the findings of empirical studies mentioned in the literature review section of this study. The involvement of line managers has been suggested not only in the process of training design and training delivery to ensure not only the quality of training but also ‘committed attendance from subordinates’ (Sloman, 2017, p.135). Meanwhile, the influence of ‘supervisory or peer’ is emphasised (Baldwin and Ford, 1988) when it comes to the stage of training transfer. Apart from discussing the changes from the strategic business perspective, there are also differences that some participants who are the selected luxury company’s frontline employees observed in their daily work. Therefore, the word ‘*transition*’ has been applied by them to compare the past situation to the current one that they experienced at work, such as, the change from ‘*receive the new collections in stores and then have a relevant training after*’ to ‘*having a training*

regarding new collections ahead of receiving the actual products in store, or *providing us with an overview of the next quarter*. As discovered in empirical literature earlier (see Internal Branding & Internal Communication), an effective communication within an organisation makes a big difference. In this case, employees feel motivated as they have a clear understanding of the important information regarding the business strategy through an in-time internal communication actively, instead of being told passively afterwards. In the meantime, this transition can also be explained as a result of having a learning environment in the workplace, as one of the features of a learning organisation has been considered as creating transparency *'across all levels of a company'* (Hayes *et al.*, 1988). Therefore, no matter how this change would be justified, for sure it has brought a significant influence on the chosen brand's employee's work experience.

Secondly, the evidence collected from the in-depth interviews suggests that the chosen organisation provides learning opportunities for all employees. The material of these courses is believed to be *'reachable'* and covers *'a broad range of themes or subjects'*. However, there is a noticeable conflict between the attitudes of the brand's managers and frontline employees towards this matter. According to most of the interviewees who work with the chosen brand as its managers, the brand *'encourages you a lot in developing yourself'* through providing its employees with *'the possibility of any training' 'from HR perspectives to product knowledge to management skills'*. Therefore, they believe that *'the support is always there'*. By contrast, some interviewees who work as the brand's frontline employees recalled some unpleasant experiences that reflected on their opinions on this matter. Some of them complained that she did not have the opportunity to attend trainings for the area she is interested, as *'the chance is very limited'*. Likewise, the other one felt frustrated as *'I don't get to choose'*. At the same time, the issue of a lack of communication between the brand and its frontline staff about the launch of its online learning tool was addressed by one of the interviewees who works as a manager there. The gap between *'I don't think a lot of people aware of it'* and *'they spent quite a lot of money on developing this online platform'* confused her. By contrast, another manager who also participated in the interviews of this study considered the motivation to learn at work to be the employee's decision to make, as he said, *'it is your responsibility to find it and read and absorb it. We are adults and we have been given the space to research yourself what is right for you'*. Whether the intention of learning is *'all up to you'* or could be affected by the brand's encouragement, the researcher also compared other participant's reactions not only collected during the interviews but also gathered from the answers of the questionnaires.

During the in-depth interviews, it was clear to notice the resistance of some of the interviewees' to the idea of learning at work, the excuses for avoiding any learning chance in the workplace they made were either *'I am lazy'* or *'I am not at school anymore'*, while others demonstrated their understandings of the benefits that training brings, for example, *'get to know new things'*, *'enhances my understanding about my responsibility at work'* or *'the opportunity to expose your ideas'*. Similarly, the result of question twelve in the questionnaire (see Figure 4-24) also positively indicates the fact that the benefits of learning at work have been widely accepted by most of the target employees of the chosen brand in this research. At the same time, the responses to question nine (see Figure 4-24) show a significant portion of the target population have a negative attitude towards the current learning environment at the selected brand. By comparison, most of the participants in this research have demonstrated their clear understandings on the impact of training at work on their self-development. Despite the benefits of learning at work, an interviewee who works as a manager at the selected brand surprised to learn that *'a lot of people they don't want to attend any training courses'*. The researcher considers the reason for causing this conflict is due to the gap that existed between *'encourage'* and *'all up to you'*. The learning opportunities at work can be viewed as an initiative that the selected organisation took to encourage learning across the company. However, this idea was not promoted among the employees to arise their awareness on how to get involved. This acts against those key characteristics of a learning organisation that were mentioned in the previous paragraph, which include *'transparency'* (Hayes *et al.*, 1988) and *'facilitates the learning of its members'* (Pedler *et al.*, 1996). If the chosen brand has become a learning organisation with a supportive learning environment, the ultimate situation would result in a clear message regarding its online learning resources sent across the company from its top management to its junior staff. Then its employees' attitudes towards learning opportunities at work would shift enormously. By borrowing the words from the interviewees, people might think *'what I could get from it'* as a starting point to *'view the training from one way or various ways'* and end up with *'change people's attitude towards the training session'* and *'be willing to get involved'*. When the mindset is ready, it is the employee's decision to make on subjects to learn in the workplace, the choice can vary from person to person, for example *'understand the impact'* or *'treat course as investment'* or *'your growth matters the brand's growth'*.

About the training opportunities at the selected luxury brand, a hidden message from the interview data also reveals that a manager who works above a certain level in the company has

more learning options when comparing with a frontline sales associate. In reality, the chosen brand gives its staff *'the opportunities to pick the courses based on your level'*. To managers, *'there is a huge amount of opportunities for you to learn at work'*, while considering the learning options that are entitled to sales associates, *'if you want to develop yourself in a certain area you might have to reach a certain level'*. The conflict between offering the chance and meeting the requirement to seize it has had a negative influence on some of the brand's frontline sales associates, as one interviewee commented on this situation angrily *'I don't think they value us as what they supposed to'*. This person's reflection on the brand's current learning culture made the researcher wonder who would gain benefit from creating a learning work environment, the company, or its employees. For this purpose, the opinions regarding this concern were also collected from other interviewees. However, they could not reach a consensus on this matter. Some of them viewed it from the business point of view, they think the brand would benefit greatly from its employees' personal development within the workplace. They stated, *'your growth matters the brand's growth'* or *'the brand invests in you, you invest in the brand'*. On the contrary, some of them shared the view that the employee would gain more benefits from learning at work, such as, *'With the different exposure on various area across the brand, then you can think about your personal and career growth'* and *'you would be set for success'* or *'people, who would enjoy their job, have an expectation, when you come to work, you would be trained'*. The researcher agrees with them both; however, it would be too extreme to believe only the brand or its employees could benefit from a learning-friendly work culture. This is because, what really makes a learning organisation is the people who work there. Just like what has been reviewed in this study's literature review section, a learning organisation *'facilitates the learning of its members and continually transforms itself'* (Pedler *et al.*, 1996). Therefore, through the process of transforming a brand into a learning organisation, not only everyone works with the brand but also the brand itself would be affected. That is, the employees are encouraged to *'continually expand their capacity'* (Senge, 2006) and the brand would keep itself competitive in the market. In particular, these changes could not be made only by its most senior person, but with the effort of its employees across all levels. Thus, it is also important for the chosen brand's frontline employees to have more opportunities to learn and understand the brand's business, as it is part of the initiatives that contribute to a learning work environment. Especially, the responses to question twelve (see Figure 4-24) in the questionnaire show ninety-five out of hundred candidates, who work as the chosen luxury brand's frontline employees, view the opportunity of learning at work as

an investment and are interested in getting themselves involved. It is clear that their mind has been shifted. The chosen brand is on its way to becoming a learning organisation.

Last but not least, it is worth discussing the negative feedback received from many participants of this study. They are about the disappointing reaction the management team had towards an upcoming training session. The reason for including this discussion here is because managers' behaviours could provide this study a clue about the potential challenge that would cause damage to the chosen brand's learning environment. According to some of the brand's frontline employees, they expected *'some insights about the training content'* from their managers before they went to attend a session. However, the reality was *'only after people went for it you might get some information about it'*. In particular, some interviewees have experienced something even worse, *'you are told to go for a training session and you have to go'* or *'it is more like what they tell you to do'*. Likewise, the responses of question nine (see Figure 4-24) also suggest the similar reality of the situation. Forty-five out of one hundred participants, who work with the chosen brand as its frontline sales associates, denied that they have been providing with a clear idea of the learning objectives before attending the most recent training sessions at work. This situation did not only get noticed by the chosen brand's frontline employees, but also by some of its managers. Some of them admitted that *'sadly we don't motivate our team to attend any training'*; *'I have never been asked to share anything about the structure or schedule before a session with my team'*. Meantime, some explained why this happened. It is because *'we do not receive enough information about the training except the date'*; or *'I don't remember the team organised this conference sent me any email about the structure or schedule in details'*. It is clear to notice the gap exists between the chosen brand's frontline employee's expectations and its manager's frustrations. The former felt disappointed at the fact that they only got told to attend sessions without any encouragement, while the latter felt annoyed because they failed to achieve what their members wanted. In the meantime, this message also shows this research the lack of communication between the chosen brand's managers and its retail trainers. This is against one of significant features of a learning organisation that has been widely accepted in the academic field, which is 'transparency' (Hayes *et al.*, 1988). This explains the reason why some managers could not recognise the importance of giving encouragement to their team members. It is because a learning-friendly work environment has not been ready at the chosen brand yet. It is still in transition. But most importantly, *'they are trying to make it right'* though *'you cannot change everything in one go'*, *'it builds over time'*. It is worth mentioning that a 'training calendar' has been planned in

some stores by the brand's retail trainers to provide the managers with '*a brief book with all the activities in it*'. It aims to 'start planting the seeds' through daily briefings to build the learning culture in the workplace gradually. This little change would eventually bloom, the researcher strongly believes.

4.3.2 Training Needs Assessment

It is worth mentioning that four of the interviewees are the chosen brand's retail trainers, and three of the remaining six are managers of the brand's London stores. Therefore, they provided this study with rich insights into the normal measurements and some real cases they experienced within the workplace to demonstrate how they usually identify a training need in practice. According to the conversations with them, there are two main types of training needs, which generally result from assessing either from the '*corporate level*' or from the '*store level*' (see Figure 4-1). The former '*ties in with what business strategy is*' and this type of training needs would normally be assessed by '*the central team*' '*from the head office*' to recognise whether or not '*something needs to be implemented globally*'. The latter is '*much more specific*' '*within the store*' and it would be analysed by the local trainer to look at '*the teams and the individual needs of those teams*' to decide whether or not there is a specific training need to be '*addressed locally*'. The data collected from observations can be applied to show how do these two types of training needs assessment work with real-life scenarios. For example, the one-day training session was designed for all the brand's frontline staff who work in its London stores. The primary purpose of it was to update them on the brand's new designer's debut collection. Therefore, the need for this training course can be viewed from the corporate level. On the other hand, the three-hour training program was developed only for the brand's sales associates who locate in the stores at the terminals of London Heathrow airport. The retail trainers who are in charge of these stores designed it for refreshing the members' memories of key products and service standards to get them ready for the coming festival season. Thus, this training need was assessed from the store level. To understand these collected messages regarding how the chosen brand normally accesses the training needs within the workplace, the theories that have been reviewed in this study also played a critical role. The chosen brand's regular activity regarding identifying the learning requirement from the store level can be categorised into the three-approach training needs analysis, which has been suggested by Kenny and Reid (1992, quoted in Buckley and Caple, 2009, p.76). This is because, both place great emphasis on job-related learning possibilities. Then, the brand's trainers access a training need from a corporate level meets Goldstein's suggestion of analysing

a company from a broader perspective instead of only considering the task analysis (Tannenbaum *et al.*, 1993). No matter what type of the training needs the brand's trainers identify, it is clear that the chosen brand works on the principles that are emphasised in the transitional training model (refers to Figure 2-3). That is, the brand always takes its business, goals, and values into consideration when it comes to identifying specific learning requirements within the workplace, which is what the researcher thinks that the chosen brand should be given recognition for.

In the meantime, the messages from the interviews also placed the emphasis on the partnership between the brand's retail trainers and its line managers in the process of training needs assessment. For example, some trainers stated that most of the time they would *'spend time on the shop floor with the team, to observe if there is an opportunity needed'*, while *'manager feedback is very important as well'* as they *'really understand the different levels everybody is at'* in their teams. Especially, *'certain figures'* would be applied as measurements to assess whether or not there is *'a gap in knowledge or behaviour'*, such as, *'NPS scores'* (Net Promoter Score), *'mystery shoppers'*, *'KPIs'* (Key Performance Indicator) or *'UPT'* (Units per Transaction). Then this is the moment that most of the trainers who participated in the interviews choose to *'speak to the managers'* to *'see if it is a big callout across their stores'* or *'the training needs with that specific team'*. At the same time, some managers would also choose to come to the trainers *'say when you are next in store please can we go through scarf styling'*. The involvement of line managers in training has also been appreciated by many scholars in the academic field. In this study's literature review section, this suggestion has been raised not only in the training needs assessment process but across all steps that are recommended in a training circle, for example, Sloman (2017); Baldwin and Ford (1988) and Goldstein and Ford (2002). The researcher also considers the collaboration between the brand's retail trainers and managers is a great approach, as with the effort of both it is more likely to identify the real learning needs. Just like what a trainer participant stated, *'it is really the case of changing the way we do things'*.

Then what did other people think about the practice that the chosen brand did for assessing the training needs within the workplace? The first question that was included in the online questionnaire was designed to explore this matter. Based on the responses received from one hundred of the chosen brand's frontline employees, the majority were satisfied with the knowledge they have learnt from their most recently attended training sessions at work (see Figure 4-24). Their positive responses indicate the chosen brand's success in identifying the

needs of learning within the workplace. Therefore, what have been delivered during those sessions were recognised as useful to the jobs by the trainees. However, some qualitative data that were collected from the in-depth interviews surprisingly revealed some negative situations that were caused by ineffectively conducted training needs assessment at the chosen brand. Some interviewees stated, *'the training was not relevant to Heathrow'*, *'no relevant training provided on how to use it at work'*, *'only thirty percent of what we learnt were useful for our daily work'*. No doubt these assessments failed, as the real training needs were not recognised. Therefore, the sessions were considered as irrelevant. Due to this reason, the disappointment was expressed, *'they assume what you need without asking'*; while some of them suggested the company to *'assess what we really need and deliver some relevant training sessions to meet our needs'* instead of *'deliver over and over again on the same knowledge'*. What they ask for has been defined as 'personal analysis' by Arthur Jr and colleagues (2003). Meantime, they also recognised its increasingly important role as the value of human assets have become the focus of a company. Therefore, they suggest considering the employee's opinions when it comes to assessing the learning opportunities within the workplace (Arthur Jr *et. al.*, 2003). This suggestion was passed on to the chosen brand's retail trainers during this study's interviews by the researcher. It has been recognised as a great idea as most of them were happy to give it a try, *'this is probably an opportunity that I could do'*. Meanwhile, there are *'training ambassadors, training champions or product specialists available on the shop floor with people all the time'*, as a result of the chosen brand's determination to build a learning work environment. Although there are a few inconsistencies in recognising the real training needs, the researcher is pleased to see some changes are happening at the selected luxury brand.

4.3.3 Design a Training Session

The conversations about the normal procedures for designing a training course were carried on with the chosen brand's retail trainers and managers who took part in this study's interviews. Firstly, they described the differences between the preparations for corporate-level training and those of a store-level training program in detail. When it comes to the design of a training session regarding the latest business updates, the routine at the selected luxury organisation is that the corporate training team from the brand's London head office *'provides all the training materials'*. *'What the corporate training function does'* is to work with the brand's other functional teams, for example, *'the merchandise team'* or *'the marketing team'* to gather all the information needed to prepare the training materials. After *'they set up the main framework and key aims'* and *'the delivery plan'*, the message would be passed to the retail trainers

'through the corporate trainings' and be *'carrying into the stores'* by the brand's retail training team. Although the training material is designed for all stores, it needs to be customised based on the different situation of each team by the retail trainers. For this purpose, the retail trainers would normally *'take things out that are irrelevant'* and decide whether the delivery plan *'is a good way of doing the training here or come up with something different'*. When it comes to the design of a training session to meet a local training need, the retail trainers would *'pull together different areas of already existing material to make our own like a collage'* and make a delivery plan accordingly. From the information they provided to this study, it is certain that the purpose of the brand's corporate training team is to evaluate the learning opportunities from the business level, while the main responsibility of the retail training team on the other hand is to observe the learning gap from the store level. Apart from a joint effort of these two training teams, the partnership between the chosen brand's retail trainers and its line managers has been brought up again by some interviewees when the topic regarding training design was under discussion. A chosen brand's manager explained how this partnership normally works in her case, *'part of my job is to assist the local trainer, sometimes deliver the training to my team with the material made by the trainer, sometimes I did everything by myself from material to the delivery'*. The idea of involving managers in the process of training design suggested by other scholars has been discussed in the literature review section of this study, for example, Sloman (2017); Buckley and Caple (2009). It is certain that managers play a significant role in assisting trainers in understanding their audiences better. However, this participant also complained about the *'downfall'* of this collaboration. She stated, *'sometimes nobody checked on the content of the training I delivered to my team, it is only my perceptions of things'*. The researcher considers this matter as a challenge that the chosen luxury brand needs to be aware of. But overall, she approves of the situation of either two training teams or trainers and managers working together to design a training session at the chosen brand.

One of the biggest emphasis in the process of the training design most interviewees placed was on the training methods. On one hand, *'it depends on what the message you are conveying'*. On the other hand, *'who learns and how'* plays a critical role, as everybody is different regarding their ways of learning. For example, some prefers *'something practical'* *'with the real scenario'* while others *'don't necessarily like doing activities'*. Therefore, when the retail trainers *'mix up colleagues'* to involve *'lots of people who are from various background and nationalities'* in one training session, they need to focus more on their audiences in order to *'design one that would suit all'*. What the chosen brand's retail trainers expressed has also been

discussed by many scholars. For example, ‘trainer-centred strategy and learner-centred strategy’ (Buckley and Caple, 2009, p.189). Correspondingly, *‘it depends on what the message you are conveying’* can be understood as the ‘trainer-centred strategy’, therefore, the retail trainers who provided this study with this message, prefer using their judgement to make decisions on the training design. Then, the message *‘who learns and how’* can be interpreted as the ‘learner-centred strategy’. In this case, the partnership between trainers and line managers has been recommended by Sloman (2017). It has also been considered as an important way of working at the chosen luxury brand, as *‘they are there every day, it is their team; they know them well’*. Then how did the chosen brand’s frontline employees react to their most recent training sessions? The researcher designed the eighth question in the questionnaire to discover the brand’s frontline employee’s opinions on this matter (Figure 4-24). The responses to this question show how much the majority enjoyed the activities included in their most recent training experience within the workplace, as seventy-five out of hundred participants expressed positivity towards this question. This result can be understood as the proof that *‘the ways of learning they prefer individually’* have been taken into consideration by the trainers of the chosen brand. As a conclusion, the designs of these sessions were successful.

Apart from training methods, an intense discussion on training schedule also caught the researcher’s attention during the in-depth interviews. According to some interviewees, who work in the chosen brand’s retail training team, the arrangement on both training time and the length of a course is carefully made, though it is a tough decision on *‘taking a big group of people out of the shop floor to do training’*. Normally, they have to *‘sit with manager and look at rota’* to fix a time together. The trainee’s availability would result in condensing that session to make it *‘fit within half an hour framework’* or end up with trainers changing their schedule to make it happen. No matter what, they would always *‘discuss with the team together to figure out what is the best’*. However, some managers told the researcher their side of the story, for example, some of them said, *‘I didn’t know anything about the last training, they (the trainers) only asked me to book our team in and send everybody to the training based on the training schedule they sent to me’*. Likewise, some of the brand’s front-line employees also gave different voice to this matter during this study’s interviews. According to these interviewees, they believe that they *‘don’t get to choose the time for training’*. *‘You are told to go, and you have to go’* is their reflection on the situation they experienced. Some of them claimed that the reason they could not attend any session recently was due to *‘staff shortage’*; while others complained that she had to give up her break time due to *‘an overlap’* existed between the

course and her work time. Overall, this interviewee's words can be quoted here to summarise the main points of the dissatisfaction these frontline employees experienced with the training schedule, *'you do not get to say if you want to go or if you think it is necessary for you to attend, your opinion is not important. It is more like what they tell you to do'*. The researcher also dealt with the same situation when she attended the three-hour training session as a participant to conduct the observations (see Figure 4-14, Category 1: "AGREEMENT ON SCHEDULE"). She recorded it in her fieldnotes, *'I didn't know that I needed to go to this session on that Wednesday. I was supposed to start my shift from 3 pm. I only got told to go to attend this program on that Wednesday morning. I had no choice of other date but had to go. But it normally takes me three hours on the way to work, the sudden change on the time when I had to get to the training venue, it made me have to rush myself'*. It was not a pleasant experience to her. By comparing the ideas from both sides, although trainers worked hard on planning a session, some of the trainees still felt disappointed at the schedule. As the training time arrangement is usually made between trainers and managers, it seems there is a disconnect between the decision-making and the communications with the employees on the agreement. It also indicates an ineffective partnership between the chosen brand's retail trainers and managers in these cases.

Last but not least, a discussion about whether it is feasible to include an evaluation plan in the process of training design was held with all the interviewees, who work at the chosen luxury brand as its retail trainers. Their opinions vary from person to person based on the individual work experience (see Figure 4-6). Some of them accepted the idea of having an evaluation plan prepared at the beginning, as they claimed in the interviews that *'when you set up the objective, you need to know what your evaluation is'*. From this point of view, the evaluation plan would *'potentially influence'* *'how you deliver it'*. Therefore, it is necessary to prepare an evaluation plan in the training design stage before a training session is delivered. Meanwhile, there are also some of them agreed on *'having 'a loose framework of what exactly you are looking for'*, but *'just a thought step'*. Therefore, it might change while delivering. However, others had different opinions, as they thought *'until you put it into practice, we are not able to evaluate it'*. Therefore, *'launch it first'* to *'run it with real people'*; and then collect the feedback to evaluate the session. Although there were three different views expressed by the interviewees, they mainly discussed their opinions from two directions. That is, one group of them decided to place the evaluation plan in the training design stage, while the others included it in the training delivery stage. However, the researcher considers these two different ideas of

evaluation as two types of evaluation. One is the evaluation of the training session itself, while the other is the evaluation of its effectiveness. Therefore, the researcher kept the idea of preparing an evaluation plan in the step of training design, as it is important to have a clear idea of what to achieve and how to evaluate at the beginning. It acts similarly as the training objectives, which have been considered as ‘guidelines for course design’ (Buckley and Caple, 2009). This plan might change after the delivery, but it could be applied as a framework to deal with the adjustments.

Overall, the effort on producing well-designed training materials has been recognised by the majority frontline staff who took part in this study’s questionnaire (see Figure 4-24) as sixty percent of the respondents liked the presentation slides used in their most recently attended training program at the chosen luxury company (Question Five); eighty-two out of hundred respondents considered the structure of their most recently attended training session was easy to follow and understand (Question Three). Despite this, some improvements would be suggested by the researcher to the company to ensure the standard of training materials would be consistently complied by both its trainers and managers.

4.3.4 Training Delivery

After a training session is designed and scheduled, it will be delivered as planned. Because of the fact that retail managers also take the ownership in training at the selected luxury company, most of the training sessions are delivered by both trainers and managers. Normally, retail trainers will ‘provide’ the chosen managers ‘with the relevant material’. In theory, trainers would also prepare managers for the coming training program, as they claimed in the interviews ‘If I am not delivering the training, what I would do is I would get together with the managers, so, this is the deck, these are the objectives, this is what we want to achieve, and this is how we plan to deliver it’. However, some of the brand’s managers criticised the retail trainers for failing to help them to get ready for delivering a training session during the interviews of this study, as they claimed that they ‘didn’t get trained’ before they went to train their team members but ‘read all the training materials’ and ‘absorb the information’ by themselves. Or, the material the trainers sent to them ‘is actually not the material for the training but something made by themselves, for example, it may contain some information from the magazines about our certain product or collection or news about the company but it is really vast, and they expected the managers to provide this kind of information to the team. But it takes time to make it ready for other team members. Therefore, it is a bit frustrated’. As a consequence, some of the brand’s frontline employees discussed their frustrations at not being

able to understand the content of a training session they attended with the researcher in the interviews, as they have been *'told to read the slides without giving any explanation on the content'*. In the meantime, the researcher also experienced a dry presentation conducted by a store manager in the one-day session that she observed as a participant when she was working at the selected luxury brand (refers to the third trainer's performance presented in Figure 4-18; the codes "READ EVERYTHING WORD BY WORD" and "FAILED TO ENGAGE"). According to the fieldnotes, *'The slides were not well organised, as he kept everything on the screen. Instead of focusing on the key knowledge, he read everything on the slides word by word. There was no eye contact between him and the audiences. As his part was arranged as the end of the morning session, everyone was exhausted after the whole-morning intensive learning. His teaching style made the whole situation even worse. I started to hear people chatting. I also saw a lot of participants checking the time. During the time when he was teaching, there was no activity, there was no interaction'*. The experience raised the researcher's doubt about manager's performance in delivering a training session. Without having a good understanding on the content and the confidence in presenting in front of a large group, how could they deliver an effective training course? This is the situation that requires the selected luxury company to investigate and make improvements.

The researcher does not intend to send a purely negative message and deny all the efforts in achieving the effective training delivery by the chosen luxury company. There is also rich evidence collected during this study to suggest that many of the brand's frontline employees had memorable training experience in the workplace. They complimented some of the brand's trainers on their professionalism. In the in-depth interviews, some interviewees claimed that *'I enjoyed most of the training programs that I went at work'*; *'I remember the training about the Chinese New Year, I found it quite interesting, so that one stick in my mind'*; *'I remember that trainer, she was very professional and good at the job'*; *'we were pretty comfortable to express thoughts'*; or the session was *'interesting but challenging'* and *'I enjoyed it'*. During the observations, two retail trainers organised the one-day session left the researcher a deep impression. In her fieldnotes, she recorded, *'The first trainer welcomed us when we arrived. She did not only greet us warmly but also motivated us to introduce ourselves. she successfully broke the ice and got us relaxed before the session started. ... Her formal opening set up high expectations towards the brand's new runway collections. It effectively encouraged us to make a commitment to this session. Then she applied the storytelling technique to show us the background and the inspirations behind the show. The slides were well organised. She well*

prepared the material with simple but conclusive bullet points. She knew the context really well. She kept herself facing the audiences when she was teaching, and she properly read our reactions and used her body language to interact with us. ... The second trainer taught us the knowledge of the new women collections. Instead of telling the stories, she asked us to feel the fabric and try styling with these new collections in groups and to share our opinions on the selling points we picked afterwards. The combination of teaching and group activity made us fully engaged' (refers to the first and second trainer's performance presented in Figure 4-18). Then what about the other participants' opinions on this matter? According to the responses to some questions included in the questionnaire, seventy-eight percent of the participating frontline staff of the chosen luxury company agreed that the learning objectives of the latest training session they joined were achieved effectively (Figure 4-24, Question Two); sixty-four percent of them enjoyed their most recent training (Figure 4-24, Question Six); seventy-seven percent of them agreed that the multimedia materials were clearly visible and audible in their latest training session (Figure 4-24, Question Four); and seventy-two percent of them agreed that the trainer of their most recently attended training session was knowledgeable about the subject (Figure 4-24, Question Seven). From these figures, it is clear to notice the majority of the training sessions organised by the chosen brand's trainers within the workplace have been successfully delivered.

When the researcher discussed the subject of the training delivery with some retail trainers from the chosen brand during the interviews, there is one opinion shared by most of them caught her attention. They all suggested including an evaluation step in the training delivery stage in this study's theoretical framework (refers to Figure 3-1). Of course, the researcher understands the importance of evaluation as it has been recognised as one of the most critical steps in the empirical studies that she reviewed when she planned on conducting this research, for example, The Systematic Training Model (Figure 2-1); The Restructured Systematic Training Model (Figure 2-2) and A Transitional Model (Figure 2-3). However, she only took the evaluation of the effectiveness of a training program into consideration. She failed to identify the difference between these two types of evaluations in a training circle. They are both about keeping a training course on the right track, but their focuses vary. According to the explanations given by the brand's retail trainers in the interviews, '*An evaluation for the training product*' would be applied to examine whether its design is successful, while to '*evaluate the success of the program*' aims to testify its impact on trainee's performance or attitude's change after they returned to their jobs. They are both evaluations but represent two

different steps within a training framework. As the content of this section is mainly about the training delivery, the evaluation of a training course itself is the focus here. The evaluation regarding training effectiveness will be discussed later in the next section separately. To examine the success of a program is to test the feasibility of its design, as what a retail trainer who participated the interviews of this study explained, *'design is the theory, but until you put that into practice on the training stage, you will be not for certain whether that is a good plan or not'*. Therefore, the pilot session is recommended. This is because the first one is for testing. It provides the trainer with an opportunity to *'run it with real people'* and *'engage with people's reactions'*. During the first initial training, the observed trainee's responses and *'their feedback'* could help the trainer to understand *'how it went, what would we do differently next time'*. In the meantime, *'some other things might come up'* during the delivery process. Therefore, it is an ongoing process till the result is satisfying. As what one of the chosen brand's retail trainers that the researcher interviewed in this study discussed, *'once you launch, you evaluate the program itself and you re-assess, once you are satisfied, then you launch again'*. The suggestion about evaluating the training design while delivering the session echoes what Thorne and Mackey's opinion (2003, p.71), a *'meaningful evaluation allows you to monitor results and to make any appropriate changes...also provides you with information that you are "doing a good job" and allows you to celebrate your success'*. It also inspired the researcher in improving her training framework designed on the purpose of this study.

4.3.5 Training Evaluation - Training Effectiveness

After a training session is delivered, *'there will be an evaluation for the implementation of the training product'*, which is to *'evaluate the success of the program'*. It is without doubt one of the most important steps within a training circle, as it has been described as *'a necessary weapon in a training manager's armoury'* (Sloman, 2017). In comparison with the evaluation of the training course itself, it aims to track the impact of the newly learnt knowledge on the changes in the employee's attitudes and work performance after a training course is delivered. Then how to track how much of the training content has been successfully transferred to the trainees's jobs? Goldstein and Ford (2002, p.138) suggested collecting *'descriptive and judgemental information'*. What are the thoughts shared by the chosen brand's retail trainers on this matter? According to their conversations, the usually applied approaches include *'knowledge checking and observations'*, while business-related figures, for example, *'UPT'* or *'the results from the mystery shoppers'*, will also be taken into consideration. The researcher saw the similarity between what the scholars suggested and what the trainers applied in

practice. The knowledge the brand's retail trainers learnt from quiz and observations can be understood as 'descriptive information'; while the facts they found out through examining the business-related figures can be categorised into 'judgemental information'. Therefore, the theory approves the effectiveness of the criteria the chosen brand's retail trainers usually apply to measure the impact of a delivered training course in practice.

At the same time, the partnership between the chosen brand's managers and retail trainers was emphasised again in the interviews to demonstrate that they '*work together*' on following up on the effect of trainings within the workplace. The involvement of line managers in this stage should be a good call. However, the researcher received a few complaints from some retail managers during the interviews. According to them, they were not asked to '*follow up*' or '*there was no evaluation plan to monitor team's progress*' after some training events, though the significance of training evaluation has also been recognised by the brand's managers, as they expressed '*we should evaluate the effectiveness of every training session to make sure people actually obtained the key knowledge from the session and are willing to apply them at work, this is what the brand needs to improve*'. On the other hand, some trainers also gave voice to this matter during the interviews. They argued, '*the managers spend a lot time on the shop floor with the team, we would think they observe their performance and they check on the business scores and provide us with the feedback*'. It is apparent that a lack of communication exists that would damage the partnership between the chosen brand's retail trainers and managers. In the long term, this would negatively affect training effectiveness. Meanwhile, there is another risk that was brought up in the interviews, which would also prevent the chosen brand achieving training effectiveness. According to some retail trainers, a few effective evaluation tools are no longer used at work, for example, '*certificate*' or '*must-knows*' that used to be applied '*every six months*' to bring back people's memories on the core knowledge. As a consequence of inconsistency in assessing knowledge, skills and attitudes that trainees have learned throughout trainings, the most frequent response that the researcher received from interviewees who are the frontline employees of the selected luxury company is '*no one checked on us whether we actually understood the material afterwards, so some of the members missed the sale of the new trench coat because the lack of enough product knowledge*'; or '*I cannot remember much about that training*'. No doubt, '*things need to be refreshed*' as '*after certain amount of time, all of that knowledge just dropped off*'.

Although having a long memory is critical, the determination to apply the newly acquired information to the jobs could also affect training effectiveness. According to the conversations

with some retail trainers, the differences in trainee's behaviours after returning to work from a training session can be understood as the result of *'the immediate transfer'*; and the changes observed in trainee's attitudes towards work is recognised as the result of *'the long-term transfer'*. Coincidentally, the researcher recalled some scholar's expressions she read about from the empirical studies, which are 'generalization' and 'maintenance' (Baldwin and Ford, 1988, refers to Figure 2-6). These two have been considered as two dimensions of training transfer (Blume *et al.*, 2010). After attending a training course, trainees return to their jobs. They are expected to show trained behaviours to respond to different types of requirements at work. Take the examples that are given by the chosen brand's retail trainers, they witnessed some brand's frontline employees discussing *'how to implement the new floor setting from the training session in store'*, or *'telling these stories to their customers'* or *'sharing with team the new knowledge from the training as soon as return to work'*. At this stage, the changed behaviours are determined by how much trainees learnt from the session. They can only simply apply what they have been taught in response to their daily work. Eventually, the newly learnt behaviours became something they are familiar with, and they can apply them flexibly as they are their own work experience. Then, their attitudes change due to the enhanced capability of applying a high level of skills at work. This is the next stage in training transfer. The changed behaviours have been retained. As a result, some frontline employees stated in the interviews, *'I feel more and more comfortable in applying the knowledge at work'* or *'training makes me confident at work'*. From the comparisons the researcher made between the theory and the current situation of the chosen brand, it is certain the brand's retail trainers who attended this study's interviews showed an excellent knowledge of training transfer. But, how about the brand's frontline employees? What did they say regarding this matter? According to the responses to the tenth question of the online questionnaire (Figure 4-24, Question Ten), the majority of the participants (seventy-six percent) were confident about applying the newly learnt knowledge from the most recent training sessions organised by work to their jobs. That means it has a high possibility of successful transfer if they are determined. Furthermore, based on the results of question eleven of the online questionnaire (Figure 4-24, Question Eleven), sixty-six out of hundred respondents agreed that they were offered the opportunities to apply the changed behaviours to their jobs. Therefore, it is more likely that these participants would successfully transfer the newly learnt skills to respond to different work settings with both their determination and the motivations from the brand. In this case, the training sessions organised by the chosen brand would mostly achieve effectiveness.

Despite this, the researcher heard different voices during the interviews regarding training transfer. They said, *'only 30% of what we learnt were useful for our daily work'* or *'some of the selling techniques from the trainings cannot be applied at work'* or *'there is a gap between training and receiving the new products'*. There is no doubt that all these issues they addressed would have a negative impact on training effectiveness. Each of them represents a different stage within a training circle. For example, the first feedback reflects a failed training needs analysis, as most of the training content was considered as irrelevant to their jobs. The second piece of information may indicate an unsuccessful training needs assessment or less opportunities within the workplace. The last one reveals an inappropriate training design. But they still share similarities. That is, they all suggest the correlations among different stages in a training circle. Eventually, these aspects would all have an impact on training effectiveness. Similarly, the theories that were included in this study's literature review section also approved the fact that training is an on-going process (for example, Figure 2-1; Figure 2-2; Figure 2-3).

4.3.6 Training Strategy in the Selected Organisation

All the findings that are related to the chosen luxury brand's current training initiatives were discussed in the above sections. The similarities and differences that existed in the data collected through three different data collection methods were interpreted and compared to present a whole story from both the corporate and the individual side. In order to provide readers with a clear view of the current training strategies that are adopted in the chosen luxury company, the researcher will summarise the main points in the following paragraph first and then express her thoughts on them afterwards.

About its current training and development strategies, three key elements were repeatedly discussed by most of the participants who took part in this research. Firstly, the brand's senior management team has placed an emphasis on aligning its training initiatives with its business strategies since the brand's new CEO joined the company in 2017. As a result, its training strategies are fully integrated into the brand's business goals and plans. Therefore, the potential training needs would not only be considered and assessed from a store level. The training needs assessment would also be affected by the brand vision and its latest business strategies. Secondly, the brand promotes the idea of learning within the workplace. As a result, an online platform is developed to ensure a broad range of learning material is easily reachable. In the meantime, various training opportunities are provided for the brand's employees across all levels to give them the access to every part of the business. At last, the chosen brand aims to build a supportive learning environment within the workplace. To achieve this goal, the

partnership between its line managers and retail trainers is introduced. Thus, training is not only the retail trainer's job, instead, trainers are working with line managers together to make sure the support is always there.

From these training policies, it is clear to see the importance of training and development has been recognised by the senior management of the chosen luxury brand. But what could be the impact these policies make on the brand's people? Firstly, all of them highlight the brand's determination to become a learning organisation. As discussed in this study's literature review section, a learning organisation is believed to be transparent across all levels (Hayes *et al.*, 1988), and it commits itself to facilitating 'the learning of its members and continually transforms itself' (Pedler *et al.*, 1996). In the case of the chosen luxury brand, the first benefit of being a learning organisation is improving the communication within the workplace. Having an open conversation across all levels of the company increases its employees' opportunities to get involved in the brand's business to create a sense of belonging within the workplace. As the benefits that are linked to higher workplace belonging have been recognised as higher organisational commitment and engagement (Carr *et al.*, 2019). Especially, 'the need for relatedness' (Markus and Kitayama, 1991), which is considered as human nature (Maslow, 1981; Thoits, 1982), can help the luxury business to bond its people to share the same brand identity. Therefore, cultivating a workplace belonging has become a focus for some luxury companies, for example, Hermès (2019). Meanwhile, the chosen brand has been recognised as one of the most famous British luxury brands globally. In the case of the chosen luxury brand, with its exclusive British identity, it has over one hundred and sixty years of history. In the luxury world, the unique brand history has been recognised as 'a cult of inherited values' (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012, p. 93) and the 'proof of the brand's power and ability to survive' (Gutsatz and Auguste, 2013, p.2). Creating more learning opportunities within the workplace helps the chosen brand's employees to carry on the company's glories. Ultimately, the continuous learning and development provided at work would benefit the chosen brand with 'a fundamental mind shift' (Jones and Hendry, 1994). Just as what an interviewee expected, *'the brand would give you the luxurious mindset to adapt yourself to the job in the luxury industry'*.

Then, what could these training policies change its frontline employees' performance particularly? Firstly, having a learning-motivated work environment, the chosen brand's frontline employees are entitled to reach a broad range of learning materials within the

workplace. These learning opportunities will prepare them with rich knowledge of the essence of the luxury business. As discussed earlier in this study's literature review part, the luxury business is much different from the non-luxury business, for example, its unique business models (refers to Luxury Business Model), the types of its clients (refers to The Luxury Clients), and their purchase intentions (refers to Luxury Purchase Intention). Their work performance would be undoubtedly improved with the help of these learning opportunities within the workplace. But most importantly, their attitudes towards working in the world of luxury would also be changed, as they commit themselves to 'living the brand' (Ind, 2007). In general, those who work in the front line are viewed as 'a reliable port for the customer, inspire trust, strengthen the relationship between the company and the customer (Pignataro, 2019, p.93). In the case of the luxury business, they are not only act as 'the interface of the brand with the customer' (Pinkhasov and Nair, 2014, p.155), but also as the brand ambassadors to 'represent it at its best' (Pignataro, 2019), because 'luxury brands have a lot to tell, to show, to reveal, to say and to make people experience' (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012, p.268).

4.3.7 Challenges

Although the chosen luxury brand's current training policies are recognised as effective in preparing its frontline employees with the luxurious mindset, some challenges that would prevent this from happening were also revealed during this research. In the following paragraphs, the researcher will firstly provide the readers with a whole picture of how the chosen brand's trainers, especially its retail trainers, perform their jobs within the workplace. It will be explained by following the steps that are included in a training circle. Meanwhile, the complaints received from the chosen brand's frontline employees during this research will also be included in the discussion. As a result, the issues that would damage the effectiveness of the chosen brand's training practice will be demonstrated.

Firstly, the interviewees who work as the chosen brand's retail trainers explained how they perform their jobs on a daily basis. If there is a corporate-level training session that needs to be delivered to the store level, the chosen brand's corporate training team '*designs the session*'; '*sets up key aims and delivery plans*'; '*prepares the training materials*'. The role that the brand's retail trainers play in this case is to '*tweak*' these materials for different teams and '*deliver this to stores*'. On the other hand, when there is a need observed from a store level, most of the retail trainers who participated in this study described their routines, '*pull together different areas of already existing material to make our own like a collage*'. Afterwards, some

of them would add the prepared information simply *'in the morning briefings'*; while some would figure out *'a loose framework'* and *'key objective'* before the delivery. These training sessions can be delivered either by the retail trainers, or *'by the managers, or we have the training ambassadors who support us with the delivery of the training'*. After the sessions, the methods the brand's retail trainers usually apply to evaluate *'whether the training is successful or not'* include, *'observe in the store'*; *'asking people questions on the shop floor'*; *'track business figures'* and *'management's feedback'*. It is clear to see a training circle from their conversations, from analysing a training need to training design and delivery to training evaluation, just like what was suggested in the systematic training model (refers to Figure 2-1). Specifically, the learning requirements are assessed from both the corporate and the store perspectives. Based on the specific training need, a corporate-level training is normally designed by the brand's corporate training team. The delivery plan and the materials are then passed to the brand's retail training team to deliver to the store level. A store-level training course, on the other hand, is usually planned and delivered by the retail trainers. After sessions, the effects of training are tracked and evaluated by retail trainers. Meantime, there are supports from training ambassadors and managers. They work together with the retail trainers in every step of a training circle.

Then what are the complaints received from the chosen brand's frontline employees regarding their training experience during the research? Their comments will also be presented and discussed by following the steps in a training circle. Firstly, regarding the training needs assessment, they said, *'some trainings they just deliver over and over again on the same knowledge'*; *'my training on this area is very limited'*; *'a lot of the training programs that we were asked to attend are irrelevant'*; *'your opinion is not important'*. Among these comments, the word *'irrelevant'* and the expression *'over and over again'* indicate the knowledge that these training sessions offered did not satisfy those trainees' needs. At the same time, the complaint about *'limited'* training opportunities revealed the possibility that the individual's opinions were not taken seriously as the potential learning requirements by the chosen brand's retail trainers and managers. However, apart from the organisational analysis and the task analysis, the personal analysis has also been suggested to be considered (Arthur Jr *et. al.*, 2003). Since a training needs assessment is defined as *'the process of deciding who and what should be trained'* (Salas and Cannon-Bowers, 2001), these training needs analyses were not successfully conducted. Then, about training design and delivery, they stated, *'I don't get to choose the time for training'*; *'there was an overlap between the training and my work time, and I had to give*

up my own break time'; *'read the slides without giving any explanation on the content*'; *'the chosen manager is not professional enough to deliver the training*'; *'I don't like this kind of activities, I prefer a bit more interactive*'. Among these complaints, the first two described their experience of an unsuccessfully planned training schedule, which can be viewed as evidence to suggest that the chosen brand lacks a learning work environment. This is because a learning organisation 'facilitates the learning of its members' (Pedler *et al.*, 1996), but the chosen brand did not achieve this goal in these cases. These participants were included in a training course; however, their availabilities were not considered when the training schedules were made. This negative experience could demotivate the brand's frontline employees and make them less enthusiastic about the learning opportunities at work. The rest comments are all about the training delivery. They all suggest that some of the chosen brand's retail trainers and line managers were not able to deliver an affective session. According to the STAR training design model (refers to Figure 2-5), 'transfer' the knowledge is only one of the goals to achieve in the process of training, meanwhile, a trainer's responsibilities also include, to 'stimulate' the trainee's interest, to give trainees opportunities to 'apply' what was taught through activities, to 'review what's changed as a result of the experience' at the final stage of learning (Bray, 2006). Apparently, these trainees' interest was not aroused by either simply reading the slides without giving any explanation or the trainer's unprofessional behaviours. These could also be viewed as the outcomes of an ineffective training design. As what Buckley and Caple (2009, p.189) recommended, there are 'trainer-centred strategy and learner-centred strategy' that can be applied to design a training course. However, it is critical to understand the targeted audiences well first, no matter which approach is preferred. This is also what these interviewees tried to express in their conversations. At last, regarding training transfer and evaluation, they commented on, *'I could not immediately use the new knowledge at work after training because we still didn't receive the new collection in store, and it has been a month since we attended that training*'; *'I can't remember much about that training honestly*'; *'we do need a little bit encouragement to apply the new knowledge*'; *'I think only 30% of what we learnt were useful for our daily work, I am sure this is not only me felt in this way*'. From these messages, there are three reasons that caused poor training transfer results. They are an ineffective training needs analysis, a lack of evaluation and unavailable support from work. These are also highlighted in Baldwin and Ford's model of the transfer process (refers to Figure 2-6). Therefore, it is certain that training is an on-going process, the steps that are included in this circle affect each other (refers to The Restructured Systematic Training Model). Overall, by interpreting these negative opinions about the chosen brand's training practice, it is clear to see

the brand's retail trainers and managers' inconsistent performance in organising and delivering training sessions within the workplace.

In the researcher's opinion, two main reasons affect the brand's trainers' work performance and prevent the brand's training practice from achieving effectiveness in the long term. For these purposes, they can be considered as challenges. The first challenge is related to the chosen brand's learning environment. It is certain the brand has committed itself to encouraging its people to learn at work and aims to become a learning organisation. Especially, the brand introduced a joint effort of both the corporate and retail training teams to create more transparency across the company. Meanwhile, the partnership between retail trainers and line managers has been formed to improve the effectiveness of the brand's training practice. However, these new changes just started. By quoting what the interviewees said, *'they are trying to make it right'* though *'you cannot change everything in one go'*. It is certain, the learning environment is building at the chosen brand, but it is not ready yet. The second challenge is regarding the training framework. The evidence collected from this research revealed a fact that there is not an agreed framework to guide the brand's retail trainer's work. They cannot conduct corporate-level trainings on their own initiative but only follow what they have been told by the brand's corporate training team. Regarding store-level training sessions, the way they prepare, and deliver may vary due to their different experiences in the training area. Taking the four retail trainers who took part in this study's interviews as an example, two of them have professional experience as trainers, while the rest were promoted to this role after their long experience with the brand as its senior sales associates. Apparently, this is not the only case, as these interviewees shared, *'the rest of the training team here in the UK were all sales associates'*; *'I don't think they had any specific training background'*. However, *'there is not any workshop for us to improve training skills'*. In particular, the involvement of the brand's managers in the process of training has been introduced. They are not professional trainers and are lack of training experience. In this case, an agreed training framework is necessary as it would not only, provide the chosen brand's trainers with the systematic training principles. Meanwhile, it would also prevent this group of less-experienced trainers from performing their jobs consistently. In conclusion, these are believed as the main challenges that the chosen luxury brand is facing, which would damage the effectiveness of its learning activities in the workplace. However, the researcher was not intent on criticising the current training practice in the chosen luxury brand. Instead, she affirms the brand training strategies

to successfully prepare its frontline employees with the right mindset to work in the luxury segment but suggests the brand to make some improvement to achieve this goal.

4.3.8 The Evolution of the Training Framework

The reason why the researcher planned on conducting this research at the very beginning was due to her interest in training and development. Especially after she started working at the selected luxury company as a part-time sales associate, her work experience inspired her to explore the role of training in the luxury segment. This idea began to take shape when the researcher tried to find answers from the empirical studies. After reading up the topic of training, it is clear that the role of training becomes more and more important in today's organisations, as employees are recognised as the most valuable asset of a company and their growth is vital to development and success of a business. At the same time, the evidence also demonstrates that the luxury market grows dramatically, and it needs to reshape its business to adapt to the emerging market and potential customers. Although these two topics have attracted a large amount of attention in the academic field, there are few articles on the link between the function of training and building a strong luxury brand. Especially, after the researcher discovered that there is not a fixed training framework adopted by the chosen brand's retail training team to guide their daily work. Therefore, she made the decision to develop a training framework that would be suitable for luxury companies as a contribution of this study.

During the journey of this research, this training framework has been modified three times. In the early stage of this study, the dominant training models from the literature gave the researcher the idea that training is an ongoing process, for example, the systematic training model (see Figure 2-1). At the same time, both the restructured systematic training model (see Figure 2-2) and the transitional model (see Figure 2-3) helped the researcher to identify the main stages within a training circle, in the context of business. In addition, more information gathered from the empirical studies confirmed the importance of these identified stages that are suggested to be included in a training circle. Therefore, the theoretical framework of this study (see Figure 3-1) was formed after reading on the topic of organisational training. It consists of three main stages, which are pre-training stage, training stage and post-training stage. A training circle starts with assessing a training need (refers to Training Needs Assessment), which takes not only organisational needs (business mission and task), but also its employee's opinions (individual analysis) into consideration. Then, the supportive learning environment within the workplace is built to motivate people to learn at work (refers to Organisational Learning Environment). The appropriate training methods are chosen to

achieve learning objectives (refers to Training Design & Delivery). At last, a plan for evaluating the training session with some potential measurements are suggested to be made beforehand to ensure the training objectives will be met during the training delivery. Then it comes to the training stage. After the session is delivered, it is the time when the trainees apply what they learnt to their jobs, which starts with a behavioural change (immediate transfer) then an attitudinal change (long-term transfer), in the post-training stage (refers to Transfer of Training). The ideas of both these two types of transfer have been promoted by many scholars in the field, such as, ‘generation’ and ‘maintenance’ (Blume *et al.*, 2010); or the two conditions of transfer that were emphasised in Baldwin and Ford’s model of the transfer process (see Figure 2-6). At the end of a training circle, a training evaluation is conducted to examine the effectiveness of the session (refers to Training Evaluation). The result of a training evaluation is potentially a training need of another training program; therefore, training is an on-going process (this view has been demonstrated by other scholars and has been explained in section 2.1.2.3). The theoretical framework of this study is shown in Figure 4-25.

Figure 4-25. Training Framework – The Theoretical Framework

However, further changes were made to the theoretical framework after the analysis of the interview data was completed. Based on the evidence collected from the in-depth interviews, training is proved as an ongoing process, and some steps that are included in the theoretical framework are also proven as valid in practice (see Figure 4-7). However, it is suggested that

unless the supportive work environment is ready, it could not be built in a short period of time. By quoting the words of one of the interviewees who works as the chosen luxury brand’s retail trainer, ‘*this is something that comes over time in terms of creating that learning environment, it builds over time*’. Due to the critical role that a learning environment plays in the training process (refers to 2.1.2.4c), it has been moved to the outer layer of the training cycle to indicate its influence on every stage that is included in a training circle. Apart from this, the information from interviews helped the researcher to understand the relationship between transfer of training and training evaluation (see Figure 4-5). On one hand, the goal of successful training transfer is to achieve training effectiveness. That is, an effective training would either have an impact on trainee’s behaviours or attitudes towards work (refers to immediate training transfer and long-term transfer, Figure 2-6). On the other hand, the purpose of conducting an evaluation is to examine whether or not the delivered session is effective (see Figure 2-7). Therefore, both the situation of training transfer and the result of training evaluation could be applied as indicators of the success of a training program. As a result, the researcher chose to only place training evaluation in the post-training stage instead of having both training evaluation and training transfer as in the theoretical framework (see Figure 4-25). The second version of the training framework of this study is presented in Figure 4-26.

Figure 4-26. Training Framework – Transitional Stage

However, it was modified again after finishing the analysis of the observation data. The interpretation of the observation data reveals the detail of the training delivery stage. It mainly emphasises how flexible a trainer needs to be to facilitate a training session (see Figure 4-23). But at the same time, the problematic situation would provide the trainer some clues on how to improve the training design, for example, trainee’s reactions and their feedback. The real-life scenario made the researcher realise that the importance of evaluating the training program itself is also suggested in the interview data, as some interviewee who works at the chosen luxury brand as its retail trainer stated *‘design is the theory, but until you put that into practice on the training stage, you will be not for certain whether that is a good plan or not’*. But the researcher overlooked it as there was only one participant raised it. However, it appears that only if the arrangement of a program satisfied the trainees, they would be more willing to be involved with learning. This would also affect training transfer afterwards. Because of its critical role in achieving training effectiveness, it is added to the training framework; and is emphasised and presented as another circle within a training loop. They are not independent but have an impact on each other. The final version of the training framework is shown in Figure 4-27.

Figure 4-27. Training Framework – The Researcher’s Final Version

Chapter 5 - Concluding the Study

5.1 Conclusion

The researcher started this project four years ago, as a result of her interest in the role of training in the luxury segment. When it was in its early planning stage, the purpose of the research was set to examine whether or not training plays a vital role in communicating a luxury company's marketing strategies with its frontline employees. In other words, the researcher expected to discover a relationship between the training function and the implementation of the marketing campaigns in a luxury organisation. Why focused on the impact on marketing strategies mainly, this was due to the researcher's work experience at the time when she was preparing for the research proposal. She was a part-time sales associate at one of famous British luxury brands, which was later chosen as the case to study in this project. At the time when she joined the company, the luxury brand was promoting the idea of engaging customers through social media to raise public awareness of its new collections. It was a very creative move that the company made when comparing with other luxury brands in the market, as most of them mainly depended on their in-store services to interact with the customers by then, which is due to the different business rules followed by the luxury brands (refers to The Paradox of Luxury-goods Marketing). To the researcher, who was new to the business environment, the first training program that she attended at the beginning of her career with the company left her a deep impression; and she assumed that organisational trainings would be adopted primarily for the marketing purposes. This assumption had a direct influence on her decision about the research objectives. After the researcher made up her mind on the study aim, she started to look into the possibility of applying training at work to enhance the implementation of a company's marketing initiatives in the context of the luxury industry, through reading the empirical literature in the field. At the same time, the researcher planned to conduct a qualitative research in the luxury organisation that she was working at, to explore its current training strategies regarding delivering the company's marketing directions to its frontline employees. In other words, she decided to have a better understanding of what were its training policies and whether they were effective in delivering the objectives regarding marketing strategies.

During reading literature on training, it is evident that the critical role of training, especially training's strategic alignment in organisations, has been widely accepted, for example, Goldstein (1980); Carey (2000); Salas and Cannon-Bowers (2001); Arthur Jr *et al.* (2003). The

knowledge obtained from empirical studies, broadened the researcher's understandings of the influence of training on organisations. It is more than only enhancing the implementation of marketing campaigns. Instead, the use of training has been closely aligned with a company's business strategies in most of the cases, as the role of training has been considered as an 'integrated, strategic component of the organization' (Salas and Cannon-Bowers, 2001). About the world of luxury, on the other hand, the literature helped the researcher to understand what luxury really means, in terms of the essence of the luxury business, such as the brand's heritage and values, which are clearly demonstrated in Figure 2-9. At the same time, the information about luxury brand's unique business models, for example, The Pyramid Business Model (Figure 2-11) and The Louis Vuitton Diamond Model (Figure 2-12); and the theories regarding the values luxury consumers perceive as a result of the luxury consumption (A Luxury Value Model, Figure 2-16; The Luxury Brand Purchase Intention Model, Figure 2-17) distinguish the luxury segment from the other business sectors. By combining with her work experience, the researcher gradually recognised the critical role that the frontline employees play in the luxury business. They are not only working as the sales in stores, but also assisting the company to create the brand-related dreams (Figure 2-9) to drive the interest from luxury consumers. More importantly, the frontline employees represent the luxury brand directly to the public. Therefore, the researcher concluded from all the evidence that the priority to luxury business is to transform the frontline staff into excellent brand ambassadors, as 'luxury brands have a lot to tell, to show, to reveal, to say and to make people experience' (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012, p.268). For this purpose, training has been considered as a useful tool to achieve this goal. Firstly, training could enhance a luxury company's internal communications, which offer its frontline staff more opportunities to 'see the bigger picture' (Pignataro, 2019, p.93), such as the luxury world, the luxury business models and its exclusive features. This could help the brand to achieve higher organisational commitment and engagement, as its employees, especially those who work in the frontline, would feel a sense of belonging in the workplace (Carr *et al.*, 2019). In the meantime, the use of training could enhance the luxury frontline employee's work skills. As a result, they are capable of delivering 'high-quality brand content' to 'create the dream and to recharge the brand's value' as excellent brand ambassadors (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012, p.255). By taking all of these into consideration, the researcher modified the original research question to broaden the research aim from examining the role of training in delivering a luxury brand's marketing strategies to evaluating the use of training to prepare the luxury frontline employees with the luxury mindset. Although the reviewed empirical literature on both organisational training and luxury management brought the

researcher more insights into the research topic, most of the training related sources are out of date and only little evidence which suggests the use of training in luxury organisations for the purpose of this study. The gap between the existing knowledge and the proposed research objectives clearly demonstrated the necessity of conducting this research. Meanwhile, the researcher decided to develop a training framework that could suit the luxury business as a contribution, as it has come to her knowledge that training is a systematic process but most of the well-known training models were introduced to the field around the early sixties, for example, The Systematic Training Model. But it is worth mentioning that those existing training models, which are presented in this study's literature review section (see 2.1.2.3) have had a great impact on the development of the theoretical framework in this study (see Figure 3-1), for example, its round shape and the key elements included in a training circle.

While the research topic was refined and the decision on developing a training framework at the end of this study was made, it was the time to review the research design. The researcher was planning to conduct this study in the chosen luxury brand, at where she used to work. This was because the idea of this study was inspired by her work experience at the beginning, and her role as the brand's employee would increase the chance to get approval to access the data. She planned on giving interviews to both the frontline staff and the trainers of the company to explore the research objectives from more dimensions (the details about why the researcher made this decision and how did these interviewees get picked were included in section 4.1.1.1), for example, trainee's training experience and trainer's training design routine. Meanwhile, the researcher also decided on observing a couple of training sessions at work as a participant to understand training delivery with real-life scenarios. Even after the main research question was refined, both the in-depth interviews (see Interviews) and the observation (see Participant Observations) data collection methods were still considered as effective to meet the purpose of this study. However, the researcher considered a possibility of giving voice to more of the brand's frontline employees. Thus, the questionnaire data gathering method (see Questionnaires) was also chosen to not only reach more participants, but also complement the qualitative data collected by interviews and observations. As a result, this research was designed to apply mixed methods (see Research Methods – Mixed Methods) instead of only the qualitative approach. But most of the data were expected to be gathered through interviews and observations while only twenty-five percent of the data was quantitative (see Figure 3-2), as this study was aiming to explore the chosen luxury brand's training practice first and evaluate its effectiveness when the researcher had a good understanding on the whole situation

afterwards. In total, the researcher gave one-to-one interviews to ten interviewees, observed two training sessions, and received one hundred responses out of a targeted population of three hundred (see Sampling) to the online questionnaire. In the process of the data analysis, the researcher insisted on analysing the qualitative data manually, as the data collected through in-depth interviews and observations were the participants' personal feelings and experience. From the researcher's point of view, processing the data by applying the electronic methods, the personal factors could not be fully taken into consideration. However, coding all the qualitative data of this research manually was a complicated process. The researcher had to code the data twice, and she learned a lot from the mistakes. During the first time, her understandings of the theoretical framework affected her judgement on the interpretations of the data. As a consequence, the categories that were developed in the first coding cycle were determined by the researcher's opinions that were formed based on the knowledge from the literature she reviewed in the early stage. Fortunately, the researcher realised what she did contradicted the principles of grounded theory method, which has been chosen to guide both the data collection and the data analysis stages of this research (the details were explained in 3.2.4 & 4.2.1.1). The coding process has been conducted for the second time to avoid any bias towards interpretations of the raw data. During this time, the researcher let the data speak for itself. With applying Strauss and Corbin's three-phased coding method (1990), the links among different categories were revealed. On the other hand, the quantitative data collected from the questionnaires was analysed by using Microsoft Excel to aggregate the responses to generate reports of the statistical results (see Figure 4-24).

By comparing and interpreting the data collected in this research, the results answered the research questions. Regarding the chosen luxury brand's current training policies, first of all, the brand's corporate training team and its retail training team work closely to deliver the brand's latest messages to the store level. Therefore, the training function is aligned with the chosen brand's business strategies. Secondly, a partnership between the chosen company's retail trainers and its line managers is introduced into the workplace. As a result, the store-level training sessions are not only the brand's retail trainers' responsibility. The managers would also be expected to assist the retail training team with the design and the delivery of training programs. At last, an online-learning platform has been built and shared with all the chosen brand's employees. As a result, various learning materials are expected to be easily reachable by the brand's people to provide them with more learning opportunities at work. It is clear to see that training function has been placed as the core to the chosen brand's business. As a result

of implementing the identified training strategies at the chosen brand, the researcher believes that the brand will gradually become a learning organisation. Because both corporate and retail training teams work in close collaboration on updating the employees across all levels on the brand's latest business-related information will create an open company culture. Meanwhile, the online learning platform will encourage the brand's employees to explore the brand's business and continuously achieve personal growth within the workplace. By involving the brand's line managers in training will enhance the learning atmosphere and motivate their team members to learn actively in the workplace. Under these circumstances, the chosen brand can be viewed as a learning organisation, which is defined as a company creates 'transparency across all levels' (Hayes *et al.*, 1988) and 'facilitates the learning of its members and continually transforms itself' (Pedler *et al.*, 1996). Then how will these training policies have an influence on preparing the chosen brand's frontline employees to become brand ambassadors? It is evident that excellent luxury frontline employees are considered as those who can 'share the mystery, the spirit of the place, of the objects, and the time embodied in each object' (Kapferer and Bastien, 2012, p.236); as they have the knowledge of 'the key elements that have passed on from generation to generation to nurture the brand's DNA' and 'the craftsmanship experience' (Gutsatz and Auguste, 2013, p.55); also 'the brand's culture... its identity, and its philosophy' (Pignataro, 2019, p.71). On the other hand, a brand ambassador is considered as those 'who are genuine supporters and devotees of a brand' (Wang and Hariandja, 2016). Therefore, luxury brand ambassadors are not only those frontline employees who could deliver the brand messages, but also those who could represent the brand at its best. In other words, being knowledgeable is not the only quality of a luxury brand ambassador; the willingness to live the brand is also critical. Therefore, the researcher believes that the learning opportunities offered by the chosen brand would help its frontline employees to possess these characteristics of a brand ambassador. Likewise, there was a note of optimism in some interviewee's voice as one of them said '*the brand would give you the luxurious mindset to adapt yourself to the job in the luxury industry*'. At the same time, some challenges, which would prevent the chosen brand's training policies from being effective, are also recognised. Firstly, the chosen brand's retail trainers have not adopted a fixed training model to guide their daily work, resulting in their inconsistent training performance at work. At the same time, this also affected their collaboration with the brand's line managers. Therefore, even the brand has committed itself to building a learning environment within the workplace, this study still collected a few complaints from its frontline employees about lacking a sense of belonging at work, for example, '*your opinion is not important*'; '*I don't think they value us as what they*

supposed to'. These negative feedbacks were given by those with low workplace belonging. To them, the chosen brand is not their brand, and they do not live the brand. Because 'living the brand requires commitment and sincerity' (Ind, 2007). If the chosen brand's frontline employees are not willing to live it, it is impossible that they will represent the brand at its best in their day-to-day jobs as brand ambassadors. Overall, just as what an interviewee concluded, *'they are trying to make it right'* but *'you cannot change everything in one go'*; and the researcher believes a well-designed training framework is a key factor in helping the chosen brand to improve the current situation regarding achieving the training effectiveness. Therefore, the training framework planned and revised through this study's whole research process is considered as the contribution to this study.

5.2 Contribution to Practice

The researcher conducted this study with the aim of exploring the impact of organisational training on transforming the mindset of luxury frontline employees from not only selling the products but also to represent the brand's unique identity and values at work. The exploration was carried out in a well-known British luxury brand to study its training practice. As a result, a training framework (refers to Figure 4-27) was developed at the end of this research with the purpose of enhancing the effectiveness of training programs that are designed and delivered in the selected company, for example, to streamline the training design process and to improve the training delivery. Specifically, it has been noticed that there was not a well-designed training framework adopted by the brand's retail training team, therefore, this training framework was designed to provide its retail trainers with guidance in training design, delivery and evaluation. Moreover, there are two areas of focus that have been emphasised in this training model. Firstly, the step of creating a learning environment has been placed in the outer layer of a training circle. The idea of this design was inspired by divergent opinions expressed by interviewee participants on the situation of the chosen luxury brand's learning environment. It appeared the encouraging learning atmosphere in the company was not well built, which was recognised as one of the main challenges that would affect the success of training practise (the details are included in section 4.3.7). By considering participant's advice (the code 'CULTURE OF TRAINING, MENTALITY, COME BEFORE', Figure 4-7), the stage of creating a learning environment has been placed as the premise that a training program would be based. Meantime, it would also affect each step of a training circle. In other words, a supportive learning environment in the workplace has a significant impact on achieving training effectiveness.

Then, the inner evaluation circle has also been emphasised in this training framework. This decision was made to enhance the effect of a training design. By assessing the success of the session itself, trainers would examine the feasibility of the chosen training methods and training tactics, which would also have an influence on the effectiveness of the training activities at the chosen brand. As the training model (refers to Figure 4-27) was designed to help the chosen company to overcome the identified challenges to enhance its training effectiveness, it is considered as a contribution of this study to this luxury brand. Furthermore, it can also be contributed to the luxury business sector as the importance of communication in luxury business has been proven (refers to Internal Branding & Internal Communication).

5.3 Recommendations

In order for this training model to be implemented successfully in the chosen luxury brand, some recommendations are included in this section. Firstly, having a supportive learning work environment ready is critical to the success of the adoption of this training framework. This is because a learning company culture would increase the possibility that the training cycle, which is illustrated in the proposed training framework of this study, would perform effectively. Secondly, the researcher suggests the chosen luxury brand to assess training needs from a broader point of view, at the time that the training model designed in this study is applied. The reason why this recommendation is given is due to the uniqueness of luxury business. Therefore, the researcher considers that it would be necessary to assess training needs from a bigger picture during the development of this training framework. Instead of only taking certain tasks into consideration, the chosen luxury brand's business mission, values, brand tradition, its customers and even the current trend in the luxury market would also be included when it comes to training needs assessment stage. The last thing the researcher would recommend to the chosen brand is to ensure the evaluation of both the effectiveness of a training program and the success of its design would be taken seriously. This is because these two types of training evaluation relate to each other in the proposed training framework. Only if the design has been proven as successful and satisfied by trainees, the knowledge gained from the session would be effectively applied to the jobs. That is the reason why the researcher set a step of planning the possible measurement for the later evaluation before the training delivery stage in the training framework. Furthermore, these recommendations would also be applied in other luxury companies. However, as the uniqueness of each luxury brand's business model, these

suggestions offered by the researcher would be slightly modified to fit the individual brand's various situations.

5.4 Limitations

As this four-year journey comes to an end, the researcher looked back on the things that happened during this period of time. It is worth mentioning that some limitations of this study might have an impact on the final results. The first one would be the time issue. As this project is part of the DBA programme (Doctorate of Business Administration), there is a limit on the time that the researcher was able to spend on completing the research. One of the research objectives was related to the chosen luxury brand's frontline employee's attitude change. This transformation from the mindset of a sales associate to a luxury brand ambassador takes time. Due to the limited time available, the researcher could not easily witness this change as a result of learning at work in the selected luxury organisation, though the importance of training in the luxury segment has been identified in this study. Therefore, the researcher suggests that a longer research time frame would be more suitable for recording a change in the participants' attitudes towards work over an extended period of time. Secondly, all the trainers took part in the interviews of this study are the members of the chosen luxury brand's retail training team. As a result, most of the information collected from the interviews were mainly the retail trainers' opinions on the research objectives. However, this is only one side of the story. Therefore, the recommendation on this issue would be to broaden the choice of suitable candidates in the future study, for example, the chosen brand's corporate trainers, to acquire more thoughts on the studied phenomenon. As the same concern that discussed above, it might be better if the results of this study could be tested in other luxury brands, as the aim of this research was not only about exploring the current training strategies practiced in the chosen luxury company, but also to reflect on the situation regarding learning at work in the luxury industry. Therefore, the result of a future study with more luxury brands included would be more convincing.

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Appendixes

Appendix A. Participant Information Sheet

1. Research Project Title

A Mixed-Method Study into the Effect of a Well-known British Luxury Brand's Training Practice on Transforming its Frontline Employees into Brand Ambassadors

2. Invitation

You are invited to take part in this research. Before you decide to do so, it is important that you understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and decide whether or not you wish to take part. Ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information.

3. What is the project's purpose?

The researcher intends to explore the current training strategies practised by the chosen company, which is one of the well-known British luxury brands, in regard to the effectiveness of the training activities on transforming its frontline employees into brand ambassadors. She expects to develop a new training framework that will be more effective in practice, based on the findings of this research.

4. Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen because you work at the selected company and have the knowledge about its training activities.

5. Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part, you will be asked to sign the Consent Form. You will be given a copy of both the Participant Information Sheet and the Consent Form. You can still withdraw at any time. You do not have to give a reason.

6. What will happen to me if I take part?

You will be asked to take part in an interview with the researcher which will approximately take 20-30 minutes.

7. What do I have to do?

You will be asked to describe your experience in training at work. All of the draft interview questions will be sent to you before the interview is conducted for your review. You can refuse to answer any of them that makes you uncomfortable.

8. What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

This research will not cause you any disadvantage or risk.

9. Will I taking part in this project be kept confidential?

All of the information that the researcher collects about you during the research will be kept strictly confidential. Anonymity is assured. All audio recordings, transcriptions and other raw and processed data will be destroyed after the research is complete.

10. Will I be recorded, and how will the recorded media be used?

You will be recorded during the interviews only when the permission has been gained from you.

11. What type of information will be sought from me and why is the collection of this information relevant for achieving the research project's objectives?

The interview questions will be designed about your experience in relation to the most recent training activity at work. Your feelings and experience are just what the researcher is interested in exploring.

12. What will happen to the results of the research project?

The results of the research will be used to understand the actions and procedures that are implemented in the chosen company, regarding its training practice. It is only for the academic purpose.

13. Contacts for further information

Name: Qi Liu

Email:

Thank you for taking part in this research.

Appendix B. Participant Consent Forms

Participant Consent Form

Title of Research Project

A Mixed-Method Study into the Effect of a Well-known British Luxury Brand's Training Practice on Transforming its Frontline Employees into Brand Ambassadors

Brief Description of Research Project

- Explore the current training strategies practised by the chosen luxury brand
- Develop a new training framework that will be more effective in practice

Contact Details

Name: Qi Liu

Email: [REDACTED]

Consent Statement

I agree to take part in this research and I am aware that I am free to withdraw at any point. I understand that the information I provide will be treated in confidence by the researcher and that my identity will be protected in the publication of any findings.

Name: [REDACTED]

Signature: [REDACTED]

Date: 15.10.18.

Participant Consent Form

Title of Research Project

A Mixed-Method Study into the Effect of a Well-known British Luxury Brand's Training Practice on Transforming its Frontline Employees into Brand Ambassadors

Brief Description of Research Project

- Explore the current training strategies practised by the chosen luxury brand
- Develop a new training framework that will be more effective in practice

Contact Details

Name: Qi Liu

Email: [REDACTED]

Consent Statement

I agree to take part in this research and I am aware that I am free to withdraw at any point. I understand that the information I provide will be treated in confidence by the researcher and that my identity will be protected in the publication of any findings.

Name:

[REDACTED]

Signature:

[REDACTED]

Date: 31.3.19.

Participant Consent Form

Title of Research Project

A Mixed-Method Study into the Effect of a Well-known British Luxury Brand's Training Practice on Transforming its Frontline Employees into Brand Ambassadors

Brief Description of Research Project

- Explore the current training strategies practised by the chosen luxury brand
- Develop a new training framework that will be more effective in practice

Contact Details

Name: Qi Liu

Email: [REDACTED]

Consent Statement

I agree to take part in this research and I am aware that I am free to withdraw at any point. I understand that the information I provide will be treated in confidence by the researcher and that my identity will be protected in the publication of any findings.

Name: [REDACTED]

Signature: [REDACTED]

Date: 23/10/2018.

Participant Consent Form

Title of Research Project

A Mixed-Method Study into the Effect of a Well-known British Luxury Brand's Training Practice on Transforming its Frontline Employees into Brand Ambassadors

Brief Description of Research Project

- Explore the current training strategies practised by the chosen luxury brand
- Develop a new training framework that will be more effective in practice

Contact Details

Name: Qi Liu

Email: [REDACTED]

Consent Statement

I agree to take part in this research and I am aware that I am free to withdraw at any point. I understand that the information I provide will be treated in confidence by the researcher and that my identity will be protected in the publication of any findings.

Name: [REDACTED]

Signature: [REDACTED]

Date: 20/05/19.

Participant Consent Form

Title of Research Project

A Mixed-Method Study into the Effect of a Well-known British Luxury Brand's Training Practice on Transforming its Frontline Employees into Brand Ambassadors

Brief Description of Research Project

- Explore the current training strategies practised by the chosen luxury brand
- Develop a new training framework that will be more effective in practice

Contact Details

Name: Qi Liu

Email: [REDACTED]

Consent Statement

I agree to take part in this research and I am aware that I am free to withdraw at any point. I understand that the information I provide will be treated in confidence by the researcher and that my identity will be protected in the publication of any findings.

Name: [REDACTED]

Signature: [REDACTED]

Date: 24/10/18

Participant Consent Form

Title of Research Project

A Mixed-Method Study into the Effect of a Well-known British Luxury Brand's Training Practice on Transforming its Frontline Employees into Brand Ambassadors

Brief Description of Research Project

- Explore the current training strategies practised by the chosen luxury brand
- Develop a new training framework that will be more effective in practice

Contact Details

Name: Qi Liu

Email: [REDACTED]

Consent Statement

I agree to take part in this research and I am aware that I am free to withdraw at any point. I understand that the information I provide will be treated in confidence by the researcher and that my identity will be protected in the publication of any findings.

Name: [REDACTED]

Signature: [REDACTED]

Date: 1/5/19

Participant Consent Form

Title of Research Project

A Mixed-Method Study into the Effect of a Well-known British Luxury Brand's Training Practice on Transforming its Frontline Employees into Brand Ambassadors

Brief Description of Research Project

- Explore the current training strategies practised by the chosen luxury brand
- Develop a new training framework that will be more effective in practice

Contact Details

Name: Qi Liu

Email: [REDACTED]

Consent Statement

I agree to take part in this research and I am aware that I am free to withdraw at any point. I understand that the information I provide will be treated in confidence by the researcher and that my identity will be protected in the publication of any findings.

Name: [REDACTED]

Signature [REDACTED]

Date: 18-12-2018

Participant Consent Form

Title of Research Project

A Mixed-Method Study into the Effect of a Well-known British Luxury Brand's Training Practice on Transforming its Frontline Employees into Brand Ambassadors

Brief Description of Research Project

- Explore the current training strategies practised by the chosen luxury brand
- Develop a new training framework that will be more effective in practice

Contact Details

Name: Qi Liu

Email: [REDACTED]

Consent Statement

I agree to take part in this research and I am aware that I am free to withdraw at any point. I understand that the information I provide will be treated in confidence by the researcher and that my identity will be protected in the publication of any findings.

Name: [REDACTED]

Signature: [REDACTED]

Date: 24/10/15

Participant Consent Form

Title of Research Project

A Mixed-Method Study into the Effect of a Well-known British Luxury Brand's Training Practice on Transforming its Frontline Employees into Brand Ambassadors

Brief Description of Research Project

- Explore the current training strategies practised by the chosen luxury brand
- Develop a new training framework that will be more effective in practice

Contact Details

Name: Qi Liu

Email: [REDACTED]

Consent Statement

I agree to take part in this research and I am aware that I am free to withdraw at any point. I understand that the information I provide will be treated in confidence by the researcher and that my identity will be protected in the publication of any findings.

Name: [REDACTED]

Signature: [REDACTED]

Date: 15/10/18 .

Participant Consent Form

Title of Research Project

A Mixed-Method Study into the Effect of a Well-known British Luxury Brand's Training Practice on Transforming its Frontline Employees into Brand Ambassadors

Brief Description of Research Project

- Explore the current training strategies practised by the chosen luxury brand
- Develop a new training framework that will be more effective in practice

Contact Details

Name: Qi Liu

Email: [REDACTED]

Consent Statement

I agree to take part in this research and I am aware that I am free to withdraw at any point. I understand that the information I provide will be treated in confidence by the researcher and that my identity will be protected in the publication of any findings.

Name: [REDACTED]

Signature: [REDACTED]

Date: 22/10/18

Appendix C. Sample of Raw Interview Data

Participant D: That is my point too. I think that is another thing, particularly in terms of, I guess it comes **under the methods** in some way. I was told **never put too much on the screen**. Because if you put too much on the screen, I might just give you a book, there is no point of me being there. So, my whole purpose is to **bring this to life**, yeah, that comes on the design but **also in the delivery**. And I guess that facilitation makes it (the session) applicable to your audience. **Think about your audience**. Is any language not barriers, but for example, I am London born and bred, I speak fast, I know I do, so I have to make sure even when I think I am **slowing down** this time I need to slow down further. Sometimes, training sessions can be **started off by asking the questions** straight away. And you as a person attending it, think, 'I just got here, I have no idea'. **Think about the delivery** sometimes, it can **set the tone**, we are sitting within that environment and also are setting in that tone in the actual delivery. Make sure you have materials, make sure you have time and you **understand the activities**, and also making sure when it comes to **the actual delivery**. For example, in onboarding, I don't know if you have been to one-day onboarding session.

Note: *The words highlighted in the interview transcript are examples of the initial codes in In Vivo coding stage. Some of them can be found in Figure 4-3. Interview Data - Axial Coding: Training Delivery Overview.*

Appendix D. Sample of Raw Observation Data

There was one trainer **welcomed us** when we arrived. She did not only greet us warmly but also motivated us to introduce ourselves to each other. She successfully **broke the ice** and got us relaxed before the session started. When the session in the morning officially started, it was still the same trainer gave us a formal opening. This time, she **explained the importance of this session**, as it is organised to educate us about the brand's new chief designer's debut collection. As **the brand was in the transition** after the former Chief Designer left the job after his 17-year journey with the company, it is necessary for us to **understand the changes** in not only design, but also company's business direction by learning from the new collections. Her formal opening set up high expectations toward the brand's new runway collections. It **effectively encouraged us** to make a commitment to this session. Then she applied the **storytelling technique** to show us the background and the inspirations behind the runway show. The **slides were well organised**. Instead of having everything listed, she well prepared the material with simple but conclusive bullet points. When she was presenting the slides, she did not only stare at the screen and read everything from the slides, instead, she **knew the context really well**. She kept herself facing the audiences when she was teaching, and she could properly **read our reactions** and use her body language to interact with us. Therefore, people were **concentrating** during the time when she was presenting her part in the morning session.

Note: *The words highlighted in the observation field notes are examples of the initial codes in In Vivo coding stage. Some of them can be found in Figure 4-5. Interview Data - Axial Coding: Evaluating Program Success Overview*

Appendix E. Analytical Process Leading to Figure 4-1

Both the code “CORPORATE LEVEL: DIRECTION FROM CORPORATE” and the code “STORE LEVEL: TEAMS, INDIVIDUAL NEEDS” indicate two specific types of needs assessment that explain the main category code “ASSESS THE TRAINING NEEDS” in specific details. The relationships among these two codes and the main category code are identified as follows.

Interview Data - Axial Coding: Training Needs Assessment 1

“NEVER RUNNING OUT OF THINGS” and “NEEDS ASSESSMENT IS IMPORTANT”, these two codes were generated in the interviews with the trainer participants when they were expressing their thoughts on the necessity of conducting training needs assessment as part of their day-to-day work. They discussed it from a business point of view, as they recognise the importance of embedding the training needs assessment into the company’s business strategy to update the corporate’s latest directions to its employees through trainings. Therefore, the researcher considered including these two codes within the boundary of the corporate level training needs assessment. The links among these three codes are identified as follows.

Interview Data - Axial Coding: Training Needs Assessment 2

“MANAGER, MORE CHOICES”, “YOUR OPINION, NOT IMPORTANT”, “ASK OUR OPINIONS” and “DON’T VALUE US”, these four codes describe the situations that happen within the context of assessing the individual needs. However, they represent completely different conditions. Firstly, it is clear to see the individual needs are divided into the manager’s needs and the other employee’s needs. When it comes to meet what managers want, it results in having more self-development options. By contrast, the opinions of others did not catch too much attention, as some interviewees passed the frustrated message through the interviews. Therefore, the researcher made the decision on including all these four codes within the setting of the store level training needs assessment. The relationships among these codes are presented as follows.

Interview Data - Axial Coding: Training Needs Assessment 3

Appendix F. Analytical Process Leading to Figure 4-2

To break this category into details, the five codes that represent the major factors in the training design process, which include the organiser, the location, the methods, the schedule and the content, are chosen to transform as the main subcategories in this group. These codes are “WHO ORGANISES”, “WHERE YOU PRESENT”, “WHAT TO ACHIEVE, HOW DELIVER”, “AGREE ON A SCHEDULE TRAINING” and “THE CONTENT OF TRAINING”.

Interview Data - Axial Coding: Training Design Factors 1

Among the rest codes in this category, both the codes “KNOWING WHO LEARNS AND HOW” and “BEST METHODS, DEPEND ON THE MESSAGE” reflect the importance of knowing the audience in achieving an effective training delivery. Therefore, these two codes are subordinate to “WHAT TO ACHIEVE, HOW DELIVER”. Regarding the choice of training methods, the code “DESIGN ONE SUIT ALL” and “MERGE PERSONALITY AND COURSE” represent two completely different ways that the trainers who attended the interviews normally adopt at work. This is why they are placed under the code “BEST METHODS, DEPEND ON THE MESSAGE”. In the meantime, the words of some trainee interviewees revealed a negative reality of the training situation they experienced, for example, “DON’T LIKE ACTIVITIES”, “PREFER SOMETHING PRACTICAL” and “NOT AT SCHOOL ANYMORE”. When they expressed their opinions on this matter, they expected to

have their ideas being considered by trainers regarding merging different personalities and the course design. Therefore, these three codes are under the subcategory code “MERGE PERSONALITY AND COURSE”. As a result, the relationships among these codes are demonstrated in the following figure.

Interview Data - Axial Coding: Training Design Factors 2

Appendix G. Analytical Process Leading to Figure 4-3

In terms of the training delivery, the code “TONES, BODY LANGUAGE, ACTIVITIES” gives a list of various training skills, while the code “THINK ABOUT YOUR AUDIENCE” places emphasis on the importance of the trainee factor. The code “EVALUATION: TRAINING PROGRAM ITSELF” identifies a requirement to consistently evaluate the design of a training session to meet the target audience’s learning preferences. By combing all these three codes together, it would result in an effective training delivery, which is exposed by the code “BRING THIS TO LIFE”.

Interview Data - Axial Coding: Training Delivery 1

Another code in this group “BEING FLEXIBLE TO FACILITATE SESSION” also indicates the relationship between the trainee factor and the choices of training techniques. Therefore, it is linked to the code “THINK ABOUT YOUR AUDIENCE” to fully emphasise the critical role of the targeted audiences play in achieving training effectiveness.

Interview Data - Axial Coding: Training Delivery 2

To elaborate on the subcategory “EVALUATION: TRAINING PROGRAM ITSELF”, the code “AN OPEN-TABLE DISCUSSION” provides the way to do it. As a result of having an

open discussion with a group of targeted learners, their negative feedback, such as, “NOT SATISFIED”, “CHOSEN MANAGER, NOT PROFESSIONAL”, “FEW PEOPLE THERE” and “NO ENOUGH EXPLANATIONS”, needs to be taken seriously by trainers to “IMPROVE” the design of the session; while the comments, for example, “INTERESTING BUT CHALLENGING”, indicates the course is “ENJOYED” and successful.

Interview Data - Axial Coding: Training Delivery 3

Appendix H. Analytical Process Leading to Figure 4-4

To elaborate on this category, it is clear to see that there are three determinants that affect what is happening in the process of creating a learning environment at the selected organisation. They are, “UNDERSTAND THE IMPACT”, “TRANSITION” and “LONG-TERM VISION”. The following diagram identifies the connections among the category and the subcategories.

Interview Data - Axial Coding: Learning Environment 1

Under the subcategory of “TRANSITION”, the codes are divided into two groups, which are the changes in trainee’s attitudes towards training programs at work and the measures that management takes for making this transition happen. There are six codes that are involved in this correlation that is presented in the following figure, they are “CHANGE, LITTLE BY LITTLE”, “MOTIVATION, CHANGE ATTITUDES”, “DON’T WANT TO ATTEND”, “TOLD TO GO, HAVE TO GO”, “NEED ENCOURAGEMENT FROM MANAGEMENT” and “YOU DID WELL”.

Interview Data - Axial Coding: Learning Environment 2

As what is clarified earlier, the subcategory of “UNDERSTAND THE IMPACT” refers to trainee’s perceptions of learning environment in the workplace. Therefore, “TREAT COURSES AS INVESTMENT” and “YOUR GROWTH MATTERS BRAND’S GROWTH” are included in this subcategory, and the relationships among these codes are shown in as follows,

Interview Data - Axial Coding: Learning Environment 3

To elaborate on the subcategory “LONG-TERM VISION”, it can be explained with the perspectives from both the corporate and individual level. About the company’s long-term vision regarding creating a learning-friendly work environment, the code “IMPORTANT, EVERYONE TO BE TRAINED” capture the action that is taken. About the changes in trainee’s attitudes towards training as the result of having a learning culture at work, there are three dimensions from “NICE TO LEARN, SHARE, DISCUSS”, “COMFORTABLE TO EXPRESS THOUGHTS” to “WILLING TO GET INVOLVED, MINDSET” and “MADE TIME FOR IT” till “HAPPY TO APPLY TO THE JOB”. The following diagram shows the connections.

Interview Data - Axial Coding: Learning Environment 4

Appendix I. Analytical Process Leading to Figure 4-5

To elaborate on this category, there are three main determinants that affect how to evaluate and what to achieve, regarding the effectiveness of a training session. They are, “EVALUATE WITH FIGURES, KNOWLEDGE CHECKS, OBSERVATIONS”, “IMMEDIATE TRANSFER, TELLING STORIES AND SALES” and “LONG-TERM, ATTITUDE CHANGED”.

Interview Data - Axial Coding: Evaluating Program Success 1

In this category, some codes, which are captured from the conversations with the trainer interviewees, for instance, “YOU DO FORGET THINGS”, “VIVIDLY, REMEMBER DETAILS” and “A LOT OF TIME, TEAM REMEMBER”. As these codes represent the results of some evaluations, the researcher places them under the subcategory “EVALUATE WITH FIGURES, KNOWLEDGE CHECKS, OBSERVATIONS”.

Interview Data - Axial Coding: Evaluating Program Success 2

Likewise, some of the codes are collected from the conversations with the trainee interviewees, for instance, “NOT THE CASE FOR US”, “IRRELEVANT”, “CANNOT BE APPLIED” and “ONLY 30%, LEARNT, USEFUL”. These messages reveal the first impressions that some sessions left the trainee participants at the time when they attended. These codes can also be understood as the results of immediate training transfer. Therefore, they are placed under the code “IMMEDIATE TRANSFER, TELLING STORIES AND SALES”.

Interview Data - Axial Coding: Evaluating Program Success 3

In this group, other two codes also demonstrate trainee’s attitude change. They are, “GAIN CONFIDENCE” and “A LITTLE KNOWLEDGE, BENEFIT CAREER”. By contrast, the former indicates positive result, while the latter shows the opposite. These two are chosen to represent both sides of the opinions regarding the influence of a training session in a long-term.

The connections among these codes are presented in the following figure.

Interview Data - Axial Coding: Evaluating Program Success 4

Appendix J. Analytical Process Leading to Figure 4-6

Firstly, both the code “MERGE WITH TRAINING STAGE” and “AFTER SESSION” indicate the possible stage to place an evaluation plan in a training cycle. The code “UNTIL YOU PRACTICE, NOT ABLE TO EVALUATE”, on the other hand, explains the reason why the evaluation plan should be considered after a training session. Therefore, the relationships between these codes and the main category code “ESTABLISH FROM BEGINNING, EVALUATE AT THE END” are illustrated in the following figure.

Interview Data - Axial Coding: Evaluation Plan 1

In the meantime, the idea of “EVERY POINT, AN EVALUATION” is suggested by some trainer interviewees based on their work experience, as they understand it as “A CHECKING” to “KEEP YOU ON TRACK”.

Interview Data - Axial Coding: Evaluation Plan 2

Appendix K. Analytical Process Leading to Figure 4-24

- Training Needs Assessment

Among these twelve questions (**Error! Reference source not found.**) that are included in the questionnaire, only the first question is about training needs. As the responses to the first question presents, seventy-nine out of hundred participants chose to agree (fifty percent) or strongly agree (twenty-nine percent) that they were satisfied with what they have learnt from the most recent training sessions. Apart from them, ten people preferred not to give the answer (ten percent, neutral), while the rest eleven disagreed (ten percent) or strongly disagreed (one percent) with the statement. The responses of this question can be interpreted as a positive result of successful training need assessments that were conducted by the trainers of the selected luxury brand. That is, only when a real training need is recognised and met through delivering a particular training session, the trainees would be satisfied with the knowledge that was taught as it would be useful to their jobs.

Responses to Question 1

- Training Design

Among these twelve questions in the questionnaire (**Error! Reference source not found.**), three of them were designed to reflect on the training design, which are questions three, five and eight. Regarding the participants' most recent training sessions, the third question is about

the structure of the session. The fifth question mainly discusses the presentation slides, and the question eight focuses on the activities.

Regarding the results of question three, eighty-two out of hundred respondents chose to agree (fifty-seven percent) or strongly agree (twenty-five percent) that the structures of their most recently attended training sessions were easy to follow and understand. By contrast, there are eighteen participants either had no strong opinions (ten percent) on the investigated area, or eight of them disagreed (seven percent) or strongly disagreed (one percent). The responses of this question can be understood as a positive result of well-designed training programs organised by the trainers of the selected luxury brand.

Responses to Question 3

About the responses of the fifth question, sixty out of hundred participants had a positive opinion, as thirty-six of them agreed and twenty-four out of these sixty people strongly agreed that the presentation slides used in their most recently attended training programs were well-designed and appealing. In the meantime, twenty-four out of the rest forty respondents did not pick either positive or negative answer instead they chose neutral, while fifteen people disagreed, and one strongly disagreed. Based on the data, it is clear that most of the respondents were satisfied with the design of the slides that were presented in the latest training sessions that they attended. But the negative response from the small group of the participants also suggests the inconsistency in the preparation of the training slides at the selected luxury company.

Responses to Question 5

In relation to the results of question eight, seventy-five out of hundred participants chose to agree (fifty-four percent) or strongly agree (twenty-one percent) that the activities in the most recent training sessions that they attended satisfied them. By comparison with them, sixteen out of the rest twenty-five respondents preferred to not give an answer, while the rest nine had a negative attitude (eight of them disagreed and one strongly disagreed). The responses of this question can be interpreted as an affirmative, regarding the employment of the well-planned activities in the recent training session by the trainers of the selected luxury brand.

Responses to Question 8

- Training Delivery

Among these twelve questions in the questionnaire, there are four questions that were designed to examine the training delivery, which are questions two, four, six and seven. In relation to the most recent training sessions that the target population attended at the selected luxury brand, question two aims to examine the success of the training delivery by achieving the learning objectives. Question four focuses on checking the physical settings of the training program, for example, the application of multimedia. The sixth question discusses the interactions between the trainers and the trainees during the training delivery, and the seven question is about the trainer’s performance.

Regarding the results of question two, seventy-eight out of hundred participants had a positive opinion, as fifty-eight of them agreed and twenty out of these seventy-eight people strongly agreed that the learning objectives of the latest training session they joined were achieved effectively. In the meantime, there are thirteen out of the rest twenty-two respondents neither agreed nor disagreed on the statement, while nine of the rest group of people held a negative opinion as seven of them disagreed and two strongly disagreed. As a significant amount of the target population observed their improved understandings on what was taught in this course, it is believed that their most recently attended training sessions were successfully delivered by the trainers of the chosen luxury company. The responses can also be viewed as the result of an effective evaluation at the end of the training.

Responses to Question 2

About the responses of the fourth question, seventy-seven out of hundred respondents chose to agree (forty-five percent) or strongly agree (thirty-two percent) that the multimedia materials were clearly visible and audible in their latest training sessions. By contrast, there are twenty-three participants either had no strong opinions (thirteen percent) on the examined area, or ten of them disagreed (nine percent) or strongly disagreed (one percent). The responses of this question can be interpreted as an affirmative, regarding the application of multimedia in the recent training sessions by the trainers of the selected luxury brand.

Responses to Question 4

In relation to the results of question six, sixty-four out of hundred participants enjoyed their most recent training sessions, as thirty-eight of them involved themselves in it and twenty-six of them were fully engaged. By comparison with them, twenty-four out of the rest thirty-six respondents reported their involvement in that session as about average, while the responses of the remaining twelve people are below average. Therefore, it is positive that most of the respondents enjoyed and fully engaged themselves in the most recent training sessions they attended, which indicates successful deliveries of the sessions by the trainers of the chosen luxury brand recently.

Responses to Question 6

Regarding the results of question seven, seventy-two out of hundred respondents chose to agree (thirty-seven percent) or strongly agree (thirty-five percent) that the trainer of their most recently attended training session was knowledgeable about the subject. However, there are twenty-eight participants either had no strong opinions (nineteen percent) on the investigated area, or nine of them disagreed (eight percent) or strongly disagreed (one percent). The responses of this question can be interpreted as an affirmative, in relation to the trainer’s performance in the recent training session conducted at the chosen luxury company.

Responses to Question 7

- Training Transfer

Among these twelve questions in the questionnaire, there are two questions that were designed to investigate the training evaluation, which are questions ten and eleven. Regarding the most recent training sessions that the respondents joined at the selected luxury brand, question ten examined their understandings on how to transfer what they learnt at work. Question eleven focused on checking whether it is possible to apply the new knowledge to the job at the chosen luxury firm.

About the responses of question ten, seventy-six out of hundred respondents chose to agree (forty-eight percent) or strongly agree (twenty-eight percent) that they fully understood how to apply what they were taught in the most recent training courses to their jobs. By contrast, there are twenty-four participants either preferred not to answer this question (fourteen percent), or ten of them disagreed (eight percent) or strongly disagreed (two percent). The responses of this question can be interpreted as an affirmative, regarding a possible effective training transfer.

Responses to Question 10

Regarding the results of the eleventh question, sixty-six out of hundred participants had a positive opinion, as thirty-eight of them agreed and twenty-eight out of these sixty-six people strongly agreed that they had the opportunity to apply the newly learnt knowledge from the most recent training courses that they attended at work. In the meantime, there are twenty out of the rest thirty-four respondents neither agreed nor disagreed on the statement, while fourteen of them held a negative opinion as twelve of them disagreed and two strongly disagreed. Therefore, it is believed that it is possible to transfer what the participants learnt to their jobs at the selected luxury organisation. It can be explained as a result of a successful training needs assessment or a supportive work environment.

Responses to Question 11

- Learning Environment at Work

Among these twelve questions in the questionnaire, there are two questions that were included to collect the current situation of the learning environment at the selected luxury company, which are questions nine and twelve. In relation to the most recent training sessions that the respondents experienced at work, question nine examined whether the supportive learning culture has been created at the chosen luxury firm. In the meantime, question twelve was designed to check whether the benefits of learning at work have been widely accepted by the employees.

About the responses of question nine, forty-six out of hundred participants responded positively, as twenty-two of them agreed and twenty-four out of these forty-six people strongly agreed that they have been motivated before attending the most recent training sessions by providing with a clear idea about the learning objectives. However, there are fifty-four respondents either preferred not to answer this question (twelve percent), or forty-two of them disagreed (thirty-nine percent) or strongly disagreed (three percent). It is obvious that there is a significant portion of the target population have a negative attitude towards the current learning environment at the selected luxury brand.

Responses to Question 9

Regarding the results of question twelve, ninety-five out of hundred respondents have a positive attitude, as forty-eight of them agreed and forty-seven out of these ninety-five participants strongly agreed on viewing the opportunity of learning at work as an investment. Only five preferred not to answer this question, while no one responded negatively. The responses of this question can be interpreted as an affirmative, which indicates that the benefits of learning at work have been widely accepted by most of the employees of the chosen luxury organisation.

Responses to Question 12